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Contributors	Batoul Hojeij (CICERO); Jolanda Luime (EMC); Ilja Tchetverikov (CICERO); Cátia Gonçalves (PSR); Ana Rodrigues (PSR); Georgios Apostolidis (AUTH); Vasilis Charisis (AUTH); Eleni Vasileiou (AUTH); Sofia Dias (FMH-ULISBOA); Laura Coates (OUXF); Kenana Muaiad Al (TUM); Sílvia Reis (PLUX); Prince Ofori (HUJI); Francesca Levi-Schaffer (HUJI); Kosmas Dimitropoulos (CERTH); Ilias Papastratis (CERTH); Nikos Melanitis (AIN); Christos Chatzichristos (AIN)
Reviewed by	Eleni Vasileiou (AUTH) Kosmas Dimitropoulos (CERTH)
Approved by	Leontios Hadjileontiadis (AUTH, Project Coordinator)
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Contents

List of Figures	8
List of Tables.....	9
List of abbreviations	10
Executive summary.....	14
1 Introduction	15
1.1 Document scope.....	17
1.2 Document structure	18
2 Symptoms of psoriatic arthritis	19
2.1 Fatigue.....	19
2.1.1 State-of-art	19
2.1.2 Measurement	21
2.1.3 Datasets	22
2.2 Pain	23
2.2.1 State-of-art	23
2.2.2 Measurement	25
2.2.3 Datasets	27
2.3 Stiffness.....	27
2.3.1 State-of-art	27
2.3.2 Measurement	30
2.3.3 Datasets	43
Section highlight.....	43
3 Triggers and consequences of flare in psoriatic arthritis.....	44
3.1 Mood.....	44
3.1.1 State-of-art	44
3.1.2 Measurement	45
3.1.3 Datasets	46
3.2 Stress	46
3.2.1 State-of-art	46
3.2.2 Measurement	49
3.2.3 Datasets	51
3.3 Sleep	51
3.3.1 State-of-art	51
3.3.2 Measurement	52
3.3.3 Datasets	55

3.4	Physical activity and fine motor skills	55
3.4.1	State-of-art	55
3.4.2	Measurement	60
3.4.3	Datasets	61
3.5	Bowel movements	62
3.5.1	State-of-art	62
3.5.2	Measurement	63
3.5.3	Datasets	64
3.6	Environmental factors.....	65
3.6.1	Weather.....	65
3.6.2	Air pollution.....	65
	Section highlight.....	66
4	Markers for the development and monitoring of psoriatic arthritis	67
4.1	Markers based on clinical examinations.....	67
4.1.1	Joints inflammation/enthesitis/dactylitis.....	67
4.1.2	Nail	72
4.1.3	Skin	74
4.2	Markers based on optoacoustic imaging	78
4.2.1	State-of-art	78
4.2.2	Measurement	79
4.2.3	Datasets	81
4.3	Laboratory markers	81
4.3.1	DNA.....	81
4.3.2	Gut microbiome.....	85
	Section highlight.....	87
5	AI-based models for the detection/prediction of disease activity and flare	87
6	Implications for clinical practice.....	101
6.1	Recommendation systems	101
6.1.1	State-of-art	101
6.1.2	Datasets	104
6.2	Serious Games.....	104
6.2.1	State-of-art	104
6.2.2	Datasets	109
	Section highlight.....	113
7	Methods for datasets harmonisation and curation	113
8	Conclusions.....	118
	References.....	120

Appendix I Supplementary material 162

List of Figures

Figure 1 Example of positive feedback loop triggering inflammation in PsA driven by key immune cells and cytokines.	15
Figure 2 Baseline model for predictors of inflammation in PsA based on literature, and patients and physicians' perspective.	16
Figure 3 Digital biomarker measuring devices, tasks and features.	17
Figure 4 Connection between data sets identified in Task T2.1 with task T2.4, and tasks of WP3 and WP4.	18
Figure 5 Central and peripheral mechanisms in fatigue. BH4, tetrahydrobiopterin; GTP-CH1, guanosine-triphosphate cyclohydrolase-1; IDO, indoleamine 2,3 dioxygenase; TRP, tryptophan; KYN, kynurenine; NMDA, N-methyl-D-aspartic acid. Source: (Dantzer et al., 2014)	20
Figure 6 Pain traveling from the peripheral area to the brain via the spinal cord. Source: (Kuner & Kuner, 2021).....	24
Figure 7 Associations with disease measures. Source: (Sumpton et al., 2020)	45
Figure 8 Immune-Stress Axis (adapted from neuro-immune crosstalk in the pathology of hypertension). Source: (Calvillo et al., 2019)	47
Figure 9 Crosstalk between autonomous nervous system, hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal and immune system. Source: (Mueller et al., 2022)	48
Figure 10 Interpretation of stress signals. Source: (Mueller et al., 2022).....	48
Figure 11 Sleep deprivation, immune response and inflammation. Source: (Garbarino et al., 2021).....	52
Figure 12 Taxonomy of sleep assessment methods. Source: (Ibáñez et al., 2018)	53
Figure 13 Keystroke dynamics features.....	61
Figure 14 EGG conventional electrode placement proposed by Chen et al. Images extracted from (Komorowski et al., 2015; Riezzo et al., 2013)).....	64
Figure 15 OMERACT Endorsed Core Domain Set for Psoriatic Arthritis. MSK, musculoskeletal.	68
Figure 16 Main joint counts (A) and enthesitis indices (B) used in PsA. Swelling of the hip is not assessed (66 swollen/ 68 tender joints). Adapted from: Ogdie et al., 2020.....	69
Figure 17 . The locations of the 21 landmarks generated by the MediaPipe framework.	71
Figure 18 The effective width of a joint is calculated as the ratio of joint width to average PIP to DIP length. The yellow lines on the image indicate how these joint related measures are calculated given the generated landmarks and the segmentation contour of a finger. Source: (Webster et al., 2022).	71
Figure 19 Swollen joint detection processing dorsal finger fold images with CNN. Source: (Hugle et al., 2022).	71
Figure 20 Nail-enthesal-joint apparatus, the anatomical structure that manifests the nail and distal interphalangeal extensor tendon enthesis relationship. Source: (Raposo & Torres, 2015).....	72
Figure 21 Interactions between MCs and other immune cells. Source: (Zhou et al., 2022) .	76
Figure 22 Filtering of histological skin images for use in the SVM classification. Source: (TR Thamizhvani, 2022)	78
Figure 23 Genetic polymorphisms in CYPs and drug metabolism. Source: (Ahmed et al., 2016).....	84
Figure 24 OMOP CDM schema. The figure shows the standard tables of OMOP CDM. All iPROLEPSIS data will be converted to this format.	114
Figure 25 Use of Rabbit-In-A-Hat for Reuma.pt data.....	115

List of Tables

Table 1 Instruments available in literature for assessing stiffness in PsA.	32
Table 2 Relevant organ systems for measurement of stress	50
Table 3 Summary of state-of-art literature on symptoms, triggers, consequences, and markers for development and monitoring of PsA.....	88
Table 4 Summary of retrospective datasets and datasets identified from scientific literature.	94
Table 5 Data-driven decision models for PsO/PsA activity.	100
Table 6. Game formats and interventions	105
Table 7 Variables of interest and their associated OMOP concepts ids for data collected through wearables in iPROLEPSIS.	115
Table 8 Variables of interest and for data collected in iPROLEPSIS PDPID study.....	117

List of abbreviations

ABC	ATP-binding cassette
ACPM	Automated computer guided PASI measurements
ACR	American College of Rheumatology
AD	Autoimmune disease
AI	Artificial intelligence
AI-PGS	AI-based personalization of the iPROLEPSIS Serious Gaming Suite
AMP	Antimicrobial peptides
ANKRD20A4	Ankyrin Repeat Domain 20 Family Member A4
ANS	Autonomous nervous system
ASQOL	Ankylosing Spondylitis Quality of Life
AxSpA	Axial spondyloarthritis
BASDAI	Bath Ankylosing Spondylitis Activity Index
BSA	Body surface area
CAMP	Cathelicidin antimicrobial peptide
CASPAR	CIASsification for Psoriatic ARthritis
CB	Content-based
CDM	Common Data Model
CF	Collaborative filtering-based
CI	Confidence interval
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network
COMT	Catechol-O-methyltransferase
CPDAI	The Composite Psoriatic Disease Activity Index
CPE	Carboxypeptidase E
CRP	C-reactive protein
CRPS	Complex Regional Pain Syndrome
C-SOSI	Calgary Symptoms of Stress Inventory
CVD	Cardiovascular diseases
CYP	Cytochromes P450
DAPSA	Disease Activity index for Psoriatic Arthritis
DAS 28	Disease activity score 28
DC	Dendritic cell
DIP	Distal interphalangeal
DLQI	Dermatology-Life-Quality-Index
DMARD	Disease modifying anti-rheumatic drug
DSQ	Four-Dimensional Symptom Questionnaire
DSS	Dactylitis Severity Score
ECG	Electrocardiography
EEG	Electroencephalographic
EEQ-G	Exergame Enjoyment Questionnaire
EFSA	European Food Safety Authority
EGEG	Electrogastroenterography

ERAP1	Endoplasmic reticulum aminopeptidase 1
ESR	Erythrocyte sedimentation rate
ETL	Extract Transform Load
EULAR	European League Against Rheumatism
FACIT-F	Functional Assessment of Chronic Illness Therapy Fatigue
FHR	Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources
FV	Feature vector
GWAS	Genome-wide association study
HADS	Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale
HAM-A	Hamilton Anxiety Rating Scale
HAQ	Health Assessment Questionnaire
HAR	Human Activity Recognition
HDL	High density lipoprotein
HDRS	Hamilton Depression Rating Scale
HIIL	High-intensity interval training
HLA	human leukocyte antigen
HPA	Hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal
HRV	Heart rate variability
HRV	Heart rate variability
IFN- γ	Interferon- γ
IL	Interleukin
ILC	Innate lymphoid cells
iMAT	Intelligent Motor Assessment Tests
iPROLEPSIS PDPID	PsA digital phenotyping and inflammation drivers
JAK/STAT	Janus kinase/signal transducers and activators of transcription
JSS	Jenkins Sleep Scale
KIR	Killer Immunoglobulin-Like Receptor
LDI	Leeds Dactylitis Index
LDL	Low density lipoprotein
LEI	Leeds Enthesitis Index
LOOCV	A Leave-One-Out Cross-Validation
LSSI	Lipp's stress symptoms inventory
LSTM	Long Short-Term Memory
MAF	Multidimensional Assessment of Fatigue
MC	Mast cell
MCI	Mild cognitive impairment
MDA	Minimal disease activity
mFSS	(modified) Fatigue Severity scale
MHC	Major histocompatibility complex
MICA-TM	Major histocompatibility complex class I chain-related gene A transmembrane
MiMT	Movement in Multiple Time
mNCD	Mild neurocognitive disorder
MRI	Magnetic resonance imaging

MS	Morning stiffness
MSAS	Morning Stiffness Assessment Scale
MSOT	Multispectral Optoacoustic Tomography
MTL	Multi-task learning
NF- κ B	Nuclear factor kappa-light-chain-enhancer of activated B cells
NF κ BIA	NF- κ B inhibitor alpha
NLRP	NLR family pyrin domain
NRS	Numerical analogue scale
NSAID	Non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug
OMERACT	Outcome Measures in Rheumatology Clinical Trials
OMOP	Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership
OPRM1	Mu-opioid receptor 1
OR	Odds ratio
OTOF	Otoferlin
PASDAS	Psoriatic Arthritis Disease Activity Score
PASI	Psoriasis Area Severity Index
PBD	Pain-related behavior detection
PD	Parkinson's disease
PGS	Personalized Serious Game Suite
PHQ-9	Patient Health Questionnaire
PPG	Photoplethysmogram
PRO	Patient reported outcome
PsA	Psoriatic arthritis
PsAID	Psoriatic Arthritis Impact of Disease
PSG	Polysomnography
PsO	Psoriasis
PSQ	Perceived Stress Questionnaire
PSQI	Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index
PSS	Perceived stress scale
PTGS2	Prostaglandin-endoperoxide synthase 2
PTX3	Pentraxin 3
RA	Rheumatoid arthritis
RANKL	NF- κ B (RANK) ligand
RAST	Rheumatoid arthritis stiffness
RCT	Randomized controlled trial
REL	Relish
ROM	Range-of-motion
RSOM	Raster-Scan Optoacoustic Mesoscopy
SB	Spike bursts
SDIM1	Stress Responsive DNAJB4 Interacting Membrane Protein
SG	Serious game
SJC/TJC	swollen and tender joint count
SLC	Solute carrier

SLE	Systemic lupus erythematosus
SLR	Systemic literature review
SNP	Single nucleotide polymorphism
SOP	Standard operating protocol
SpA	Spondyloarthritis
SRTs	Stepping reaction times
STL	Single task learning
STS	Sit to stand
SVM	Support Vector Machines
SW	Slow wave
Th	T helper
TNF-a	Tumor necrosis factor alpha
TNFAIP	Tumor necrosis factor α induced protein
TNIP	TNFAIP3-interacting protein 1
TRAF	Tumor necrosis factor receptor (TNFR)-associated factors
US	Ultrasound
VAS	Visual analogue scale
VLDA	Very low disease activity
VR	Virtual reality
VT	Vitality
WHO	World health organization
WP	Work package

Executive summary

Psoriatic arthritis (PsA) is a chronic immune mediated inflammatory arthritis occurring in patients with psoriasis (PsO). Disease manifestations can be heterogeneous between subjects, and the resulting musculoskeletal impairment can interfere with physical function as well as quality of life of patients. Based on disease activity, patients can experience burden at physical, psychological, social and financial levels. Such burdens can be also experienced when patient is in the flare state which is an acute exacerbation of disease. Here, we review the literature on what is known in PsA in terms of disease symptoms, the factors that may be associated with flare, and markers for development and monitoring of disease. Of interest, the literature was also reviewed to provide information on the measurement tools for these factors, as well as approaches to disease activity prediction models. Implications for clinical practice by means of recommendations and serious games were also reviewed. Moreover, various multi-source datasets have been identified that can potentially yield valuable information for the discovery of PsA inflammation drivers and the development of novel digital biomarkers and predictive models for disease monitoring and progression prognosis.

Briefly, fatigue, pain and stiffness are commonly reported symptoms of PsA. In terms of flare, previous literature suggests flare may be triggered by alterations in mood, stress, sleep, bowel movements, and environmental factors. As a consequence of flare, mood, stress, sleep and bowel movements may be also affected, as well as physical activity and motor skills. Certain symptoms of PsA may also trigger or be triggered by flare. Clinical measurement of these symptoms and hypothesized flare associated factors is mainly through questionnaires. The use of smartphones and wearables to monitor physical activity (mainly through accelerometer data), fine motor skills (through keystroke dynamics), heart rate, and heart rate variability have also shown potential to measure these symptoms and hypothesized flare associated factors. Electrography techniques can be also used in the assessment of certain factors such as electrocardiography for heart rate and electrogastroenterography for bowel. Monitoring of PsA can be through clinical examination for inflamed joints, enthesitis dactylitis, nail and skin and subsequent calculation of relative indices and composite scores. Imaging-based approaches including images obtained from smartphones and optoacoustics represent a complementary or alternative approach to clinical assessment. At biological level, genetic factors may contribute to development of PsA, pain perception and response to treatment. Gut microbiome may be also involved in PsA. Mast cells in skin are also suggested to play a role in skin inflammation. Moreover, data-driven models can serve to find predictive relations even when the underlying mechanisms are poorly understood or are too complex. Besides, diet and physical activity have been linked to PsO and PsA and can be modified by providing patients with recommendations and serious games. Serious games can also address other aspects of disease including medication adherence, social support, cognition, breathing, biological and neural function.

This document (deliverable D2.2) constitutes the initial report of task T2.1 “State-of-the-art analysis and datasets landscape” and T2.4 “Datasets retrieval, harmonisation and curation”. T2.1 deals with the extensive review of literature related to PsA as well as the identification relevant datasets/databases and approaches to disease activity prediction models. The literature including state-of-art and measurements will provide background knowledge for the different work packages, namely WP3, WP5 and WP4 (tasks T4.2 and T4.4). The identified datasets will be retrieved, harmonised and curated in task T2.4. These datasets and the prediction models will contribute to the research on PsA monitoring and inflammation drivers (WP3). In addition, the identified (existing) datasets will guide the development of the Lifestyle AI-driven recommendation system and the serious games in tasks T4.2 and T4.4, respectively.

1 Introduction

Psoriatic arthritis (PsA) is a chronic immune mediated inflammatory arthritis occurring in patients with psoriasis (PsO) and is usually serum rheumatoid factor negative (Tiwari & Brent, 2023). The prevalence of PsA in general population is estimated to be around 0.13% and affects 20% of patients with PsO (Alinaghi et al., 2019; Scotti et al., 2018). The disease manifestation can be heterogeneous between subjects, and the resulting musculoskeletal impairment can interfere with physical function as well as quality of life of patients (Gudu & Gossec, 2018). Common clinical features of disease include, spondylitis, sacroilitis, dactylitis, enthesitis, psoriasis, uveitis and nail dystrophy, in addition to radiographic features such as asymmetric presentation, and pencil-in-cup and bone formation (McArdle et al., 2018). Depending on disease activity, patients can experience burden at physical, psychological, social and financial levels (Gudu & Gossec, 2018; Lee et al., 2010).

PsA is a multifactorial disease with pathology that is not yet fully understood. It is believed that an interplay between genetic factors (e.g., HLA-B27, haplotypes B27-C02 and B38-C12, interleukin (IL)-13 rs1800925), environmental triggers (e.g., gut microbiome, stress, mechanical stress) and immune-mediated inflammation underpins the disease mechanisms (Veale & Fearon, 2018). Dysregulation of immune cells such as the dendritic cells (DCs), T helper 1 (Th1) and Th17, and macrophages plays a central role in pathogenesis of PsA (Carvalho & Hedrich, 2021; Veale & Fearon, 2018). These cells secrete cytokines mainly IL23 (DC and macrophages), IL12 (DC), IL17 (Th17), tumor necrosis factor alpha (TNF- α) (Th17 and macrophages), interferon- γ (IFN- γ) (Th1), IL6 (macrophages) triggering immune cell activation and secretion of inflammatory markers (Carvalho & Hedrich, 2021; Veale & Fearon, 2018). These result in a positive feedback loop leading to chronic inflammation (**Figure 1**).

Figure 1 Example of positive feedback loop triggering inflammation in PsA driven by key immune cells and cytokines.

Several factors have been associated with disease activity in PsA. In **Figure 2**, we present a baseline model on predictors of inflammation in PsA, with main focus on flare (i.e., state of acute exacerbation of disease). The variables included in the model and the relationship between each other and with flare, as depicted in **Figure 2**, are based on literature (reviewed in this document), and input from focus group of patient partners' as well as physicians participating in the iPROLEPSIS project.

Figure 2 Baseline model for predictors of inflammation in PsA based on literature, and patients and physicians' perspective.

Conventional methods used to assess disease activity include clinical measures and self-reported patient symptoms during the routine clinical visits. Consequently, recall bias and survey fatigue are limiting factors when evaluating disease activity. Besides, PsA flares are usually unpredictable, which highlights on the importance of monitoring patient on daily basis. The widespread use of smart devices by the general population, such as smartphones or smartwatches provides a promising alternative or complementary approach to conventional disease assessment methods (**Figure 3**). The digital biomarkers measured using the sensors embedded within the smart devices allows for unobtrusive real-time disease activity monitoring, as compared to assessment during the routine clinical visits. Examples of such sensors include motion sensors (i.e., accelerometer) and keystroke dynamics.

Figure 3 Digital biomarker measuring devices, tasks and features.

1.1 Document scope

The deliverable D2.2 is the initial report for Task T2.1 and Task T2.4 which are part of work package (WP) 2. Here, we review the literature on what is known in PsA in terms of disease symptoms, the factors that may be associated with flare, and markers for development and monitoring of disease (Figure 2). Of interest, the literature was also reviewed to provide information on the measurement tools and models for prediction of disease activity. Implications for clinical practice by means of recommendations and serious games (SGs) were also reviewed. The literature will provide background knowledge for the different work packages, namely WP3, WP5 and WP4 (tasks T4.2 and T4.4). Moreover, authors have identified existing datasets from literature that can potentially yield valuable information for the discovery of PsA inflammation drivers and the development of novel digital biomarkers and

predictive models for disease monitoring and progression prognosis. Indeed, these datasets will be assessed for relevancy and usability, retrieved, harmonised and curated in Task T2.4 (Figure 4). Then, the identified datasets and predictive models will contribute to the research on PsA monitoring and inflammation drivers in WP3 (Figure 4). The identified datasets will also guide the development of the Lifestyle AI-driven recommendation system and the SGs, both of which are parts of WP4 (Figure 4).

Figure 4 Connection between data sets identified in Task T2.1 with task T2.4, and tasks of WP3 and WP4.

1.2 Document structure

This document represents an overview on the state-of-art literature and existing datasets in the field of PsA with special focus on flare. The document consists of 8 sections: (1) introduction, (2) symptoms of PsA, (3) triggers and consequences of flare in PsA, (4) markers for the development and monitoring of PsA, (5) prediction models for disease activity, (6) implications for clinical practice, (7) methods for datasets harmonisation and curation, and (8) conclusion. The introduction section presents a brief overview on disease epidemiology, pathophysiology, manifestation, activity, and insights into digital biomarkers. This section also includes the document scope and structure. Section 2 comprises the main symptoms of PsA, namely, fatigue, pain and stiffness. The triggers and consequences of flare are reviewed in Section 3, and these include mood, stress, sleep, physical activity, bowel movements and environmental factors. In section 4, the authors review clinical, laboratory and alternative digital markers that can be applicable in predicting the risk for PsA as well as in monitoring disease activity. Section 5 includes approaches to disease activity and flare prediction/detection models in PsA. Section 6 provides information for clinical practice by means of recommendation systems and SGs. Of note, in sections 2, 3, 4 and 6 authors provide the state-of-art background, information on measurement tools, and where applicable, the datasets identified for each topic. Section 7 provides information on methods for data

harmonization and curation. Finally, section 8 provides a conclusion summarizing the main points of the document and future steps.

2 Symptoms of psoriatic arthritis

2.1 Fatigue

2.1.1 State-of-art

Fatigue can be defined as a psychophysiological condition which involves physical or mental tiredness and feeling of exhaustion that are not relieved by resting, usually leading to reduced mental or physical activity (Dupond, 2011; Phillips, 2015). It is also worth noting that currently, there is no standard definition of fatigue (Phillips, 2015). In PsA, fatigue is one of the mostly assessed PROs and has been reported in 45-80% of patients with 20-30% reporting severe fatigue (Duruöz et al., 2020; Gossec et al., 2022; Gudu et al., 2016; Haugeberg et al., 2020; Krajewska-Włodarczyk et al., 2017, 2020; Tan et al., 2020; Walsh et al., 2021). Nevertheless, it is an underestimated symptom in PsA patients, with patient-physician discordance in reporting fatigue (Walsh et al., 2021; Wang et al., 2019). Moreover, fatigue has been associated with disease activity, pain, quality of life and other PROs such as sleep and depression, making this symptom a key contributor in the transition to the flare state in PsA (Conaghan et al., 2020; Esbensen et al., 2020; Haugeberg et al., 2020; Husted et al., 2010; McDonough et al., 2014).

When studying fatigue, authors would classify fatigue as physical or mental, as well as differentiating between subjective fatigue or fatigability (Lou, 2009). Briefly, subjective fatigue reflects patient sensation on the amount of effort they need to put in for performing certain activities or concentrating (Lou, 2009). On the other hand, fatigability reflects performance i.e., change in physical or mental activity as compared to a reference level (Desthieux et al., 2017; Wang et al., 2019). Indeed, these differences in perceiving fatigue can partly explain the observed patient-physician discordance when measuring fatigue (Desthieux et al., 2017; Wang et al., 2019).

Little is known on the pathophysiology of fatigue. In terms of inflammation-associated fatigue, previous studies suggest involvement of central and peripheral mechanisms. At systemic level, fatigue has been associated with inflammatory markers such as IL6, TNFa, CRP in certain medical conditions such as cancer and multiple sclerosis (Dantzer et al., 2014). Moreover, randomized control trials that assessed biologics (e.g., TNFa inhibitors) showed reduction in fatigue, suggesting a causal relationship between inflammation and fatigue (Reygaerts et al., 2018). Peripheral cytokines induce production of inflammatory mediators by the central nervous system which have been found to target the basal ganglia, frontal cortex and insula in the brain and the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal (HPA) axis accounting for fatigue (Dantzer et al., 2014; Hanken et al., 2014). The inflammatory cytokines are also implicated in tetrahydrobiopterin deficiency, which is a cofactor in the biosynthesis of neurotransmitters dopamine, norepinephrine and serotonin (**Figure 5**) (see reviews (Dantzer et al., 2014; Karshikoff et al., 2017)). Moreover, these cytokines are involved in formation of neurotoxic kynurenine metabolites which has been shown to be associated with fatigue (**Figure 5**) (Dantzer et al., 2014; Groven et al., 2021). Besides, they can activate microglia which has a negative effect on dopaminergic neurotransmission (**Figure 5**) (see reviews (Dantzer et al., 2014; Karshikoff et al., 2017)). Of note, immune-mediated inflammation is a central mechanism in PsA. Therefore, these mechanisms could provide insights into the pathophysiology of fatigue in PsA especially when experiencing flare, as (to best of the author knowledge) no previous studies investigated biological mechanisms of fatigue in PsA.

Figure 5 Central and peripheral mechanisms in fatigue. BH4, tetrahydrobiopterin; GTP-CH1, guanosine-triphosphate cyclohydrolase-1; IDO, indoleamine 2,3 dioxygenase; TRP, tryptophan; KYN, kynurenine; NMDA, N-methyl-D-aspartic acid. Source: (Dantzer et al., 2014)

At the clinical level, previous literature showed an association between fatigue with clinical characteristics of PsA. At the skin level, fatigue has been associated with Psoriasis Area and Severity Index (PASI), and patients with nail psoriasis indicated more fatigue (Carneiro et al., 2017; Cengiz et al., 2023; Lai et al., 2021; Mease, Liu, Rebello, McLean, et al., 2021). In addition, fatigue was explained by skin psoriasis in Gudu et al. study (Gudu et al., 2016). In terms of arthritis, patients reporting higher fatigue showed higher swollen and tender joint counts, had enthesitis particularly at the lower or both upper and lower sites (Gossec et al., 2022; Mease et al., 2017; Mease, Liu, Rebello, Hua, et al., 2021). Importantly, fatigue has been also associated with disease activity in observational studies. Remission or low disease activity as measured by DAS28 remission, Disease Activity index for Psoriatic Arthritis (DAPSA) remission, cDAPSA remission, minimal disease activity (MDA), and very low disease activity (VLDA) scores were observed with better fatigue scores (i.e., less fatigue) (Duruöz et al., 2020; Linde et al., 2023; Mease, Karki, et al., 2018; Snoeck Henkemans et al., 2022). Moreover, fatigue correlated with DAPSA scores, where increased scores indicate increased disease activity (Gado et al., 2021; Lai et al., 2021). Besides, information on association between fatigue with PsA duration are inconsistent (Krajewska-Włodarczyk et al., 2020; Lai et al., 2021; Skougaard et al., 2020; Tan et al., 2020).

Epidemiological studies that monitored fatigue longitudinally mostly reported fatigue as a treatment outcome. For example, lower fatigue was shown after 6 months of treatment with Secukinumab after 6 months, as well as after 3 and 6 months treatment with Adalimumab (Garrido et al., 2022; Gladman, Mease, Cifaldi, et al., 2007). When considering observational studies, few have assessed fatigue longitudinally. In the study of Janice et al., fatigue was assessed at 6- and 12-months in PsA patients and showed positive associations with disease activity levels (Husted et al., 2010). In another study by Ballegaard et al., fatigue was assessed at baseline and after 4 months, and was shown to be higher in PsA patient compared with PsO and healthy controls (Ballegaard et al., 2021). Wang also collected information on fatigue

at baseline, 4- and -8 months, 1-, 2- and 5-years and which showed associations with patient-physician discordance (Wang et al., 2019).

At last, fatigue seems to be an important outcome for patients with PsA, thus frequent monitoring of fatigue in these patients, is recommended (Tillett et al., 2017).

2.1.2 Measurement

Various questionnaires and scales have been developed to measure fatigue (Hewlett et al., 2011). The commonly used tools when measuring fatigue in PsA include The Functional Assessment of Chronic Illness Therapy Fatigue (FACIT-F), Visual analogue scale (VAS) fatigue and Numerical Rating Scale (NRS) fatigue, Fatigue Severity scale (FSS), Multidimensional Assessment of Fatigue (MAF), and SF-36 vitality (VT) scale (Krajewska-Włodarczyk et al., 2017).

2.1.2.1 Clinical measurement of fatigue

The Functional Assessment of Chronic Illness Therapy Fatigue

The FACIT-F is one of the mostly used questionnaires when assessing fatigue in patients with PsA (Gladman, Mease, Healy, et al., 2007; Højgaard et al., 2018; Krajewska-Włodarczyk et al., 2017). The questionnaire consists of 13 fatigue-related questions and has been validated in patients with PsA (Chandran et al., 2007). Response to each question is on a 5-point Likert scale, from 0 “Not at all” to 4 “Very much”. The questionnaire and scoring system can be found on <https://www.facit.org/>. The score ranges between 0 to 52, with higher scores indicating less fatigue.

VAS fatigue and NRS fatigue

The VAS fatigue scale scores fatigue in patients with PsA on a 0-100mm line (Højgaard et al., 2018; Kwok & Pope, 2010). Moreover, a 10-cm VAS has been also used in some studies (Duruöz et al., 2020; Tutuncu et al., 2004).

The NRS fatigue, is usually used as part of Psoriatic Arthritis Impact of Disease (PsAID) composite score and has been validated in patients with PsA (Coates, 2015; Gladman et al., 2020; Højgaard et al., 2018). NRS fatigue is an 11-point Likert scale, which ranges from 0 “No fatigue” to 10 “Totally exhausted” (EULAR).

The NRS fatigue 11-point Likert scale will be used to measure fatigue in the iPROLEPSIS PDPID study in Task T5.2.

Fatigue Severity scale

The FSS scale is a 9-item questionnaire focusing on measuring fatigue in daily activities, which has been used to assess fatigue in PsA patients (Krupp et al., 1989; Rosen et al., 2012) (Coates, 2015; Krajewska-Włodarczyk et al., 2017). Each item is scored on a 7-point Likert scale ranging from 1 “completely disagree” to 7 “completely agree” (Krupp et al., 1989). A modified version of the questionnaire has also been developed (mFSS) and used in patients with PsA (Husted et al., 2009; Schentag et al., 2000). The mFSS is 9-item questionnaire that rates fatigue on 10-point Likert scale (Schentag et al., 2000). In both versions, higher scores represent more severe fatigue.

Multidimensional Assessment of Fatigue

The MAF has been also used to measure fatigue in studies of patients with PsA (Duruoz et al., 2018; Ulus et al., 2019). MAF is a 16-item questionnaire that covers fatigue in terms of severity, degree, distress, and impact on daily activities and timing. Each item is scores on a

1-10 point numeric scale, with higher scores indicating more severe fatigue (Bahouq et al., 2012).

SF-36 vitality scale

The SF-36 VT is a 4-item questionnaire that measures vitality as part of the full SF-36 instrument (Elera-Fitzcarrald et al., 2020). SF-36 VT has been also used to assess fatigue in some studies of patients with PsA, with higher scores indicating less fatigue (Cella et al., 2019; Tan et al., 2020; Ware & Sherbourne, 1992).

2.1.2.2 Digital biomarkers for measuring fatigue

Besides clinical assessment, the technological advances made a room to measure fatigue using digital biomarkers. A recent study by Rao et al. in patients with chronic inflammatory rheumatic diseases and healthy participants showed that heart rate and step features captured using Fitbit wearable were relevant in predicting physical and mental fatigue and tiredness (Chaitra Rao, 2023). Sleep features were also shown to be a relevant predictor for physical fatigue (Chaitra Rao, 2023). Another pilot study in healthy subjects also showed that heart rate features and physical activity features including steps contributed to the prediction of fatigue (Luo et al., 2020). Moreover, previous studies have also assessed the suitability of accelerometers to detect physical fatigue in various physical exercises with the peak tibial and sacral acceleration being the mostly studied (Marotta et al., 2022). Fatigue has been associated with an increase in peak tibial and sacral acceleration in the majority of these studies (Marotta et al., 2022). Keystroke dynamics have been also suggested to be a promising digital biomarker in detecting fatigue (Al-Libawy et al., 2016; Chen et al., 2022; K. H. Lam et al., 2022). Besides, in the study of Elbéji et al., prediction models were developed to derive vocal biomarkers for Android and iOS smartphones from voice recordings in patients with COVID-19, and were capable of recognizing fatigue from non-fatigue (Elbeji et al., 2022). Another model developed using gaze data obtained from smartphone application with gaze tasks have shown potential in predicting mental fatigue (Tseng et al., 2021).

To best of our knowledge, no previous studies investigated digital biomarkers to capture fatigue in patients with PsA, which is one of the study objectives in the iPROLEPSIS-PDPID study (Task T5.2).

2.1.3 Datasets

In general, prospective studies that followed-up patients with PsA were intervention studies conducted to assess effectiveness of medication on various clinical and PROs, which included fatigue. Here we mention observational studies that monitored fatigue which might provide relevant datasets.

2.1.3.1 Clinical monitoring of fatigue

Datasets from existing cohorts of clinical partners (DEPAR, MONITOR and Reuma.pt) collected information on fatigue longitudinally.

An interesting study by Husted et al. analysed fatigue longitudinally in relation to disease activity (Husted et al., 2010). The study included 390 patients with PsA (men and women) in which fatigue was measured at baseline, 6 and 12 months using the mFSS.

Three observational studies assessed effectiveness of medication in relation to fatigue and other manifestations of PsA. The study of Behrens et al. assessed effectiveness of Leflunomide in PsA patients on clinical manifestations of PsA and some PROs including fatigue (Behrens et al., 2013). The study included 514 patients with PsA and fatigue was assessed at baseline and after 6 months. Similarly, the study of Krüger assessed effectiveness of Golimumab on PROs including fatigue (Krüger et al., 2019). The study included 501 patients

with PsA and measured fatigue at baseline, 3-, 6-, 12-, until 24 months. Also, Heiberg compared effectiveness of anti-TNF therapy and methotrexate on disease activity and PROs including fatigue. The study included 526 patients and measured fatigue at baseline, 3- and 6-months.

The study of Wang et al. collected information on fatigue and other PROs in 142 patients with PsA at baseline, baseline, 4- and -8 months, 1-, 2- and 5-years, to study associations with patient-physician discordance (Wang et al., 2019).

2.1.3.2 Digital monitoring of fatigue

The study by Rao et al. on associations of digital measures and self-reported fatigue (Chaitra Rao, 2023). This was an observational study that included 296 patients with chronic inflammatory rheumatic disease and healthy participants. Data on physical activity, sleep and heart rate were collected continuously for a month using Fitbit with an aim to identify key predictive features physical and mental fatigue and daily tiredness.

2.1.3.3 Registries

Besides, we also mention some registries that assessed fatigue longitudinally in patients with PsA, which might be worth looking into: The Danish nationwide clinical register for patients with rheumatoid arthritis (DANBIO) register (<https://danbio-online.dk/>) (Heiberg et al., 2007); The British Society for Rheumatology psoriatic arthritis (BSR-PsA) register (<https://www.rheumatology.org.uk/improving-care/registers/psoriatic-arthritis>) (Jones et al., 2021); and the US-Based Corrona Registry (<https://www.corevitas.com/>) (Mease, Karki, et al., 2018).

2.2 Pain

2.2.1 State-of-art

Pain is one of the primary symptoms of PsA, and it plays an important role in disease management. Initially, when inflammation occurs for the first time, pain arises from joint or enthesitis inflammation. However, over time this may change as there are multiple streams of information that contribute to how we perceive pain (Rutter-Locher et al., 2023; Tracey, 2022). A recent systematic review and meta-analysis to understand the prevalence of pain sensitivity and neuropathic-like pain in inflammatory arthritis show high numbers of more complex pain patterns (Rutter-Locher et al., 2023). They found that the reported prevalence of pain sensitivity and neuropathic-like pain in inflammatory arthritis is higher compared to the general population. Rates ranged from 31% to 42% depending on the questionnaire used, while in the general population, the prevalence is around 4.2% for pain sensitivity and 6.9% for neuropathic pain. The study also revealed that pain sensitivity and neuropathic-like pain were higher in spondyloarthritis (SpA) and PsA compared to rheumatoid arthritis. These findings suggest that there may be centrally mediated pain mechanisms contributing to persistent pain in a significant number of inflammatory arthritis patients. However, it should be noted that most studies were small ($n < 200$), may have selection bias to higher pain levels and only one study was performed in Psoriatic Arthritis (Rutter-Locher et al., 2023).

Pain signaling and regulation is a complex process (Kuner & Kuner, 2021; Tan & Kuner, 2021; Tracey, 2022). It is strongly related to the stress mechanism later described in Section 4.2, and receives in the brain a lot of attention making it difficult to ignore. Outside the brain, there are special nerve cells called nociceptors that carry these signals to the spinal cord and then up to the brain (**Figure 6**). When there is tissue injury or inflammation, certain channels and proteins in the nociceptors become more active, leading to increased sensitivity and pain. This process is known as peripheral sensitization (Kuner & Kuner, 2021; Tracey, 2022).

Inside the brain, these pain signals are relayed to different areas, including the brain stem and thalamus (**Figure 6**). The thalamus acts like a relay station and divides the pain signals into three main components. One stream, called the lateral system, helps us understand the sensory aspects of pain, such as its location and intensity. Another stream, known as the medial system, is responsible for the emotional aspects of pain and triggers our responses and reactions. The posterior system generates the main perception of pain and its intensity (Kuner & Kuner, 2021).

Figure 6 Pain traveling from the peripheral area to the brain via the spinal cord. Source: (Kuner & Kuner, 2021)

It's worth noting that there are other brain systems, like the inputs to the hippocampus and hypothalamus, as well as pathways through the brain stem, that may also play a role in the complex experience of pain in the brain. The logic behind these parallel information streams

and their multiple targets remains incompletely understood, but may reflect the requirement to feed nociceptive information into different subsystems of the brain to orchestrate an overall homeostatic response. This needs to be kept in mind when considering the origination of different subjective qualities of the pain percept. More details are provided by Kuner & Kuner (Kuner & Kuner, 2021).

2.2.2 Measurement

The inclusion of pain as a core outcome in Psoriatic Arthritis studies has been established since the inception of the Outcome Measures in Rheumatology Clinical Trials (OMERACT) core outcome set. Consequently, pain information is collected in every study conducted since the adoption of this core outcome set in 2009 (Tugwell et al., 2009).

2.2.2.1 Clinical measurement of pain

Current – Snap shots of pain

Currently, pain assessment involves asking patients about the level of pain they are experiencing. This can be done through methods such as PRO measures where patients provide their own assessment, or through clinical examinations that involve applying pressure to joints or tissues to elicit pain. The severity of pain is typically scored using scales like the VAS, which ranges from no pain to extreme pain, or Likert scales that can range from 0 to 10 or other variations like 0 to 4. The lower end of the Likert scale represents no pain, while the upper end represents severe pain.

In routine clinical practice, pain is usually evaluated. However, pain levels are often not consistently recorded in patient files unless PROs are implemented, or a tender joint count is performed using a manikin. The latter method only provides a binary score indicating whether there is pain present or not in a specific joint or enthesis.

Future - Continuous monitoring of pain

Electroencephalographic (EEG)

Li et al did some work on distinguishing chronic pain EEG patterns from patterns in healthy controls (Li et al., 2021). They applied regular hospital methods to obtain EEG. Using a Supported Vector Machine, they were able to separate both groups with an accuracy of 0.97 in their development set and 0.81 in their test set. This suggest that at least with hospital-based equipment we may better understand if a patient suffers for chronic pain. However, currently there is not an easy implementable remote patient monitoring available.

Blood pressure

Pouomran et al tried to implement a blood pulse volume measure (Pouomran et al., 2022). They rely on pain being a trigger for the stress system (Autonomic Nervous System (ANS)). They applied the cold hand experiment in which participants held their hand in cold water and every 20 seconds pain scores were reported verbally. With 3 pain intensities they found precision and recall of around 80% for the low pain threshold and 90% for the high pain threshold. Observations were not checked in another sample, so the verdict is still open whether these findings will hold in similar experiments.

Heart rate and heart rate variability

Pouomran et al also evaluated the impact of their cold hand experiment on both heart rate and hear rate variability (Pouomran et al., 2022). Although Heart Rate Variability (HRV) narrowed and slightly decreased at higher pain levels, the range still felt within the no pain condition. Which is probably in line with the physiological characteristics of heart beat that is

highly variable and under the rule of many different factors (looking through the keyhole of HRV) (Karemaker, 2020).

2.2.2.2 Digital measurement of pain

Initial steps have been taken to explore a new approach to measure pain. Its implementation in the field of rheumatology has not yet occurred. Pain is a complex phenomenon involving both the peripheral and central nervous systems as explained earlier. In the brain, it can act as a stressor and lead to various responses throughout the body's nervous system, as elaborated in the stress section. This overall effect can be advantageous as pain influences factors like breathing, heart rate, and skin conductance response. However, the drawback is that these effects are non-specific, meaning that without proper labelling of the data, we cannot determine if changes in vital signs are specifically related to pain or some other factor. In brief, below are the initiatives that recently appeared in the literature. Image recognition of pain by face expression is left out as it is regarded unfeasible to use unobtrusively and in high frequency as aimed for in iPROLEPSIS.

Accelerometer data

The use of deep learning for analysing human movement to assess pain levels and pain-related protective behaviours is a relatively new field of research. Wearable sensors offer a convenient means to collect data for these algorithms. Dehshibi et al summarised in their paper the current state of research in analysing human movement data for pain level and pain-related protective behaviour assessment (Mohammad Mahdi Dehshibi, 2023).

One study conducted by Yang et al. proposed a machine learning approach to evaluate the physical performance of individuals with Complex Regional Pain Syndrome (CRPS) using gait data obtained through an accelerometer during short walking distances (Yang et al., 2012). The findings indicated that individuals with CRPS modify their gait to protect themselves from further pain. Another study by Yoo et al. investigated the relationship between alterations in stair ascent movements and pain, radiographic severity, and prognosis of knee osteoarthritis in older women with persistent knee pain (Yoo et al., 2013). Stair ascent time, maximal anterior pelvis tilting, knee flexion at initial foot contact, and ankle dorsiflexion at initial foot contact were related to pain and radiographic severity.

Combination of signals

Zhao et al studied in one chronic patient with varying pain levels over a number of days several signals (Y. Zhao et al., 2020). Two photoplethysmogram (PPG) pulse sensors held to the temples via a headband, three at the three arteries supplying blood to the brain mounted in a neck pillow, and two at the fingertip and palm, temperature sensors at each location of the PPG pulse sensors, and GSR sensors embedded in the block on which the hand rests. This experimental setup showed that changes in vital function due to pain is picked up by the developed algorithm.

Researchers working on the EmoPain database found that conventional and deep learning methods can detect pain-related protective behaviors by analysing human movement (Olugbade et al., 2015; Wang, Olugbade, et al., 2021; Wang et al., 2019). The EmoPain database contains data collected from healthy individuals and individuals with Chronic Pain. The individuals were asked to perform different activity types resembling daily living. The data were collected using 18 wearable inertial measurement unit (IMU) and four surface electromyography (sEMG) sensors.

Wang et al. demonstrated that using Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM)-based architectures allows for activity-independent pain-related behavior detection (PBD) with improved

performance (Wang, Gao, et al., 2021; Wang, Olugbade, et al., 2021). They explored stacked LSTM and dual-stream LSTM for processing body movement data along with data augmentation and segmentation window width approaches. This allowed the architecture to focus on relevant protective behavior configurations and understand protective behavior from real-life measurements beyond lab-based observations. Olugbade et al. improved on this using a Movement in Multiple Time (MiMT) neural network that encoded low-level movement features with distributed time encoding and jointly predicted pain behavior across multiple timescales (Olugbade et al., 2020). While Wang et al. proposed integrating human activity recognition (HAR) with PBD using a hierarchical architecture comprising graph-convolution and LSTM (Wang, Gao, et al., 2021). This architecture continuously leveraged activity type information to build activity-informed input for concurrent PBD, achieving state-of-the-art classification of PBD using continuous data. Dehshibi et al themselves also used the EmoPain Database. They implemented an architecture that shared the training of EMG and IMU data together in a sparsely connected recurrent neural network.

Other

Arumugaraja et al. used a sensorized insole to detect knee pain in arthritis patients (M. Arumugaraja, 2022). Heat maps of foot pressure distributions were acquired by letting participants walk a set distance. Full heat map images and various dissections were used as features and machine learning approach was used to detect pain.

In patients with rheumatic and musculoskeletal diseases, Mollard et al. assessed associations between passive smartphone data (sensor and activity data) with smartphone PROs including pain (Mollard et al., 2022). Example of extracted features included mobility distance, text message length and number of missed calls. Linear mixed effects models were used to establish association between (weekly) pain and passive smartphone data (Mollard et al., 2022).

2.2.3 Datasets

In the existing three cohorts of clinical partners (DEPAR, MONITOR, Reuma.pt), pain data are gathered using both PRO measures and assessments of tender joints and entheses. These features are commonly measured in most cohorts or registries, although the frequency of data collection varies depending on the specific aim and timeframe of the study. Typically, pain assessments occur every three months during the first year and then annually thereafter.

Other datasets outside rheumatology include data from the 2019-2020 National Health Interview Survey (NHIS) Longitudinal Cohort among US (Nahin et al., 2023) and the EMO pain dataset¹.

2.3 Stiffness

2.3.1 State-of-art

Stiffness, as well as joint pain and swelling, is one of the major manifestations of joint disease and it has been described in the literature since at least the 1960s (Wright & Johns, 1960). However, the concept of stiffness has been a matter of debate, and many authors have tried to define and characterize it both qualitatively and quantitatively (Halls et al., 2015; Halls et al., 2017; Lineker et al., 1999; Orange et al., 2020; Orbai et al., 2015; Sinnathurai et al., 2019; Zanolli & Wickle, 1992).

Stiffness is characteristically most troublesome after periods of rest in one position, especially when waking up in the morning. Because of this, stiffness was originally termed as *morning*

¹ <https://wangchongyang.ai/EmoPainChallenge2020/>

stiffness (MS). Moreover, the original conception of stiffness was fundamentally applied to Rheumatoid Arthritis (RA), which has always represented the paradigm of rheumatic diseases and influenced all research until the last decades. Consequently, one of the earliest definitions of stiffness focused on RA patients and defined it as “slowness or difficulty moving the joints when getting out of bed or after staying in one position too long, which involves both sides of the body and gets better with movement” (Lineker et al., 1999).

Stiffness is most often characterized in terms of its severity and duration. Classically, duration of MS was considered the most clinically relevant domain and was even part of the American College of Rheumatology (ACR) RA Classification Criteria of 1987 (Arnett et al., 1988). This conviction derived from longstanding observations that arthralgia patients with MS for over 60 minutes were more frequently diagnosed with arthritis than patients without MS. However, additional studies found that the discriminative ability of this single variable (through area under the receiver operating characteristic curve assessment) was low (van Nies et al., 2015), leading to the withdrawal of this criterion in the most recent ACR/European League Against Rheumatism (EULAR) RA Classification Criteria of 2010 (Aletaha et al., 2010).

In recent years, numerous studies that explored the perception of stiffness amongst patients and physicians have changed views on the concept of stiffness and its definition. Interviews with patients with RA and other rheumatic diseases concluded that experience of stiffness was substantially subjective. While some individuals mentioned transitory MS, others experienced stiffness persistently throughout the day (Orbai et al., 2014). There were also divergences in other components of stiffness such as location, relationship to other symptoms (particularly pain) and impact on daily life (Orbai et al., 2015; Orbai et al., 2014). Patients also reported feeling frustrated over the ongoing use of the term MS in literature and patient-reported outcomes (PROs), stating this term is not particularly relevant to them (Halls et al., 2018), and point out to findings that stiffness fluctuates throughout the day and is not restricted to the morning (Craig et al., 2019). Recently, the Outcome Measures in Rheumatology Clinical Trials breakout group reported that existing approaches that rely largely on estimations of MS duration were viewed as overly simplistic and do not address the multiple aspects of stiffness. It was also recognized that the localization of stiffness may be important to discern in RA and that stiffness is an important feature of other rheumatic conditions (Bykerk et al., 2014).

In line with findings from the OMERACT group, other studies have observed that severity ratings of MS are more responsive and discriminative than duration (Hazes et al., 1994; Lie et al., 2014; Vliet Vlieland et al., 1997). In addition, when some patients complain of stiffness, they may be referring to limited movement, pain, or a combination of the two. This evidence sustains the theory that perceptions of stiffness are not always clear and easy to assess and there is even an apparent lack of correlation between severity and duration of MS (Rhind et al., 1987). Observations on inter-individual consistency of self-reported duration of MS have found that a patient’s report of a typical day’s MS is subjected to considerable inaccuracy. The variability, weak reliability, and transient character make MS a rather intangible symptom (Hazes et al., 1994). On the other hand, more recent studies observed that MS reflects functional disability and pain better than the traditional markers of inflammation such as quantitative joint count, erythrocyte sedimentation rate (ESR) and CRP in RA patients, and is significantly associated with RA activity through DAS28 (Disease Activity Score-28 for Rheumatoid Arthritis) - exhibiting a moderate correlation - and with radiographic progression (Khan et al., 2009; Westhoff et al., 2008).

In terms of physiopathology, an increasing number of studies has focused on stiffness at a structural, physiological, and molecular level. Initially, it was believed that stiffness occurred due to changes in muscle strength, whereas current research has been centring the

physiopathology of stiffness in tendons and joint capsule. For example, ultrasound findings revealed a significant correlation between hand stiffness in RA and PsA patients and tenosynovitis (Tinazzi et al., 2018). Ultrasonography also has contributed to highlight differences between different rheumatic diseases, with evidence supporting that in PsA (and not RA) the involvement of the flexor compartment is determinant for hand stiffness; thus, demonstrating the relevance of the tendon synovio-entheseal complex disease in PsA (Tinazzi et al., 2018). Similar results were found by Turan *et al.*, who identified a significant correlation between the enthesis index and MS in PsA patients (Turan et al., 2009). In addition, skin has been found to play a role to some extent, although it is not yet clear how it contributes to stiffness (Wright & Johns, 1960).

From a physiological point of view, MS has been linked to abnormalities in the circadian rhythm of the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal axis. While circadian rhythms of serum cortisol are normal in RA patients with low to moderate disease activity, patients with high disease activity present abnormal cortisol rhythms with a low amplitude and two peaks (one in the morning and another one in the afternoon). In addition, RA patients with high disease activity have high levels of circulating cortisol that are, however, inadequately low to counteract the effects of upregulated proinflammatory cytokines, such as IL6 and TNF- α . These unwanted side effects of elevated circulating proinflammatory cytokines ultimately lead to symptoms of stiffness, pain, and functional disability in the morning (Straub & Cutolo, 2007).

At a molecular level, there seems to be a significant association between stiffness and the presence of synovial neutrophils and fibrin in synovial samples of patients with RA. These findings in association with patient reports of duration of MS greater than one hour suggest that acute synovial inflammation or ongoing neutrophil recruitment may play a role in mediating this symptom. The lack of association with markers typical of an adaptive immune response (plasma cells and autoantibodies), along with the fact that fibrin deposition is a finding common to a spectrum of inflammatory states, raises the possibility that neutrophil enmeshed fibrin could represent a generic cause of stiffness that may also mediate stiffness in other rheumatologic diseases such as PsA (Orange et al., 2020).

PsA is a rheumatic disease that is classified as part of the spectrum of SpA, and characterized by the involvement of the skin, peripheral joints, and axial skeleton (Chandran et al., 2009; Lopez-Medina & Ziade, 2022). PsA patients often experience symptoms including joint pain, stiffness, and swelling (Mease et al., 2022). The presence of stiffness itself is not required for establishing the diagnosis PsA as it is not included in the Classification for Psoriatic ARthritis (CASPAR) criteria. However, multiple activity indices use MS for measuring activity in PsA, even though our understanding of MS and PsA disease activity is limited (Nash et al., 2018). MS is also an extensively used criterion for clinical assessment of psoriasis patients to identify those with joint disease (Elkayam, Ophir, Yaron, et al., 2000; Zanolli & Wickle, 1992). In patients with diagnosed psoriasis, the presence of morning peripheral joint stiffness (HR 2.25, 95% CI 1.55, 3.25) and back stiffness (HR 3.71, 95% CI 1.95, 7.02) were associated with the development of PsA (Eder et al., 2017).

Assessment of stiffness in PsA usually focuses on axial involvement (Chandran et al., 2009) and even studies that focus on peripheral manifestations of PsA frequently do not mention peripheral joint stiffness as a relevant symptom (Lopez-Medina et al., 2021). However, peripheral stiffness in PsA is frequent. In a recent study, 64% of PsA patients complained of hand morning stiffness for 30 minutes or more (comparing with 34% of RA patients) (Tinazzi et al., 2018). Peripheral stiffness in PsA can be present in every peripheral joint and, besides hands, it has been reported in wrists, fingers, elbows, knees, ankles, and feet, although it is

not as likely to be symmetric or accompanied by pain or swelling as in other diseases such as RA (Zanolli & Wickle, 1992).

Recently, the Group for Research and Assessment of Psoriasis and Psoriatic Arthritis (GRAPPA) for the OMERACT, intending to contemplate every aspect of PsA, defined stiffness as “Experiencing resistance or rigidity in one or more joints, tendons or the spine, which prevents smooth and full Range-Of-Motion” (Orbai, de Wit, Mease, Shea, et al., 2017). This contemporary definition widened the concept of stiffness, unconfining it from the morning period and encircling axial and peripheral joint disease into one single stiffness perception.

2.3.2 Measurement

Measuring stiffness in PsA is undeniably relevant for patients and physicians. The GRAPPA-OMERACT working group recently updated its recommendations about the relevant outcomes in PsA and stiffness was included in the research agenda, together with independence, treatment burden, and sleep, bringing attention to the relevance of stiffness in PsA (Orbai, de Wit, Mease, Callis Duffin, et al., 2017).

It has been the goal of multiple institutions, including ACR and EULAR, to develop adequate and standardized measures for outcomes relevant for rheumatic diseases. Even though stiffness occurs in many rheumatic diseases, patients’ experiences vary from patient to patient and from disease to disease. Therefore, one of the fundamental questions is whether stiffness can be appropriately measured using universal measures rather than disease-specific ones (Craig et al., 2019). In their Stiffness Breakout Sessions, the OMERACT RA flare group reported that there is value in exploring common aspects of stiffness across diseases, including PsA (Orbai et al., 2015).

However, measuring stiffness seems to be at least as challenging as defining it. A recent Australian study explored the assessment of five dimensions within stiffness in patients with RA and PsA: severity, duration, impact, importance, and coping. The authors reported that patients described stiffness severity and impact in similar terms and rated their stiffness in relation to how it affected their ability to perform daily tasks. Stiffness severity and impact were strongly correlated and were both independent predictors of physical function. On the contrary, duration of MS was relevant to only some participants and was not associated with physical function. Although the duration of MS was strongly correlated with all the other dimensions, stiffness severity and impact appeared to be the most relevant concepts to most participants. These findings suggest that measuring both severity and impact may not provide independent information as these domains are frequently redundant. Therefore, in clinical practice it may be sufficient to measure only one of them, raising the question of whether measuring multiple dimensions of stiffness has additive value (Sinnathurai et al., 2019).

Subsequently, in 2016, the OMERACT Stiffness Special Interest Group was formed to develop an appropriate instrument to measure stiffness in RA. The group assessed the available stiffness measures and stated that stiffness assessments so far focused on MS severity or duration and reported a lack of data regarding content validity, construct validity, responsiveness, or reliability of these instruments (Orbai, de Wit, Mease, Callis Duffin, et al., 2017). This indicated a poor match between the conceptual model and PROs currently used in clinical practice, a major flaw according to the OMERACT filter 2.0 recommendations for selecting PROs (Boers et al., 2014) (latest version is the OMERACT Filter 2.1 (Boers et al., 2019)).

However, there is also a lack of instruments to assess stiffness in PsA. Although peripheral stiffness seems to be reasonably measured by RA instruments, until 2022 there were no specific PROs for axial disease activity and function in PsA (Lopez-Medina & Ziade, 2022).

Clinicians and investigators often use Axial spondyloarthritis (AxSpA)-driven PROs for assessing axial involvement in PsA, such as Bath Ankylosing Spondylitis Activity Index (BASDAI) (Garrett et al., 1994) and ASDAS (Ankylosing Spondylitis Disease Activity Score) (Lukas et al., 2009). Unfortunately, data suggests that the BASDAI is not a good instrument to evaluate disease activity in AxSpA (Fernandez-Sueiro et al., 2010; Taylor & Harrison, 2004). Most studies use PROs to assess peripheral stiffness and overlook axial stiffness as an intrinsic characteristic of inflammatory spinal pain (and consequently rated together as axial pain) (Elkayam, Ophir, Brener, et al., 2000; Elkayam, Yaron, et al., 2000). To our knowledge, there is only one study that evaluated separately peripheral and axial stiffness (Eder et al., 2017).

2.3.2.1 Clinical measurement of stiffness

A literature review was conducted to identify instruments for assessing stiffness in PsA. Studies that identify the instrument used, domains assessed, measurement details or accuracy data are summarized in **Table 1**. Studies that only mention stiffness assessment but do not provide details on the attributes formerly referred to were excluded from the table (Batmaz et al., 2016; Clemmensen et al., 1980; Emad et al., 2022; Gungor et al., 2018; Haugen et al., 1991; Saber et al., 2010; Spadaro et al., 2002).

Despite its central involvement in patient experience, we observed that measurement of stiffness remains suboptimal and no validated instruments exist for its measurement (Craig et al., 2019). While stiffness has been measured in different ways in different studies, authors frequently utilised PRO measures and evaluated stiffness in terms of its duration – usually in minutes, rarely in hours – and severity – mostly in a NRS or VAS from zero = none to ten or one hundred = maximum, rarely in a verbal scale (VS) or Likert scale (LS). Most studies used individual questions for assessing stiffness and in a smaller number of studies authors utilised validated instruments that contained one or more questions about stiffness. All instruments are PROs, with the exception of one that uses a wearable device for assessing stiffness and pain (Perraudin et al., 2018). Of note, a NRS (0-10 Likert scale) will be used to assess stiffness in The IPROLEPSIS PDPID study (T5.2). Supplementary data regarding stiffness assessment in Rheumatoid Arthritis is summarized in **Supplementary Table 1**.

Table 1 Instruments available in literature for assessing stiffness in PsA.

Ref.	Type	Population	Axial/Peripheral	Instrument	PRO	Domains	Measurements	Rating	Accuracy
(Herzog et al., 1989)	OS	RA, PsA	NA	1 question	Yes	1. Duration	1. NA	1. NA	NA
(Wilfert et al., 1990)	OS	PsA	NA	1 question	Yes	1. Duration	1. NA	1. NA	NA
(Dougados et al., 1992)	OS	SpA (including PsA)	NA	1 question	Yes	1. Presence	1. NA	1. Yes/No	NA
(Fraser et al., 1993)	RCT	PsA	NA	1 question	Yes	1. Duration	1. NA	1. Minutes	NA
(Hazes et al., 1993)	OS	IA (RA, PsA, SpA, SLE, Gout) and NIA (OA, FM)	NA	Set of questions	Yes	1. Severity 2. Severity 3. Duration 4. Duration 5. Duration	1. NA 2. NA 3. How long does your MS last until it begins to improve? 4. How long does your MS last until maximum improvement occurs? 5. How long does it take you to get going properly?	1. 10-cm VAS 2. 11-point NRS 3. Minutes 4. Minutes 5. Minutes	NA

Ref.	Type	Population	Axial/Peripheral	Instrument	PRO	Domains	Measurements	Rating	Accuracy
(Veale et al., 1994)	RCT	PsA	NA	1 question	Yes	1. Duration	1. NA	1. Minutes	NA
(Dougados et al., 1995)	RCT	AxSpA, PsA, ReA	Axial	1 question	Yes	1. Duration	1. NA	1. Minutes	NA
(Combe et al., 1996)	RCT	PsA	NA	1 question	Yes	1. Duration	1. NA	1. Minutes	NA
(Jorstad et al., 1998)	OS	PsA	NA	1 question	Yes	1. Duration	1. NA	1. Hours	NA
(Clegg et al., 1999)	RCT	AxSpA, PsA, ReA	Axial	1 question	Yes	1. Presence 2. Duration	1. NA 2. NA	1. Yes/No 2. Hours	NA
(Elkayam, Yaron, et al., 2000)	OS	PsA	NA	1 question	Yes	1. Duration	1. NA	1. Minutes	NA
(Elkayam, Ophir, Brener, et al., 2000)	RCT	PsA	Peripheral	1 question	Yes	1. Duration	1. NA	1. Minutes	NA
(Sarzi-Puttini et al., 2001)	RCT	PsA	NA	1 question	Yes	1. Duration	1. NA	1. <30min/≥30min	NA
(Cristián Labarca et al., 2003)	OS	RA, PsA, SpA	NA	1 question	Yes	1. Duration	1. NA	1. Minutes	NA
(Salvarani et al., 2003)	OS	PsA	NA	1 question	Yes	1. Duration	1. NA	1. Minutes	NA
(Cauza et al., 2006)	OS	PsA	NA	1 question	Yes	1. Duration	1. NA	1. Minutes	NA

Ref.	Type	Population	Axial/Peripheral	Instrument	PRO	Domains	Measurements	Rating	Accuracy
(Walker et al., 2006)	OS	PsA	NA	1 question	Yes	1. Duration	1. NA	1. Minutes	NA
(Husted et al., 2007)	OS	PsA	NA	1 question	Yes	1. Presence	1. NA	1. Yes/No	NA
(Liao et al., 2009)	OS	SpA (including PsA)	NA	1 question	Yes	1. Presence	1. Have you had MS?	1. Yes/No	NA
(Turan et al., 2009)	OS	SpA (including PsA)	NA	1 question	Yes	1. Duration	1. NA	1. Minutes	NA
(El Miedany et al., 2010)	OS	RA, PsA, IBD-SpA	NA	PROMsQ (1 question)	Yes	1. Presence 2. Duration	1. Over the last week when you awoke in the morning, did you feel stiff? 2. Please indicate the number of minutes or hours until you are as limber as you will be for the day.	1. Yes/No 2. Minutes	Moderate correlation with tender joint count in PsA (r=0.60, p<0.01).
(Tenga et al., 2011)	OS	SpA (including PsA)	NA	1 question	Yes	1. Duration	1. NA	1. Minutes	NA
(Baranauskaite et al., 2012)	RCT	PsA	NA	1 question	Yes	1. Duration	1. NA	1. Hours	NA

Ref.	Type	Population	Axial/Peripheral	Instrument	PRO	Domains	Measurements	Rating	Accuracy
(Gniadecki et al., 2012)	RCT	PsA	NA	1 question	Yes	1. Duration	1. NA	1. Minutes	NA
(Leung et al., 2012)	OS	PsA	NA	1 question	Yes	1. Duration	1. NA	1. NA	Weak correlation with PGA ($r=0.26$, $p<0.01$).
(Bandinelli et al., 2013)	OS	PsA	NA	1 question	Yes	1. Duration	1. NA	1. Minutes	NA
(Kragstrup et al., 2014)	OS	SpA (including PsA)	NA	2 questions	Yes	1. Severity 2. Duration	1. NA 2. NA	1. 100-point NRS 2. 100-point NRS	NA
(van Nies et al., 2015)	OS	Patients with arthralgia (including PsA)	NA	Set of questions	Yes	1. Presence 2. Duration 3. Presence 4. Duration 5. Presence 6. Duration 7. Severity	1. Do you experience stiffness when you get up in the morning? 2. If so for how many minutes? 3. Do you experience MS? 4. If yes, for how long? 5. Do you experience in stiffness in your joints in the morning?	1. Yes/No 2. Minutes 3. Yes/No 4. Minutes 5. 1. Yes/No 6. Minutes 7. 100-mm VAS	Both severity and duration of MS correlated moderately with each other, and the AUC of MS severity was not superior to that of MS duration.

Ref.	Type	Population	Axial/Peripheral	Instrument	PRO	Domains	Measurements	Rating	Accuracy
							6. And if so, how long does this stiffness endure? 7. NA		
(Baskan et al., 2016)	OS	PsA	NA	1 question	Yes	1. Duration	1. NA	1. NA	NA
(Benucci et al., 2017)	OS	SpA (including PsA)	NA	1 question	Yes	1. Duration	1. NA	1. NA	NA
(Eder et al., 2017)	OS	PsA	Both	Set of questions	Yes	1. Presence (peripheral) 2. Presence (axial) 3. Duration (peripheral) 4. Severity (peripheral)	1. NA 2. NA 3. NA 4. NA	1. Yes/No 2. Yes/No 3. <30min/≥30min 4. 0-10 VAS	NA
(Mease, Palmer, et al., 2018)	OS	SpA (including PsA)	NA	2 questions	Yes	1. Presence 2. Duration	1. NA 2. NA	1. Yes/No 2. <30min/≥30min	NA
(Nash et al., 2018)	RCT	PsA	NA	2 questions	Yes	1. Severity 2. Duration	1. NA 2. NA	1. NA 2. Minutes	NA
(Kavanaugh et al., 2018)	OS	PsA, RA	NA	2 questions	Yes	1. Presence	1. NA	1. Yes/No	NA

Ref.	Type	Population	Axial/Peripheral	Instrument	PRO	Domains	Measurements	Rating	Accuracy
						2. Duration	2. NA	2. <1h / >1h	
(Kwan et al., 2019)	OS	AxSpA	NA	BASDAI (Question 6)	Yes	1. Duration	1. How long does your MS last from the time you wake up?	1. 0-10 NRS	MS duration showed moderate accuracy to differentiate active from inactive disease (AUC 0.74; IC 95% 0.72–0.75).
(Xie et al., 2019)	OS	SpA	NA	1 question	Yes	1. Duration	1. NA	1. Minutes	NA
(Carević et al., 2020)	RCT	PsA	NA	1 question	Yes	1. Duration	1. NA	1. Minutes	NA
(Martin, 2020)	OS	PsA	NA	1 question	Yes	1. Severity	1. NA	1. 0-10 NRS	NA
(Dubash et al., 2021)	OS	PsA	NA	1 question	Yes	1. Duration	1. NA	1. Minutes	NA
(Duruoz et al., 2021)	OS	PsA	NA	1 question	Yes	1. Duration	1. NA	1. Minutes	NA
(Mease, McLean, et al., 2021)	OS	PsA	NA	1 question	Yes	1. Duration	1. NA	1. <30min/≥ 30min	NA
(Mease, Lertratanakul, et al., 2021)	RCT	PsA	NA	BASDAI (Mean of questions 5 and 6)	Yes	1. Severity 2. Duration	1. How would you describe the overall level of MS you have had from the time you wake up?	1. 10-cm VAS 2. 10-cm VAS	NA

Ref.	Type	Population	Axial/Peripheral	Instrument	PRO	Domains	Measurements	Rating	Accuracy
							2. How long does your MS last from the time you wake up?		
(Ramadan et al., 2021)	OS	PsA	NA	1 question	Yes	1. Duration	1. NA	1. Minutes	NA
(Strand et al., 2021)	RCT	PsA	NA	<i>BASDAI</i> (Mean of questions 5 and 6)	Yes	1. Severity 2. Duration	1. How would you describe the overall level of MS you have had from the time you wake up? 2. How long does your MS last from the time you wake up?	1. 10-cm VAS 2. 10-cm VAS	NA
(Khraishi et al., 2022)	OS	PsA	NA	1 question	Yes	1. Duration	1. NA	1. Minutes	NA
(Siebert et al., 2023)	OS	PsA	NA	2 questions	Yes	1. Severity 2. Duration	1. NA 2. NA	1. 100-point SSR 2. 100-point SSR	NA
(Loza et al., 2023)	OS	SpA (including PsA)	NA	1 question	Yes	1. Duration	1. NA	1. 10-point NRS	NA
New Measures									
Ref.	Type	Population	Axial/Peripheral	Instrument	PRO	Domains	Measurements	Rating	Accuracy

Ref.	Type	Population	Axial/Peripheral	Instrument	PRO	Domains	Measurements	Rating	Accuracy
(Craig et al., 2019)	OS	RA, PsA	NA	<i>RAST</i>	Yes	1. Severity 2. Physical effect 3. Psychosocial effect	Supplementary Table 2	Supplementary Table 2	Supplementary Table 3
(Perraudin et al., 2018)	OS	RA, PsA, OA	NA	4 questions	Yes	1. Presence 2. Severity 3. Severity during day 4. Duration	1. Were your joints stiff when you woke up today? 2. Please rate the activities in each category according to the following scale of difficulty: severity upon waking up, first thing in the morning. 3. Please rate the activities in each category according to the following scale of difficulty: severity after sitting, lying down, or resting during the day. 4. How long did this stiffness last?	1. Yes/No 2. 0–4 NRS 3. 0-4 NRS 4. 30min, 30min-1h, 1–2h, 2–4h, 4h, all day, none.	NA

Ref.	Type	Population	Axial/Peripheral	Instrument	PRO	Domains	Measurements	Rating	Accuracy
			NA	Wearable sensor	No	1. Severity	1. 5×STS test duration	1. NA	5×STS test duration has a positive correlation with 5 out of 8 PRO.
(Orbai et al., 2014)	OS	RA	NA	3 stiffness items	Yes	1. Severity 2. Duration 3. Interference with daily activities	Supplementary Table 4	Supplementary Table 4	Responsiveness in states of change in several clinical anchors and longitudinal construct validity was seen for all 3 items.
(Oh et al., 2021)	OS	RA	NA	MSAS	Yes	1. Duration 2. Intensity 3. Localization 4. Variability 5. Influence in pain/functional disability 6. Influence in work performance 7. Influence	Supplementary Table 5	Supplementary Table 5	Supplementary Table 6

Ref.	Type	Population	Axial/Peripheral	Instrument	PRO	Domains	Measurements	Rating	Accuracy
						in psychological well-being 8. Influence in quality of life			

AxSpA: Axial Spondyloarthritis; BASDAI: Bath Ankylosing Spondylitis Functional Index; ES: Effect size; FM: Fibromyalgia; IA: Inflammatory arthritis; IBD-SpA: Inflammatory bowel disease associated spondyloarthritis; LS: Likert scale; MS: Morning stiffness; NA: Not available; NIA: Non-inflammatory arthritis; NRS: Numerical scale; MSAS: Morning Stiffness Assessment Scale; OA: Osteoarthritis; OS: Observational study; PGA: Patient Global Assessment; PRO: Patient-reported outcome; PROMsQ: Multidimensional patient-reported outcome measure questionnaire; PsA: Psoriatic arthritis; RA: Rheumatoid arthritis; RAST: Rheumatoid arthritis stiffness; ReA: Reactive Arthritis; RCT: Randomized control trial; SLE: Systemic Lupus Erythematosus; SpA: Spondyloarthritis; SSR: slider scale rating; VAS: Visual analogue scale; VS: Verbal scale.

Instruments accuracy

Very limited data on accuracy was found in our literature review. This information is summarized in **Table 1**.

New ways of measuring stiffness

Research groups continue to pursue the goal of developing the finest instrument for measuring stiffness in rheumatic diseases. In this section, we introduce four new methods of measuring stiffness in patients diagnosed with RA, PsA and SpA.

Rheumatoid arthritis stiffness (RAST)

The RAST (RA stiffness PROM) was presented at OMERACT meeting in 2016. This is a 21-item questionnaire which addresses 3 domains of stiffness: severity, physical effect, and psychosocial effect (**Supplementary Table 2**). RAST was tested in patients with PsA and RA and ratings of stiffness severity, duration, and effect were comparable between both diseases (Halls et al., 2017).

Studies evaluating psychometric properties of this new PRO have been emerging (**Supplementary Table 3**). The RAST should now be tested in independent longitudinal studies to accumulate evidence on more psychometric properties, including a longitudinal survey to establish reliability and responsiveness (Craig et al., 2019).

3 stiffness items

The 3 stiffness items PRO is used in RA patients and assesses three stiffness domains rated through a 5-point NRS: severity, duration, and interference with daily activities. For evaluation of psychometric properties, a 100-mm visual analogue scale (VAS) rating stiffness intensity was added and completed by a subset of patients. Data offered preliminary evidence of construct validity based upon correlation with other PROs expected to correlate with stiffness. Responsiveness in states of change in several clinical anchors and longitudinal construct validity were also seen for all 3 items. Among the participants who completed both VAS and NRS items, the stiffness VAS, which did not specify a subdomain, correlated most strongly with the stiffness severity score. A score of “none” in severity corresponded to a median VAS of 0, “mild” to a VAS of 15, “moderate” to a VAS of 60, and “severe” to a VAS of 85 (Orbai et al., 2014).

Morning Stiffness Assessment Scale (MSAS)

The MSAS is a 10-item PRO based on a comprehensive model for stiffness evaluation in which MS attributes are classified into two dimensions: characteristics of MS and overall impact of MS. Characteristics of MS include duration, intensity, localisation and variability of MS. Items addressing overall impact of MS refer to those that influence other RA symptoms: pain or functional disability, work performance, psychological well-being, and quality of life. Responses to most items are rated using a 4-point Likert scale: strongly agree, agree to some extent, disagree to some extent and not agree at all. Responses to the item on MS intensity are: very stiff, somewhat stiff, almost no stiffness and no stiffness. Responses to the item on MS duration are: within 10 minutes of awaking, within 30 minutes of awaking, more than 60 minutes of awaking, within 3 hours of awaking and almost all day (Oh et al., 2021).

Exploratory factor analysis supported construct validity and showed that the two dimensions of the MSAS had acceptable total variance, which indicated adequate explanatory power. Furthermore, MSAS significantly correlated with pain, functional disability and quality of life scores, and significantly explained quality of life even in the presence of two other predictors

(pain and functional disability), which verified nomological validity. In addition, the MSAS had high internal consistency, indicating good reliability (**Supplementary Table 6**) (Oh et al., 2021).

2.3.2.2 Digital measurement of stiffness

Wearable sensor-based system

The use of wearable sensors is based on the assumption that the best way to evaluate morning pain and stiffness is to directly measure their impact on motor function, focusing on tasks such as stiffness to stand and gait. This method uses information captured by Five Times Sit to Stand (5×STS) test performance through an accelerometer and analyses the correlation between performance impairment and morning pain and stiffness in patients with RA, PsA and OA. A mixed-effects model was built to predict the severity of morning pain and stiffness via 5×STS duration, disease type, and gender. To increase prediction accuracy, the model also considers other covariates that possibly affect pain and stiffness: age, gender, body mass index, seconds since getting up, and disease type. A high correlation between 5×STS test duration and pain severity was demonstrated. Among stiffness-related PROs, the strongest relationship was to MS severity (Perraudin et al., 2018).

2.3.3 Datasets

To the best of our knowledge there are no open-source datasets that assess stiffness in PsA patients. As summarised in **Table 1**, the majority of the studies rely on self-report by the patient, with the exception of one study that collected accelerometer data for four weeks in healthy individuals and people diagnosed with RA, PsA and osteoarthritis. Study participants wore accelerometers on their wrists for the duration of the study and were asked to perform the 5xSTS test in the morning three times per week. At the same time, patients self-reported pain and stiffness via a questionnaire available in a smartphone app. Through a mixed-effects model, the Perraudin et al. demonstrated that the time taken to complete the 5xSTS test was correlated to the pain and stiffness intensity reported via the PROs.

In the iPROLEPSIS consortium, clinical partners have available retrospective PsA datasets. The MONITOR (n = 260) cohort includes a question about the duration in minutes of MS, and Reuma.pt (n = 3521) collects information about disease activity utilising a validated instrument, BASDAI, that includes questions about stiffness.

Section highlight

Summary of findings, measurement tools and identified datasets for each symptom are depicted in Table 3 and **Table 4**. Fatigue, pain and stiffness are commonly reported symptoms of PsA. Inflammatory cytokines, certain brain structures, and the HPA axis have been involved in the pathway signaling of these symptoms. Clinical measurement of these symptoms is mainly through questionnaires. The use of smartphone and wearable to monitor physical activity (mainly through accelerometer data), heart rate, heart rate variability have also shown potential to measure these symptoms. Datasets for clinical measurement of these symptoms have been also identified, mainly from the existing cohorts of clinical partners (DEPAR, MONITOR and Reuma.pt). For digital biomarkers, two datasets have been identified for monitoring fatigue and stiffness.

3 Triggers and consequences of flare in psoriatic arthritis

3.1 Mood

3.1.1 State-of-art

Psoriasis and PsA are known to have a key impact on mood with increased prevalence of anxiety, depression and other mental health impacts. A number of studies have investigated the prevalence of depression and anxiety in PsA. There are two published systematic literature reviews that summarise the prevalence of depression in PsA. The first, by Kamalaraj et al, included 3 clinical studies looking at point prevalence of depression in people with PsA as defined by CASPAR criteria (Kamalaraj et al., 2019). It also included 3 additional studies in PsA but without CASPAR criteria recorded. The initial 3 studies found a prevalence of 9-22% of depression with a pooled prevalence of 15% (confidence interval [CI] 9-21%). When including the additional 3 studies, the prevalence estimate did not change with a pooled prevalence of 15% (95% CI 8-23%). The prevalence of anxiety was 25% (95% CI 15-35%) and varied from 11 to 34% in the different studies.

A second systematic review, by Zusman et al, included 18 studies (Zusman et al., 2020). Additional studies relying on administrative data and electronic records studies were included here. Meta-analysis was performed with studies using ICD codes and the HADS as these were the most common. The pooled prevalence proportion of depression based on 11 studies with a total of 127,638 PsA patients was 17% (95% CI, 13% to 21%). A meta-analysis of four studies that compared the prevalence of depression in patients with PsA to those without PsA yielded a pooled odds ratio (OR) of 1.68 (95% CI, 1.37 to 2.38). Finally, the incidence of depression in PsA patients compared to individuals without PsA was reported in six studies with meta-analysis of five studies using ICD-9 codes to assess depression resulting in a pooled incidence rate of 21.27 (95% CI, 16.28, 26.27) per 1000 person-years and a pooled incidence rate ratio of 1.44 (95% CI, 1.20 to 1.73). The pooled prevalence proportion of anxiety based on seven studies and 18,604 PsA patients was 19% (95% CI, 11% to 29%). Only two studies compared the prevalence of anxiety in patients with PsA to individuals without, with meta-analysis yielding a pooled OR of 1.49 (95% CI, 1.39 to 1.59). Only 1 included study assessed the incidence of anxiety among patients with PsA, reporting an incidence rate per 1000 person-years of 39.6 (95% CI, 29.2 to 53.7).

A third systematic review looked at wider aspects of mental health comorbidities in PsA but found that depression and anxiety were the only consistently reported mental health disorders (S. S. Zhao et al., 2020). This analysis found 24 studies including a total of 31,227 patients. Anxiety prevalence ranged from 4 to 61% with a pooled estimate of 33% (95%CI 17 to 53%) having at least mild anxiety and 21% (95%CI 14 to 29%) at least moderate. Depression prevalence ranged from 5 to 51%, with 20% (95%CI 8 to 35%) having at least mild and 14% (95%CI 8 to 21%) at least moderate.

In addition to quantitative studies, a number of qualitative studies have addressed the patient perspective of psoriasis and psoriatic arthritis including impact on mood. A systemic literature review (SLR) of 56 qualitative studies involving 1,484 patients with psoriasis and 337 patients with PsA examined the impact of psoriatic disease (Sumpton et al., 2020). This summary identified 6 key themes of impact (Figure 7) including a number of different ways that the disease may impact mood.

Figure 7 Associations with disease measures. Source: (Sumpton et al., 2020)

In the first SLR, only one study looked at the associations with depression/anxiety. In this study, McDonough et al. identified that the factors associated with depression and anxiety were unemployment (depression only), higher actively inflamed joint counts and a poorer score on the physician global score (McDonough et al., 2014). Psoriasis severity was not associated with depression or anxiety. In the second SLR, associations with disease activity could not be studied given limitations from the design of the included studies.

In the third SLR, they identified only two studies compared disease activity according to the presence of mental health comorbidities; both reported higher disease activity and pain among those with comorbid anxiety and depression. Freire et al. found that DAS28 (3.2 vs 2.9 $p < 0.05$) and pain VAS (4.1 vs 3.0 $p < 0.01$) were higher in patients with anxiety than those without. Similarly, DAS28 and pain VAS were higher in those with depression than those without. BASDAI was only assessed in a small subgroup, thus comparisons were underpowered (Freire et al., 2011). Michelsen et al. compared those with and without anxiety or depression. In addition to DAS28 and pain VAS, they also found differences in the tender joint count, patient and evaluators global, but not swollen joint count, ESR or CRP (Michelsen B et al., 2017).

A final SLR looked at the impact of comorbidities on PROs in PsA and included 2 studies that looked at anxiety and depression as the key comorbidity (Canete et al., 2020; Carneiro et al., 2017; Gubar et al., 2018). Other comorbidities included obesity, fibromyalgia or lists of mixed comorbidities. Anxiety and depression were examined in two small cross-sectional studies using the Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale (HADS) questionnaire. Both studies found weak–moderate correlations with function and fatigue.

3.1.2 Measurement

A number of studies in the literature have not measured impact on mood but have used a diagnosis of depression or anxiety based on physician report, patient report or administrative codes in routine datasets.

3.1.2.1 Clinical measurement of depression and anxiety

When considering measures of depression and anxiety, the most used are shown below.

Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale (HADS)

The scale consists of 14 questions that can be used to identify depression (7 questions) and anxiety (7 questions). Each question is scored 0-3 giving a score of 0-21 for each component. Normal is defined as scores 0-7, borderline scores 8-10 and abnormal (or case definition of anxiety/depression) as 11 or more.

Patient Health Questionnaire (PHQ-9)

The questionnaire consists of 9 questions scored 0-3 to measure depression. The total score is categorized as: 0-5 – mild, 6-10 – moderate, 11-15 – moderately severe, 16 or more – severe depression. The PHQ-9 will be used in the iPROLEPSIS PDPID study (T5.2).

Hamilton Depression Rating Scale (HDRS)

The scale is also known as the HAM-D scale. It consists of 17 items and was designed more for inpatient use. Scores of 0-7 are considered normal while scores of 20 or more define moderate depression.

Zung Self-rating Depression Scale (ZDS)

The scale contains 20 items, 10 worded positively, and 10 negatively. Items are on a one to four scale; raw scores are converted into a percentage by dividing the sum of all questions by 0.80. Conventional cutoffs are 25–43 for no depression, 50–59 for mild to moderate depression, 60–69 for moderate to severe depression, and 70 or over for severe depression.

Hamilton Anxiety Rating Scale (HAM-A)

The scale consists of 14 items and measures both psychic anxiety (mental agitation and psychological distress) and somatic anxiety (physical complaints related to anxiety). Each item is scored on a scale of 0 (not present) to 4 (severe), with a total score range of 0–56, where <17 indicates mild severity, 18–24 mild to moderate severity and 25–30 moderate to severe.

3.1.3 Datasets

No datasets were identified.

3.2 Stress**3.2.1 State-of-art**

There is a continuous talk between the immune system and the stress axis to adapt the body to changes in the environment (**Figure 8**) (Russell & Lightman, 2019). In people with PsA this translates to the immune system alerting the stress system when inflammation occurs causing distress in people leading them to feel not their best version of themselves. Also, if external stressors activate the stress axis for longer time it results in a pro-inflammatory status of the immune system. Within PsA there is little work done to measure the impact of stress.

Stress is a complex orchestration of processes in the human body that aim to optimise survival in times of crisis (Mueller et al., 2022). This crisis could be elicited by physical trauma and disease. However, the same systems will be activated due to lack of sleep, social or psychological trauma and pain (Garbarino et al., 2021; Ibarra-Coronado et al., 2015; Irwin, 2019). The stress-trigger prompts a crosstalk between the ANS, the endocrine system (HPA axis) and the immune system (**Figure 9**). The crosstalk itself goes unnoticed but increased heart rate, alertness and decreased bowel motility are some of the initial physical signs.

Figure 9 Crosstalk between autonomous nervous system, hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal and immune system. Source: (Mueller et al., 2022)

Figure 10 Interpretation of stress signals. Source: (Mueller et al., 2022)

Minutes later a second message follows. Glucocorticoids are secreted from the adrenal cortex. Glucocorticoids maintain energy homeostasis and, under stress conditions, keep blood glucose levels high to facilitate flight-or-fight responses (Sapolsky et al., 2000). Glucocorticoids suppress the immune system by prohibiting the white blood cells to release their signal proteins facilitated by blocking some of the receptors on the cell membrane. This reduces the size of the inflammatory response (Udit et al., 2022). All this happens within minutes of the stressor being interpreted by the brain (Mueller et al., 2022; Russell & Lightman, 2019).

Stressors come in all forms and shapes. To inform the brain about local and systemic threats of tissue, messages are sent via nerves, blood and lymph (Mueller et al., 2022). When for example a pathogen enters the body, white blood cells called T-cells release tiny proteins called cytokines in the tissue. Cytokines broadcast the nature and severity of the attack to the rest of the body so that other immune cells can mount an appropriate defence. This is then picked up by the vagal nerve. The nerve projects this information in the brainstem from where it is reported to the hypothalamus.

The vagal nerve has a central role in picking up systemic stress signals (e.g., cytokines, low sugar levels, pain signals) (Mueller et al., 2022; Udit et al., 2022). It is a bidirectional nerve bundle that originates in the brainstem and communicates both upstream and downstream. Downstream it innervates the cardiovascular and gastrointestinal system to modulate heart rate and gastrointestinal motility and informs the spleen to activate an anti-inflammatory response. However, most of the messages go upstream and carry visceral information from almost every organ system to the brainstem. It also plays an important role in the “gut-brain” axis by stimulating gastric acid production, promoting motility, and modulating immune cell activity within gastrointestinal mucosa.

Besides the messaging via the nervus vagus, there is a more direct but slower route that informs the brain about systemic stress signals (Mueller et al., 2022; Russell & Lightman, 2019). One route is via glucocorticoids. Glucocorticoids can easily cross the blood-brain-barrier and target many brain structures expressing mineralocorticoid and glucocorticoid receptors. In particular, glucocorticoids influence regions critically involved in emotional learning and memory as well as emotion regulation processes such as the medial temporal lobe (hippocampus and amygdala) and prefrontal areas. The other route is via the signal molecules themselves, such as cytokines. If released in the bloodstream they will pass the circumventricular organs in the brain. These circumventricular organs are midline structures around the third and fourth ventricles in the brain that are in contact with blood and cerebrospinal fluid. They facilitate special types of communication between the central nervous system and peripheral blood. It is here where cytokines can inform their counterparts in the brain to increase cytokine activity in the brain.

3.2.2 Measurement

Although stress is mostly associated with its maladaptive effects (Russell & Lightman, 2019), it is an essential physiological response that plays a central role in synchronizing the neural, hormonal and immunological pathway in anticipation of an upcoming challenge or in response to a challenge. Due to the wide spread effect of stress in the body, it could be measured in many tissues (**Table 2**) (Chen et al., 2021). Some are, however, easier to determine than others. In **Table 2** relevant organ systems are mentioned with their effect separated for acute and chronic stress.

Measuring up- and downregulation of the stress systems started in the early 60ties of the previous century but is still complicated. This is because of the transient states and the temporal delay of one system involving or influencing another.

Table 2 Relevant organ systems for measurement of stress

Organ	Sign	Acute	Chronic
Heart (Karemaker, 2020)	Heart rate	Increases	Probably subtle increase
	Heart rate variability	Less variable, but may not only be related to stress	
Lungs (Chen et al., 2021)	Respiration frequency	Increased	Probably subtle change
	Localisation of breath	High in the thorax	Tend to creep up in the thorax under chronic stress
	Depth	Decreased	
Skin (Pearlmutter et al., 2020)	Perspiration	Increased	Increased
	Conductivity	Increased	Increased
	Dryness	Unknown	Unknown
Eyes (Tovote et al., 2015)	Pupils	Enlarged	Unknown
Mouth (Pearlmutter et al., 2020)	Saliva	Decreased	Decreased
Muscle (Chen et al., 2021)	Tone	Increased	Unknown/Increased
	Posture	Upright	Bowed and sloppy, unfocused
GI track (Bonaz et al., 2017)	Motility	Decreased or increased	Decreased
	Acid production	Decreased	Increased
	Appetite	Decreased	Increased
Brain (Chesnut et al., 2021; Niemeijer et al., 2022)	Alertness	Increased	Decreased
	Sleep	Decreased	Increased or decreased
	Sleep quality	Unknown	Decreased slow wave sleep
	Memory	Decreased and increased	Decreased
	Emotion	Specific and focussed	Easily irritated, crying and other negative emotions. Lack of joy
Adrenal glands (Sapolsky et al., 2000)	GC secretion (cortisol)	Increased	Increased

GI, gastrointestinal.

3.2.2.1 Clinical and biological measurement of stress

A number of questionnaires have been used to assess stress: perceived stress scale (PSS), LSSI, 4DSQ, C-SOSI and PSQ. The PSS is commonly used when assessing stress. The scale comprises of 10 questions and assesses stress over the past month. Response to each question is on a scale of 0 (Never) to 4 (Very often). Other versions of the scale are also available (PSS-4 and PSS-12).

Besides questionnaires, cortisol is considered a potential diagnostic marker for stress. Hair cortisol measurement (cut at the posterior vertex) has been used in various studies as a proxy

of stress. Hair grows at a rate of 1cm per month, therefore 1cm of hair would represent average cortisol release of the past month.

In the iPROLEPSIS PDPID study (T5.2), PSS and hair cortisol will be used to assess stress.

3.2.2.2 Digital measurement of stress

Heart Rate Variability

One effector area needs specific attention. The use of HRV has expanded into many areas of biomedical research and even into smart watches and other smart devices such as wrist bands, rings and breast bands. Still, in accepted medical practice HRV is at best a side note in a Holter monitoring report (i.e., a 24 h ambulatory electrocardiography (ECG)-recording) (Karemaker, 2020). Why this difference in appreciation? The HRV is not a simple feature manipulated via one source. Generally speaking, fast, beat-to-beat variations in heart rate are parasympathetic, vagally mediated. The slower changes, extending over many beats, are mainly due to sympathetic nervous influences. Heart rate changes over long periods (tens of seconds to minutes and hours) are due to humoral factors like NE, vasopressin and angiotensin. Each of these features are modified by respiration rate, respiration depth and blood pressure changes. This does not necessarily mean that HRV is an unusable stress marker. It needs careful consideration when applied to measure stress in a condition like Psoriatic Arthritis. It certainly does not tell a story when taking a short snapshot in time. Tracking a person's HRV over time, especially during the night, may better depict its role in measuring stress when inflammation is developing.

3.2.3 Datasets

There are currently no datasets that assess stress in PsA. There are several other diseases and general studies that tried to capture stress using different means.

3.3 Sleep

3.3.1 State-of-art

Sleeping patterns change due to inflammation and change in sleeping patterns could elicit inflammation (Garbarino et al., 2021; Ibarra-Coronado et al., 2015; Irwin, 2019). No data are yet available among psoriatic arthritis nor rheumatoid arthritis patients. One study described the protocol for measuring sleeping patterns using a smart watch (Crouthamel et al., 2021). A graphical depiction of the biochemical mechanisms associated with sleep deprivation is depicted in **Figure 11**.

Regarding the relationship between sleep and PsA, a recent review and meta-analysis paper summarizes the evidence from 36 relevant studies. Specifically, the prevalence of self-reported sleep problems in patients with PsA ranged from 30-85%. This wide difference in rates is justified by the inconsistency in terminology used for defining sleep problem, as well as the variety of measurement instruments, i.e., the questionnaires. Meta-analysis of six studies that used the Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index, which is the most used sleep assessment PROM, revealed a prevalence of poor sleep quality for patients with PsA of 72.9%, statistically higher than in healthy controls (26.9%), but not significantly different than patients with PsO (59.8%). However, it should be noted that the latter meta-analysis has a few limitations regarding the large heterogeneity identified and the small number of included studies. Further analysis resulted that anxiety, pain, ESR, emotional recovery, depression, fatigue, physical function, and tender or swollen joint count can be predictors of sleep problems in patients with PsA. Nevertheless, the bidirectionality of the association between these predictors and sleep was not proved. Moreover, since some studies included interventions, it was found that TNF-inhibitors, guselkumab, and filgotinib were associated with improved sleep, but the value of

the results is questionable since only two out of six studies were randomized controlled trails (RCTs) and sleep was not the primary outcome in any of those studies. Finally, a conclusion was that only self-reported sleep measures have been used in existing clinical studies, i.e., subjective measures. Thus, objective measures, i.e., actigraphy and/or polysomnography, should be incorporated and combined with existing subjective measures in the future studies to reveal insights of the sleep-PsA relationship.

Figure 11 Sleep deprivation, immune response and inflammation. Source: (Garbarino et al., 2021).

Sleep deprivation, as induced experimentally or in the context of habitual short sleep, has been found to be associated with alterations in the circulating numbers and/or activity of total leukocytes and specific cell subsets, elevation of systemic and tissue (e.g., brain) pro-inflammatory markers including cytokines (e.g., IL, TNF- α), chemokines and acute phase proteins (such as CRP), altered antigen presentation (reduced dendritic cells, altered pattern of activating cytokines, etc.), lowered Th1 response, higher Th2 response, and reduced antibody production. Furthermore, altered monocytes responsiveness to immunological challenges such as lipopolysaccharide may contribute to sleep deprivation-associated immune modulation. Hypothesized links between immune dysregulation by sleep deprivation and the risk for immune related diseases, such as infectious, cardiovascular, metabolic, and neurodegenerative and neoplastic diseases, are shown (Garbarino et al., 2021)

3.3.2 Measurement

Sleep assessment can be made with a wide variety of methods which present different properties. A taxonomy of sleep detection methods which was developed in (Ibáñez et al., 2018) is shown in **Figure 12**. The main classification refers to the involvement or not of a medical expert, i.e., “Medical Assistance” versus “Self-Assessment” methods. Moreover, another classification is about subjectivity.

Figure 12 Taxonomy of sleep assessment methods. Source: (Ibáñez et al., 2018)

Questionnaires and sleep diaries are considered subjective against the rest which incorporate measurements collected by devices or experts. Moreover, each method has different level of reliability. If the methods are arranged based on their accuracy, the order will be:

Questionnaire < Sleep diary < Contactless devices < Contact devices < Polysomnography (PSG)

In the remaining of the subsection a selection of the methods is described in more detail, i.e., polysomnography, Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index questionnaire, Consensus Sleep Diary and wrist band actigraphy because these are commonly used in practice as well as in clinical studies. Moreover, the Jenkins Sleep Scale questionnaire is briefly described as it is the only questionnaire that has been validated in PsA.

3.3.2.1 Clinical measurement of sleep

The Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index

Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (PSQI) is the most widely used sleep PROM in clinical and non-clinical populations (Buysse et al., 1989). The questionnaire consists of 19 self-reported items organized into seven subcategories: subjective sleep quality, sleep latency, sleep duration, habitual sleep efficiency, sleep disturbances, use of sleeping medication, and daytime dysfunction. Moreover, there are five supplementary questions which are answered based on responder's bed partner or roommate viewpoint. These five questions are not scored but included for clinical purposes. The PSQI questionnaire requires between 5 and 10 minutes to complete. The items of the questionnaire are presented in **Supplementary Table 7**. The scoring system of the questionnaire is shown in **Supplementary Table 8** where each of the seven components derives a score from 0 (no difficulty) to 3 (severe difficulty) and, at the end, all component scores are summed up to result the total PSQI score (0-21).

The Jenkins Sleep Scale

Jenkins Sleep Scale (JSS) (Jenkins et al., 1988) is the only sleep PRO measure whose validity and reliability in PsA has been studied (Duruöz et al., 2017). This questionnaire consists of

four items that assess the frequency and intensity of sleep-related issues in the last month. The four items are: (1) trouble falling asleep, (2) trouble staying asleep, (3) wake up several times/night, and (4) wake up feeling tired. Each item is rated on a 6-point Likert scale: 0 = Not at all, 1 = 1-3 days, 2 = 4-7 days, 3 = 8-14 days, 4 = 15-21 days, 5 = 22-28 days. The total score is ranging from 0 to 20. Obviously, the larger the score the more disturbed the sleep is.

Other sleep PRO measure that have been occasionally used in studies where PsA patients were involved (Grant et al., 2023) are the Ottawa Sleep Scale, the PROMIS Sleep disturbance, the Epworth Sleepiness Scale, the Insomnia Severity Index, and the Medical Outcomes Sleep Scale. It should be noted that PsAID questionnaire includes a question about sleep disturbance that is “Circle the number that best describes the sleep difficulties (i.e., resting at night) you felt due to your psoriatic arthritis during the last week” and the patient rates from 0 (No difficulty) to 10 (Extreme difficulty).

Sleep diaries

Sleep diaries allow patients to self-assess sleep similarly to questionnaires. While sleep questionnaires are filled in once, sleep diaries are filled periodically during the investigation time. The main advantage of sleep diaries is that they are less dependent to patients' memory. Recollecting events or summarizing information happened two or three weeks ago cannot be very accurate. On the other hand, sleep diaries are filled every day usually just after waking up. Meaning that sleep diaries contain more representative information for sleep assessment than questionnaires. The Pittsburgh Sleep Diary (Monk et al., 1994) and the Consensus Sleep Diary (Carney et al., 2012) are the most widely used sleep diaries in clinical studies. An example of Consensus Sleep Diary is shown in **Supplementary Figure 1**.

Polysomnography

PSG is the gold standard technique to diagnose sleep disorders. During PSG, a collection of physiological functions is recorded including (Rundo & Downey, 2019): brain activity via electroencephalography (EEG), eye movement via electrooculography, muscle activity via electromyography, cardiac activity via ECG, oxygen saturation via pulse oximetry, and airflow and respiratory function via oral/nasal pressure sensors and chest/abdominal belts, respectively.

Additional body functions can be rarely recorded. These include capnography, i.e., the measurement of CO₂ concentration at the airway opening, snoring using microphones, body temperature, and blood pressure. A graphic illustration of the PSG setting along with a real PSG recording excerpt is shown in **Supplementary Figure 2**.

PSG is conducted in a sleep laboratory under the supervision of a PSG expert overnight. After the collection takes place, the gathered data are pre-processed and examined by a PSG expert to extract sleep stages (awake/NREM/REM or awake/N1/N2/N3/REM) and to detect peculiarities in other physiological functions, e.g., respiration and blood oxygen saturation. Sleep disorders that can be diagnosed with PSG are mainly sleep-related breathing disorders, e.g., obstructive sleep apnea, central sleep apnea, and sleep-related hypoventilation, but also, nocturnal seizures, narcolepsy, periodic limb movement disorder and rapid eye movement sleep behaviour disorder can be diagnosed. A diagram that summarizes the sleep disorders that can be evaluated with PSG is illustrated in **Supplementary Figure 3**.

3.3.2.2 Digital measurement of sleep

Actigraphy

Wrist actigraphy is an alternative of PSG where the sleep is measured only via movement (Martin & Hakim, 2011). Although wrist actigraphy cannot reveal in depth information about the sleep architecture, i.e., sleep staging, and physiology, it is comparable to PSG in sleep detection (awake/sleep) (Marino et al., 2013). Thus, wrist actigraphy can be used for identifying peculiarities in sleep schedule leading to mainly assessing insufficient sleep syndrome, insomnia and circadian rhythm sleep-wake disorders (Smith et al., 2018). An actigraphy device is worn like a watch on the wrist of the non-dominant hand and measures movement via accelerometer sensors. The data collection is usually performed over at least several days and often several weeks (McBeth et al., 2022). When the data collection is finished, the actigraphy device is returned to the doctor, who extracts and interprets the data. A graphical example of an actigraphy recording is shown in **Supplementary Figure 4**.

3.3.3 Datasets

Datasets that consist of sleep-related data collected from PsA patients do not exist. Nevertheless, datasets that can be useful in the project are those which contain sleep-related data collected from wearable devices. Thus, the dataset search scope was widened resulting one dataset that consists of accelerometer sensor data, heart rate and step counter from smartwatch during sleep sessions.

The “Motion and heart rate from a wrist-worn wearable and labelled sleep from polysomnography” (Walch, 2019; Walch et al., 2019) dataset contains acceleration (in units of g) and heart rate (bpm, measured from PSG) recorded from the Apple Watch, as well as labelled sleep scored from gold-standard polysomnography. Data were collected at the University of Michigan from June 2017 to March 2019, and there are 31 subjects in total.

3.4 Physical activity and fine motor skills

3.4.1 State-of-art

3.4.1.1 Physical activity

According to the World Health Organization (WHO) physical activity refers to “any bodily movement produced by skeletal muscles that requires energy expenditure”, i.e., refers to all movement including activities of daily life such as getting to and from work, shopping, cleaning, and exercise. WHO recommends at least 150-300 minutes of moderate-intensity aerobic physical activity; or at least 75–150 minutes of vigorous-intensity aerobic physical activity; or an equivalent combination of moderate- and vigorous-intensity activity throughout the week. Furthermore, EULAR (Rausch Osthoff et al., 2018) promotes physical activity for people with rheumatoid and musculoskeletal diseases.

A recent systematic review (Kessler et al., 2021) investigated the effects of physical activity in PsA and assessed the level of physical activity in PsA patients. The review included two epidemiological studies, three clinical trials, four safety studies and four rehabilitation programs. The epidemiological studies concerning physical activity practice in PsA suggested that PsA patients have a sedentary lifestyle. Moreover, the three clinical trials that investigated the benefit of physical activity revealed that exercise has demonstrable advantages in PsA, positively impacting disease activity, overall well-being, and comorbidities, i.e., reduced some cardiovascular risk factors in PsA. Additionally, available research concerning the risk factors of physical activity in PsA, i.e., the effects of physical activity in joints and entheses, revealed that the benefits of physical activity appear to outweigh the risk of enthesitis, and flares triggered by mechanical stress. Finally, research on rehabilitation programs, even if the

studies were very heterogeneous, showed that pain and fatigue levels were reduced for PsA patients, while functional capacity improved.

More specifically, regarding the benefits of physical activity on PsA, Thomsen et al. (Thomsen et al., 2019) assessed the impact of high-intensity interval training (HIIT) on disease activity and disease perception in PsA patients and its sustainability over time. Patients were randomly assigned to either an HIIT intervention group or a control group and were assessed at baseline, 3, and 6 months. HIIT did not substantially affect disease activity markers in PsA patients, but it significantly reduced fatigue, suggesting that PsA patients can tolerate HIIT with improvement in fatigue levels. In another study (Roger-Silva et al., 2017) assessed the effectiveness of resistance training in PsA patients. This study involved 41 PsA patients randomly divided into an intervention group and a control group. The former group was instructed to follow a resistance exercise program twice a week for 12 weeks, while the latter continued conventional drug therapy. Resistance training proved effective in enhancing functional capacity, reducing disease activity, and improving the quality of life in PsA patients, even though these clinical gains were not closely associated with significant changes in muscular strength.

Moreover, Wervers et al. (Wervers et al., 2019) investigated the association of physical activity and medication with enthesitis in PsA patients. More specifically, the relationship between ultrasonographic changes in entheses and clinical characteristics in 84 PsA patients was investigated and compared to 25 healthy controls of the same age. Data on complaints, physical activity and activity avoidance, medication, and clinical enthesitis were collected. The study revealed that lower levels of physical activity, younger age, and not using biologics were associated with less severity of enthesitis in PsA patients. While inflammatory changes of the entheses were similar between PsA patients and healthy controls aged 35 to 60 years, distinct differences in structural changes were found with the PsA patients presenting more structural damage.

Finally, the study from Larkin et al. (Larkin et al., 2016) focused on the importance of physical activity in patients with inflammatory arthritis including RA and PsA and the examination of the psychological factors influencing physical activity in these patients. The aim was to identify the relationship between demographic and psychological variables, including self-efficacy and beliefs about physical activity, and the levels of physical activity and energy expenditure. The results showed that the patient participants reported low levels of physical activity and that their beliefs about physical activity were found to be correlated with self-reported physical activity levels over both the past week and month. This highlights the significance of addressing beliefs about physical activity to design effective interventions for improving physical activity levels in individuals with inflammatory arthritis.

Accelerometer

Wearable and mobile phone accelerometers provide an unobtrusive, objective, and reproducible way to continuously measure individuals' physical activity (Straczekiewicz et al., 2021), mobility, and gait-related characteristics in daily life and allow investigators to monitor individuals in free-living environments over an extensive period compared to conventional laboratory studies. They can generate frequent and accurate data compared to traditional questionnaire-based PROs that can be subjective and prone to recall bias, which along with health care professionals and PROs, can contribute to monitoring symptoms and disease severity more efficiently.

Only a few studies have attempted to investigate using accelerometer data in monitoring patients with PsA (Hernández-Hernández et al., 2021; McGagh et al., 2023; Walha et al.,

2022). However, actigraphy has been successfully employed in several other diseases, such as RA (Jacquemin et al., 2017), multiple sclerosis (Pratap et al., 2020) and Parkinson's disease (Omberg et al., 2021). Moreover, accelerometer data can be captured in two different ways, actively and passively. In active monitoring, individuals perform prescribed active tests such as gait and ROM assessments (Webster et al., 2022), while in passive monitoring, accelerometer data are recorded in free-living conditions and measurements such as activity fragmentation, sedentary behavior, and morning stiffness are extracted (Creagh et al., 2022).

In 2021, Hernández-Hernández et al. compared physical activity in PsA patients and healthy controls. Participants were monitored for five days via an actigraphy device mounted on their hip (Hernández-Hernández et al., 2021). Although physical activity levels proved similar in PsA patients and healthy controls, comparing PA levels in patients between the first and the 6-month follow-up visit revealed a negative correlation between physical activity and disease activity. Similarly, a recent study (McGagh et al., 2023) investigated the relationship between disease activity and PA in PsA patients. Tri-axial accelerometer data were captured daily for 28 days from 19 PsA patients using a wrist-worn actigraph. Analysis suggested that higher levels of moderate-to-vigorous physical activity are associated with decreased disease severity.

In another in-clinic validation study, Webster et al. (Webster et al., 2022) employed smartphone-based assessments using image and motion sensor data to develop digital biomarkers for PsO and PsA. Data were collected from 92 participants, 14 patients with PsO, 69 with PsA, and 9 healthy controls. The assessments included two active tests where accelerometer and gyroscope data were recorded, a 30-second walking test and a digital jar open test. Gait-related and range of motion (ROM) features were extracted, respectively. ROM significantly decreased in patients with PsA compared to PsO patients and healthy controls. However, no significant differences in gait-related features were found between PsA patients and other participants. Moreover, Walha et al. (Walha et al., 2022) assessed gait spatiotemporal parameters and gait variability in individuals with PsA and investigated the association between these gait features and self-reported foot pain. 21 participants with PsA and 21 matched healthy controls performed three in-clinic walk tests, and gait features were recorded by six body-worn IMU units. Statistical analysis indicated that PsA participants had increased gait variability and that foot pain and disability were strongly correlated with spatiotemporal gait features.

Besides PsA, wearable devices have been utilized to assess physical activity in individuals with other arthritic diseases. Several studies (Bell et al., 2022; Keogh et al., 2020; O'Brien et al., 2020; Summers et al., 2019) have examined the relationship between physical activity and inflammatory joint diseases employing body-worn devices and reported that sedentary behaviour is more frequent in arthritis patients than in healthy controls. For instance, Andeu-Perez focused on applying HAR, to assess the ability of the accelerometer to capture different types of activities in patients with RA using random forest approach (Andreu-Perez et al., 2017). Another study by Summers et al. assessed physical activity using body-worn, count-based accelerometer devices (Summers et al., 2019). The study monitored 40 RA patients with low disease activity, 32 RA patients with active arthritis, and 34 healthy controls for 7 days. Researchers reported that although patients with fewer symptoms were more active than those in the other patient group, patients from both groups have lower moderate-to-vigorous physical activity compared to healthy controls. Tada et al., also examined associations between disease activity in patients with RA and physical activity measured using a wearable triaxial accelerometer (Tada et al., 2022). Outcomes showed an association between increased disease activity and decrease in daily physical activities (Tada et al., 2022).

Moreover, accelerometer-based measurements have been used by (Gossec et al., 2019) to predict disease flares in RA and axSpA patients. Physical activity was measured continuously in steps per minute by a wearable activity tracker over three months (Jacquemin et al., 2018), while weekly patient self-reported flares served as ground truth for Naive Bayes classifiers. Similarly, the DIGITAL study (Nowell et al., 2019) investigated the association between passively collected data from a wearable over six months -physical activity, heart rate, and sleep metrics- and weekly PROs from RA patients regarding pain, fatigue, mobility, and flares. The data collected from this study were recently analysed (Rao et al., 2023) using standard machine-learning approaches. More specifically, a random forest regression model was trained to predict the weekly PRO scores and a hidden Markov model was used to improve the performance by incorporating temporal dependencies of the data.

Accelerometers were also employed during prescribed tests to quantify joint mobility and gait parameters. Perraudin et al. (Perraudin et al., 2018) assessed pain and stiffness in patients with arthritis using data collected during prescribed active tests. Patients and healthy controls were monitored over four weeks by a wrist-worn accelerometer device and were asked to perform the Five Times Sit to Stand test in the morning. The duration of the tests was then compared with PROs and associated with the pain and stiffness reported by the patients. In another study (Hamy et al., 2020), raw accelerometer and gyroscope data were collected via iPhone sensors, while the participants performed two prescribed active assessments: a wrist joint motion test and a walking test. Motion-related and gait features were extracted and compared with pain and mobility scores collected via questionnaires employing machine learning techniques, such as logistic regression and statistical analysis.

A recent study (Creagh et al., 2022) collected both active and passive accelerometer data and investigated their association with PROs. Accelerometer and heart rate data were recorded continuously from patients' Apple smartwatches over 14 days, while mobility, health status, dexterity, and fatigue were collected from prescribed active assessments using an iPhone app over the same period. Then, the daily physical activity features were extracted using a self-supervised model developed by Yuan et al. (Yuan, 2022) and trained on unlabelled data from the UK-Biobank. Finally, several machine learning classification models, regression models, and regularization techniques for feature selection were employed to distinguish RA patients from healthy controls and estimate RA severity.

3.4.1.2 Fine motor skills

Musculoskeletal manifestations of PsA include peripheral and axial joint inflammation, enthesitis and dactylitis (Myers et al., 2006). These conditions may restrict joint mobility and impair fine motor skills, making it challenging for individuals to perform tasks that require hand and finger dexterity.

A recent study (Liphardt et al., 2020) aimed to compare the impact of psoriatic disease, i.e, PsA and PsO, and RA on various aspects of hand function. The assessment involved vigorimetric grip strength, the Moberg Picking-Up Test for assessing fine-motor skills, and self-reported hand function (Michigan Hand Questionnaire). For this study individuals with RA, PsA, PsO and healthy controls were recruited. The results indicated that age, sex, disease group, and hand dominance influenced hand function. Both PsA and RA had a similar impact on hand function, particularly in women, leading to increased age-related loss of grip strength, fine-motor skills, and self-reported hand function compared to healthy controls. Moreover, individuals with psoriasis also exhibited impaired hand function compared with healthy controls.

Keystroke dynamics

Typing is a daily user-smartphone interaction that involves multiple cognitive and motor processes. A recent systematic review and meta-analysis (Alfalahi et al., 2022) investigated the use of keystroke dynamics as digital biomarkers for detecting subtle motor decline in the early stages of neuropsychiatric disorders. Longitudinal monitoring of typing dynamics can provide valuable data for early diagnosis and personalized treatment since typing pattern changes can signal symptoms' onset before they become clinically apparent, enabling timely interventions. This section focuses on the current state of research on keystroke dynamics in healthcare areas such as Parkinson's disease, cognitive impairment, multiple sclerosis, and mental health.

Early stages of Parkinson's disease (PD) are characterized by subtle motor symptoms such as tremors, bradykinesia, and rigidity. Many researchers (Arroyo-Gallego et al., 2017; Giancardo et al., 2016; Iakovakis et al., 2018; Papadopoulos et al., 2020) attempted to associate fine motor impairment and keystroke dynamics in PD patients. Giancardo et al. (Giancardo et al., 2016) employed an ensemble regression algorithm to discover patterns in the time series of key hold times obtained from early-stage PD patients while using a computer keyboard. The key hold time is defined as the time between pressing and releasing a key. Iakovakis et al. (Iakovakis et al., 2018) proposed a machine-learning approach based on keystroke dynamics for discriminating Parkinson's disease patients from healthy controls. This study employed hold time, flight time, and normalized typing pressure to detect motor symptoms in patients with PD. Typing data were collected through prescribed active typing tests. Moreover, to augment typing dynamics, Papadopoulos et al. (Papadopoulos et al., 2020) investigated the combination of accelerometer and keystroke dynamics collected from the same device. The data were captured passively from the participants' smartphones during their daily activities. Accelerometer data were used to measure symptoms like hand tremors while typing dynamics to assess fine motor impairment.

Besides Parkinson's disease, data captured from smartphone sensors have been used for monitoring mental health and mood disturbance in individuals with mood disorders such as depression and bipolar disorder (Bennett et al., 2022; Cao et al., 2017; Huang et al., 2018; Mastoras et al., 2019; Vesel et al., 2020; Zulueta et al., 2018). Zulueta et al. (Zulueta et al., 2018) reported a statistical relationship between mobile phone keyboard activity and mood disturbance in individuals with bipolar disorders. In this study, participants installed a keyboard on their devices, and keystroke metadata were collected passively over eight weeks. Since behavioural and cognitive changes are the focus of such studies, variables such as average inter-key delay, backspace and autocorrect ratio, and accelerometer displacement were analysed. It was found that participants with depressive symptoms had increased autocorrect rates, while the backspace key usage was reduced during manic states. In another study, Cao et al. (Cao et al., 2017) introduced DeepMood, an end-to-end deep learning architecture based on late fusion, trained to predict depression scores from bipolar patients and healthy controls. Typing dynamics and special characters typed along with smartphone accelerometer data were used in this study. Moreover, depressive tendencies were also associated with keystroke dynamics. Mastoras et al. (Mastoras et al., 2019) proposed a machine-learning pipeline for feature selection and classification of subjects with and without depressive tendencies. Self-reported questionnaires served as ground truth for this study while typing timing information and typing metadata were captured from participants' smartphones in the wild.

Another area where keystroke dynamics have been successfully employed is in mild cognitive impairment (MCI) and Alzheimer's disease (Chen et al., 2019; Ntracha et al., 2020; Vizer & Sears, 2015). In 2015, Vizer et al. (Vizer & Sears, 2015) exploited keystroke and linguistic

features collected via typed text samples from older adults to discriminate between individuals with pre-MCI and matched healthy controls. It was found that keystrokes per minute and pauses while typing are associated with cognitive impairment. In a similar vein, Ntracha et al. (Ntracha et al., 2020) combined keystroke timing features derived from a convolution neural network and linguistic features derived from Natural Language Processing to distinguish MCI subjects from healthy controls. This study also employed unsupervised learning using typing sessions from other research areas. Another study (Chen et al., 2019) introduced a platform for remote monitoring of symptoms related to MCI, which collected multi-modal data from multiple sensors using several consumer-grade smart devices. In this study, participants with MCI symptoms tended to have slower and more variable typing than healthy controls, possibly due to fine motor impairment and difficulties with language.

Furthermore, several recent studies (Chen et al., 2022; Hoeijmakers et al., 2023; K.-H. Lam et al., 2022; Lam et al., 2021; K. H. Lam et al., 2022; Twose et al., 2020) have investigated the association between keystroke dynamics and clinical aspects of Multiple Sclerosis, such as fatigue, MRI disease activity and clinical disability. Statistical analysis of the time-related typing features (Lam et al., 2021) suggested an association between keystroke dynamics and clinical disability outcomes in Multiple Sclerosis. Moreover, Lam et al. explored the responsiveness of typing dynamics to detect changes in disease activity, fatigue, and clinical disability in Multiple Sclerosis (K. H. Lam et al., 2022). Keystroke dynamics were collected over a year from MS patients and healthy controls during typing using the Neurokeys app on their smartphones. General typing characteristics (typing session length, backspaces) and time-related keystroke features (hold time, flight time, press-press latency) were captured and analysed. This study showed that keystroke dynamics can be more sensitive in detecting short-term disease changes compared to commonly used clinical measures.

Keystroke dynamics open up new possibilities in healthcare, from early disease detection to mental health assessment. However, there is a general lack of research regarding keystroke dynamics in PsA or other arthritic diseases. Further research should investigate the association between arthritis and keystroke dynamics since joint pain, stiffness, and reduced ROM may cause changes to PsA patients' fine motor skills and therefore influence typing dynamics. Besides motor impairment, PsA is often related to stress, mood disturbances and fatigue, which could also affect typing behaviour.

3.4.2 Measurement

3.4.2.1 Digital measurement of physical activity

PsA can impact functional mobility (Walha et al., 2022). Spatiotemporal parameters can be captured using accelerometer data. On the other hand, keystroke dynamics can assess fine motor skills and cognition.

Accelerometer

Accelerometer measures the acceleration of motion (Grouios et al., 2022). In most recent studies, as stated before, actigraphy has been employed in two different ways, actively and passively. In active monitoring, individuals perform prescribed tests such as gait (Straczekiewicz et al., 2021) and ROM assessments (Hamy et al., 2020). In contrast, in passive monitoring, accelerometer data are recorded in free-living conditions and measurements such as activity fragmentation, sedentary behaviour, and morning stiffness are extracted (Creagh et al., 2022).

Keystroke dynamics

Keystroke dynamics are key-press-related features (**Figure 13**), such as key hold times, flight times, and typing speed derived from keyboards. These could provide a passive, unobtrusive, and cost-effective measurement for assessing fine motor skills and cognition.

Figure 13 Keystroke dynamics features.

3.4.3 Datasets

3.4.3.1 Accelerometer

Currently, no datasets are available for developing or assessing accelerometer-based metrics and digital biomarkers in PsA. However, there are several other HAR datasets publicly available that can be used for pre-training machine learning models. The majority of the datasets contain accelerometer data from smartphone sensors along with other sensors such as GPS, gyroscope and magnetometer. Other datasets provide data only from smartwatches and some of them include data from both sources.

WISDM (Gary, 2019): In the WISDM dataset, 51 participants were recorded while performing 18 activities of daily living such as walking, jogging, typing etc. Raw accelerometer and gyroscope data along three axes are collected from the smartphone and smartwatch.

UniMiB SHAR (Micucci et al., 2017): A total of 30 individuals took part in the data collection process, which included 4 types of falls and 9 daily activities -running, sitting, going upstairs, going downstairs, walking, jumping, standing up from laying, lying down from standing, and standing up from sitting. Accelerometer data were recorded along 3 axes from a single smartphone placed in participants' front trouser pockets.

UCI-HAR (Reyes-Ortiz, 2012): This dataset provides accelerometer and gyroscope data along three axes captured by smartphone sensors. Seven daily activities such as sitting, lying, walking, standing, walking upstairs, and walking downstairs were carried out by 30 participants.

KU-HAR (A., 2021): Tri-axial accelerometer and gyroscope data from 90 participants were collected. A smartphone is placed in a bag fastened around participants' waists. KU-HAR dataset contains data collected from 18 daily activities performed in a controlled environment.

Extrasensory (Vaizman et al., 2018): This is the only public available dataset where participants were recorded in the wild using their own personal phones. It contains data captured from both smartphones (iPhone/ Android) and smartwatches, such as tri-axial accelerometer, gyroscope, magnetometer, location audio etc., and 51 self-reported labels. The labels were provided by the 60 users of the app while performing daily activities such as cleaning, shopping, walking, driving, watching TV, etc.

Capture-24 (Chan Chang S., 2021): Capture-24 dataset contains tri-axial accelerometer data recorded from wrist-worn activity trackers. A total of 151 individuals participated in a 24-hour study performing free-living activities. Participants were also asked to use a wearable camera, which was used to construct the ground truth labels. The daily activities of the participants were grouped into 6 free-living daily activities: bicycling, mixed, sit/stand, sleep, vehicle, and walking.

3.4.3.2 Keystroke dynamics

No datasets were identified.

3.5 Bowel movements

3.5.1 State-of-art

PsA has been associated with inflammation and alterations in gut microbiota that can disrupt the intestinal barrier, all which impact bowel movements (Muehler et al., 2020; Myers et al., 2019; Peng et al., 2022; Scher et al., 2015; Veale & Fearon, 2018). Moreover, two previous mendelian randomization studies showed a causal relationship between inflammatory bowel disease, and PsO and PsA (Freuer et al., 2022; Sun et al., 2022). In Sun et al. study, a bidirectional dual causal relationship was found between PsO, PsA and Crohn's disease (Sun et al., 2022). On the other hand, Freuer et al., showed a causal effect of Crohn's disease on PsO and PsA, but not vice versa (Freuer et al., 2022). Bowel movements can be "followed" and analysed through different methodologies, namely using an Electrogastroenterography (EGEG) sensor or by simply collecting the sounds produced due to the bowel movements, which propagate on the internal medium reaching the skin surface in an attenuated form (Riezzo et al., 2013).

A brief state of the art about these two methodologies (EGG/EGEG and Bowel Sounds Collection) will be presented on the following subsections, highlighting pre-processing and pre- and post-acquisition procedures that should be applied to the collected signals.

3.5.1.1 EGG/EGEG

The EGG/EGEG signal has an electrical origin, ensuring the progressive contraction of stomach and intestine muscles as the slow wave propagates. EGG/EGEG signal is characterised by two major components: the slow wave (SW) and the spike bursts (SB) (Zena-Giménez et al., 2018), both with very low amplitude (50-500 uV) (Riezzo et al., 2013), being advisable to amplify the signal.

Slow waves (bioelectrical events also called basal electric rhythm - BER) are characterised by an abrupt upstroke followed by a long plateau before reestablishment of the membrane electrical potential to the basal level, being spontaneously generated in the smooth muscle by pacemaker areas (interstitial Cajal cells – myenteric type | ICC-MY) located in the stomach and intestine (Al-Shboul, 2013).

The ICC-MY cells are "an integral part of the gastrointestinal neuromuscular apparatus, transduce inputs from enteric motor neurons, generate intrinsic electrical rhythmicity in phasic smooth muscles, and have a mechanical sensation ability", controlling not only the slow wave generation, but also its frequency (Al-Shboul, 2013; Kosenko & Vavrinchuk, 2013).

Accordingly to the gastrointestinal tract segment the frequency of the slow waves will change, assuming a characteristic range of values between 0.13 and 0.20 Hz in the small intestine (Parsons & Huizinga, 2018) and between 0.05 and 0.13 Hz in the stomach and large intestine (Kosenko & Vavrinchuk, 2013; Stoddard et al., 1981).

Slow wave frequency decreases between duodenum and ileum of small intestine due to a frequency gradient (Parsons & Huizinga, 2018).

Regarding the other EGG/EGEG signal event, in opposition to the omnipresent slow waves, SB structures consist in quick oscillations on the signal that occasionally happen in the plateau stage, causing antrum contraction (Cooke, 1975; Hegar & Vandenplas, 2017).

From a historical perspective, electrogastrography (EGG) technique (that supports EGEG) has its origins on a research article presented by W. C. Alvarez in 1922 (Riezzo et al., 2013), (Alvarez, 1922; Yin & Chen, 2013) but this methodology's viability, to evaluate gastric motility, was only demonstrated in 1975 by Brown et al (Brown et al., 1975; Riezzo et al., 2013), when the basic electrical rhythm of the stomach was found.

During the last decade of the 20th century, some works helped to establish a list of extractable parameters from the EGG signal, namely mean dominant frequency (DF), mean dominant power (DP), power ratio (PR) and instability coefficient (IC) (McCallum, 1994; Riezzo et al., 1992; Riezzo et al., 2013; Smout, 1994).

Since then, EGG/EGEG was refined with some interesting progressions in terms of hardware and accessories, being the projects developed by Zena-Giménez et al. (Zena-Giménez et al., 2018) and M. D. Poscente and M. P. Mintchev and an excellent example, with the proposal of a new type of concentric electrode that ensure the optimization and quality of the acquired EGG signals and the definition of a new protocol involving "...swallowing an ingestible capsule containing miniature electronic oscillator embedded in an expandable, self-disintegrable, biocompatible pseudobesoar..." (Poscente & Mintchev, 2017).

3.5.1.2 Bowel Sounds

Bowel Sounds are a consequence of bowel movements (movement of gas and fluids during peristalsis), establishing an alternative path to study gastric motility and intestinal obstruction, through auscultation, instead of focusing on the electrical activity (collected with EGG/EGEG systems).

However, this basic auscultation process (based on microphones) is, in general, very empiric and subjective (Watson & Knox, 1967).

Some of the primordial works about abdominal auscultation were written at the beginning of the 20th century (Watson & Knox, 1967; Yoshino et al., 1990), as the one presented by Cannon (Cannon, 1905), but relevant technological advances were only achieved in the middle of the century with the first attempts to objectively analyse the produced sounds, through the graphical transcription of the signal by Du Plessis and Farrer and Ingelfinger (Du Plessis, 1954; Farrar & Ingelfinger, 1955).

In terms of processing, the scientific interest has been focused on high-order statistics and multiresolution analysis (Hadjileontiadis & Rekanos, 2003; Hadjileontiadis, 2005a; Hadjileontiadis, 2005b) and deep neural networks (Bilionis et al., 2021).

3.5.2 Measurement

Taking into consideration the non-invasive nature of EGG/EGEG techniques, signal acquisition is ensured by a precise placement of surface electrodes in the skin.

To optimize the signal quality, the skin area where the electrodes will be fixed should be properly prepared, dried and cleaned with ethylic alcohol or with an equivalent product.

Additionally, it is advisable to “abrade the skin until it turns pinkish” before applying a conductive gel in the interface between the electrodes and the skin, something that ensures an adequate impedance between the electrodes and the inexistence of air in the electrode/skin interface, which could greatly contribute to changes in impedance on the measurement system, affecting the signal quality (Smout, 1994; Yin & Chen, 2013).

Both unipolar and bipolar electrode configurations can be applied, producing bipolar approach the best signal to noise ratio, taking into consideration that is more insensible to motion artifacts (Riezzo et al., 2013).

Electrodes placement should follow a standardized configuration, in order to ensure reproducibility of the results.

A commonly used configuration was proposed by Chen et al. (Chen et al., 1999) and used on studies from other authors, namely G.Riezzo et al. (Riezzo et al., 2013), D. Komorowski et al. (Komorowski et al., 2015) and H. P. Simonian et al. (Simonian et al., 2004). This standard EGG electrode configuration only defines the electrode position for the stomach segment of the gastric track, consisting in centring “...a main electrode (electrode 3) located 2 cm above the mid-point between the xiphoid process and the umbilicus. Two more electrodes (electrodes 2 and 1) were located on an upper 45-degree angle, with an additional electrode (electrode 4) located 4 cm to the right of the central electrode. The common reference electrode (CM) was placed at the cross point of two lines, one horizontal-connecting electrode 1 and the other vertical-connecting electrode 3. The ground electrode was placed on the left costal margin...” (Figure 14) (Riezzo et al., 2013).

In order to avoid the contamination of the collected sound signal with motion artifacts, the patient should stay immobile in a supine position and the test must be executed in a sound-proof facility (Yoshino et al., 1990).

There is a lack of standardization, but the microphone/stethoscope should be fixed to the abdomen (Baid, 2009) (for example lower right abdomen (Yoshino et al., 1990)).

3.5.3 Datasets

No datasets were identified.

Figure 14 EGG conventional electrode placement proposed by Chen et al. Images extracted from (Komorowski et al., 2015; Riezzo et al., 2013))

3.6 Environmental factors

3.6.1 Weather

3.6.1.1 State-of-art

In interviews with iPROLEPSIS patients, weather was frequently mentioned as a factor influencing their inflammatory arthritis. Some patients attributed their pain to cold and damp weather, while others mentioned warm temperatures making it worse. Around 75% of people with long-term pain conditions believed weather affected their pain (Reade et al., 2017). A study called "Cloudy with a Chance of Pain" involved over 13,000 UK residents with chronic pain who recorded their pain intensity using a smartphone app. The study found that higher humidity, lower pressure, and stronger winds were associated with increased pain, aligning with the beliefs of many participants (Dixon et al., 2019).

Despite the large longitudinal study, a summary of the literature shows conflicting results. Various studies showed modest to small correlations between weather conditions and pain levels, but these correlations were not consistently in the same direction. A recent review by Beukenhorst aimed to identify reasons for these discrepancies. The review included 43 papers, and the studies differed in analysis methods, weather data preparation, and adjustments for covariates. To gain more clarity, future studies should address three main limitations of previous research: small sample sizes and short study durations, exposure misclassification, and statistical analysis approaches (e.g., multiple comparisons and covariate adjustments) (Beukenhorst et al., 2020).

The weak correlations observed at the population level may be influenced by the sensitivity of subjects experiencing pain in opposite directions. Additionally, differences in the level and type of pain experienced by individuals could contribute to these variations (Horvath et al., 2023).

3.6.1.2 Measurement

The influence of weather on PsA is not extensively studied. Geoepidemiological research on PsA indicates a higher prevalence in colder northern regions compared to tropical areas, suggesting a possible impact of weather conditions on the disease (Chandran & Raychaudhuri, 2010). However, apart from studies focusing on pain and on rheumatoid arthritis, there is limited research available on this topic (**Supplementary information 1**) (Abasolo et al., 2013; Aikman, 1997; Arber et al., 1994; Azzouzi & Ichchou, 2020; Drane et al., 1997; Gorin et al., 1999; Hollander, 1985; Hopkins, 2010; Patberg, 1987; Patberg, 2003; Patberg & Rasker, 2004; Rasker et al., 1986; Redelmeier & Tversky, 1996; Savage et al., 2014; Sibley, 1985; Smedslund & Hagen, 2011; Smedslund et al., 2009).

Except for anecdotal evidence told by patients to doctors during consultation there is no standardised measurement in place to evaluate the impact of weather conditions on PsA.

3.6.1.3 Datasets

No PsA specific datasets.

3.6.2 Air pollution

3.6.2.1 State-of-art

Air pollution is not studied among PsA patients. We therefore resided to the literature in Rheumatoid Arthritis, a neighbouring disease that in phenotype resembles PsA partly, but its underlying mechanism is different.

Numerous studies have explored the association between air pollutants and the development or aggravation of RA (Adami, Rossini, et al., 2021; Adami, Viapiana, et al., 2021; Alex et al., 2020; Chang et al., 2016; Chen et al., 2023; De Roos et al., 2014; Di et al., 2020; Essouma & Noubiap, 2015; Farhat et al., 2011; Gan et al., 2013; Hadnagy et al., 1996; Hart et al., 2013;

Jung et al., 2017; Ott, 1974; Shin et al., 2019; Sigaux et al., 2019; Sun et al., 2016). Evidence from in vitro studies, where cells are exposed to air pollutants in a controlled environment, and in vivo studies, involving animal models, indicate that air pollutants can stimulate immunological processes and promote the production of inflammatory mediators and autoantibodies (Celen et al., 2022; Gałuszka-Bulaga et al., 2022; Gumtorntip et al., 2023; Piovani et al., 2023; Rosenberg, 2022; Zhang et al., 2023). These findings suggest that air pollutants may play a role in the initiation and progression of RA.

Clinical studies suggest a link between air pollution and RA. However, there have been discrepancies in the results of some studies (Celen et al., 2022; Farhat et al., 2011; Zhang et al., 2023). These discrepancies could be attributed to variations in exposure levels and duration of the studies. And likely due to the difficulty establishing air pollution exposure in individuals. To improve our understanding of the mechanisms underlying the association between air pollutants and disease, future studies should employ advanced techniques and identify reliable biomarkers to assess individual susceptibility and disease activity (Celen et al., 2022). Longitudinal studies can help establish causality and determine the long-term effects of air pollution on RA.

Further research has explored the association between air pollution and various autoimmune diseases, such as autoimmune thyroid disorders, multiple sclerosis, and inflammatory bowel diseases (Adami et al., 2022; Celen et al., 2022; Chen et al., 2023; Liu et al., 2021; Zhang et al., 2023; N. Zhao et al., 2023). The evidence suggests that long-term exposure to air pollutants, particularly particulate matter (PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀), may be associated with an increased risk of developing these autoimmune conditions. New research is essential to elucidate the mechanisms involved and develop effective strategies to mitigate the impact of air pollution on these health conditions. Reducing air pollution may not only improve overall public health but also benefit individuals with rheumatic diseases.

3.6.2.2 Measurement

The influence of air pollution on PsA has not been studied. Given the unclarity of the role of air pollutants on PsA, no measures are in place in daily clinical practice.

3.6.2.3 Datasets

No PsA specific datasets.

Datasets on air pollution data for general population are available from the Greece Air pollution², Netherlands Air pollution³, Portugal air pollution⁴ and UK air pollution⁵ databases.

Section highlight

Summary of findings, measurement tools and identified datasets for each trigger/consequence of flare are depicted in Table 3 and **Table 4**. Flare in PsA may be triggered by alterations in mood, stress, sleep, bowel movements, and environmental factors. As a consequence of flare, mood, stress, sleep and bowel movements may be also affected, as well as physical activity and motor skills. Of note, certain symptoms of PsA may also trigger or be triggered by flare. Clinical measurements for the majority of these factors mostly include questionnaires (mood, stress, sleep). Electrography techniques can be also used in the assessment of certain factors such as electrocardiography for heart rate and electrogastroenterography for bowel. Moreover, digital approaches using accelerometer data and keystroke dynamics can be used

² <https://ypen.gov.gr/perivallon/poioitita-tis-atmosfairas/dedomena-metriseon-atmosfairikis-rypansis/>

³ <https://data.rivm.nl/data/luchtmeetnet/>

⁴ <https://www.pordata.pt/en/portugal/gas+emissions-1081>

⁵ https://uk-air.defra.gov.uk/data/data_selector_service?show=auto&submit=Reset&f_limit_was=1

to capture physical activity and fine motor skills. No datasets in patients with PsA have been identified. Other datasets were identified for physical activity and environmental factors.

4 Markers for the development and monitoring of psoriatic arthritis

4.1 Markers based on clinical examinations

4.1.1 Joints inflammation/enthesitis/dactylitis

4.1.1.1 State-of-art

The musculoskeletal manifestations of PsA are diverse and include peripheral and axial joint inflammation, as well as periarticular inflammation manifested by enthesitis and dactylitis (Kerschbaumer et al., 2016; Kishimoto et al., 2021; Myers et al., 2006).

At the joint level, common clinical features in PsA include: distal interphalangeal (DIP) joint, axial joint, sacroiliitis, ankylosis, oligoarticular, polyarticular, asymmetric presentation, pencil in cup formation and new bone formation (McArdle et al., 2018). Indeed, Moll and Wright (Moll & Wright, 1973) originally suggested five subtypes of PsA: (i) distal arthritis, (ii) asymmetric oligoarthritis, (iii) symmetrical polyarthritis, (iv) axial or spondyloarthritis, and (v) arthritis mutilans. The distal subtype affects DIP of both hands and feet. The oligoarthritis is the involvement of less than five active joints and occurs in an asymmetric pattern. More likely, PsA affects all joints of the same digit, namely the ray pattern distribution. Asymmetrical oligoarthritis is the most common joint pattern at disease onset (Floranne C. Wilson et al., 2009). The polyarthritis subtype affects more than four joints, a pattern of which is usually symmetric. Axial PsA involves inflammation in the spine and/or sacroiliac joints, and occurs in 25-70% of patients with PsA (Lopez-Medina & Ziade, 2022; Lubrano et al., 2015). Arthritis mutilans is a severe form of PsA occurring in about 5-16% of patients (Rech et al., 2020; Sudol-Szopinska et al., 2016). This subtype is associated with DIP joint involvement, telescoping digits, pencil in cup deformity, diffuse bone destruction, subluxation, and ankylosis (Haddad & Chandran, 2013).

Enthesitis and dactylitis are also common clinical features in PsA and are observed in 30-50% and 40-50% of patients, respectively (Gladman et al., 2013; Kehl et al., 2016; McArdle et al., 2018). Enthesis is a connective tissue between the tendon, ligament, or joint capsule fibers and the bone. Enthesitis is inflammation of the entheses and mainly involves plantar fascia and Achilles' tendon insertion sites, the greater trochanter tubercle of the femur, the medial femur condyles and epicondyles of the olecranon (McGonagle et al., 2012). Dactylitis is characterized by diffuse inflammation of an entire finger or toe, also called "sausage digit". Specifically, dactylitis is the uniform swelling of the soft tissues between metacarpophalangeal and interphalangeal joints. Dactylitis is often seen in the polyarthritis subtype and only present on the feet in two-thirds of patients (Gladman et al., 2013).

4.1.1.2 Measurement

In clinical setting, part of the clinical examination for PsA includes assessments for joints, enthesitis, and dactylitis (**Figure 15**). Subsequently, composite scores representing disease activity are calculated. Besides, optoacoustic is also a non-invasive promising approach for profiling joint inflammation (see section 5.2 optoacoustic).

Research agenda domains		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stiffness • Independence • Treatment burden • Sleep
Important but optional domains		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Economic Cost • Emotional well-being • Participation • Structural Damage
Mandatory domains	Mandatory in all trials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MSK Disease Activity • Skin Disease Activity • Pain • Physician's global • Physical function • HRQOL • Fatigue • Systemic inflammation

Figure 15 OMERACT Endorsed Core Domain Set for Psoriatic Arthritis⁶. MSK, musculoskeletal.

4.1.1.2.1 Clinical examination

Joints

Joints are assessed by means of swollen (i.e., excess fluid accumulation) and tender joint count to quantify level of synovitis and pain. The assessment of joint is done by applying pressure on the joint (4kg/cm²) and scored for swelling (swollen/not swollen) and tenderness (tender/not tender). The scores are then summed to represent the number of swollen and tender joints out of the total number of joints assessed. Of note, asymmetric arthritis is a remarkable feature of PsA. The commonly used joint counts when assessing joints in PsA include: the 28-joint count, the 76/78-swollen and tender joint counts and the 66/68-swollen and tender joint counts (SJC66/TJC68) (**Figure 16**) (Ogdie et al., 2020). In the iPROLEPSIS PDPID study, the SJC66/TJC68 will be used. This count has been shown to have content and construct validity (Duarte-Garcia et al., 2019).

Enthesitis

Enthesitis refers to the inflammation in the enthesis where a tendon or ligament attach to the bone. The most commonly used when measuring enthesitis in PsA include: the Leeds Enthesitis Index (LEI) and the Spondyloarthritis Research Consortium of Canada index (**Figure 16**) (Ogdie et al., 2020). In the iPROLEPSIS PDPID study, the LEI, which has been developed specifically for PsA, is used as a measurement index for enthesitis. Similar to joint examination, the examination for enthesitis involves application of pressure on the enthesis regions of interest (4kg/m²) and scoring the number regions patient indicates as tender. For LEI, a total of 6 items are scored, thus outcomes are presented on a scale 0-6.

Dactylitis

Dactylitis refers to severe swelling and inflammation of an entire finger or toe (i.e., digit) which is a remarkable feature of PsA. The most commonly used indices when measuring dactylitis in PsA are the Dactylitis Severity Score (DSS) and Leeds Dactylitis Index (LDI) (Ogdie et al., 2020). For the LDI, a dactylometer is used to measure the circumference and tenderness of each digit. Briefly, the examiner marks and measures the affected digit(s) as well as the contralateral digit(s). Tenderness is assessed by palpation and a score ranging from 0-3 is assigned (no tenderness, tender, tender and winces, and tender and withdraws). Thereafter, a sum score is calculated based on the ratio of circumference of affected digit and the contralateral digit, and the tenderness score (Ogdie et al., 2020). For the DSS, a score is given to each digit on a scale of 0-3 (no, mild, moderate, and severe dactylitis), and a final summation score is calculated ranging from 0-60.

⁶ <https://omeract.org/working-groups/psoriatic-arthritis/>

Figure 16 Main joint counts (A) and enthesitis indices (B) used in PsA. Swelling of the hip is not assessed (66 swollen/ 68 tender joints). Adapted from: Ogdie et al., 2020.

Disease activity composite scores

The minimal disease activity score

MDA is defined by OMRACT as “that state of disease activity deemed a useful target of treatment by both the patient and physician, given current treatment possibilities and limitations” (Wells et al., 2005). MDA is established by patient meeting 5 out of 7 of the following criteria: tender joint count ≤ 1 ; swollen joint count ≤ 1 ; Psoriasis Area and Severity Index ≤ 1 or BSA $\leq 3\%$; tender enthesial points ≤ 1 ; patient pain VAS ≤ 15 ; patient global activity VAS ≤ 20 ; HAQ ≤ 0.5 (Coates et al., 2010). Moreover, if all 7 items are met, patient is classified as VLDA. The MDA score will be also used in the iPROLEPSIS PDPID study (T5.2).

Disease Activity Psoriatic Arthritis

Disease Activity Psoriatic Arthritis (DAPSA) is composite index to measure disease activity in PsA. DAPSA is calculated as a summation score of the following five items: tender and swollen joints (TJC68, SJC66), patient global assessment VAS, patient pain VAS and CRP (Schoels et al., 2010) (**Supplementary Table 9**). Clinical DAPSA represents DAPSA score without CRP measurement. Based on the summed DAPSA score, disease activity is classified as remission (DAPSA score ≤ 4), LDA (DAPSA score 4 to 14), LDA, moderate disease activity (DAPSA score ≥ 14 to 28) and high disease activity (DAPSA score >28) (Coates et al., 2010). The DAPSA score will be also used in the iPROLEPSIS PDPID study (T5.2).

Psoriatic Arthritis Disease Activity Score

The Psoriatic Arthritis Disease Activity Score (PASDAS) is another composite measure for disease activity in PsA. The score is calculated using the following eight items: physician global VAS, patient global VAS, SF36 PCS, swollen joint count, tender joint count, LEI, tender dactylitis count, and CRP (**Supplementary Table 9**) (Helliwell et al., 2013). The PASDAS score classifies patient as remission (PASDAS ≤ 1.9), LDA (PASDAS ≤ 3.2), moderate disease activity (PASDAS <5.4), and high disease activity (PASDAS ≥ 5.4) (Coates et al., 2010). The PASDAS score will be also used in the iPROLEPSIS PDPID study (T5.2).

Composite Psoriatic Disease Activity Index

The Composite Psoriatic Disease Activity Index (CPDAI) also measures disease activity using the following nine items: peripheral arthritis (tender joint count, swollen joint count, and HAQ), enthesitis (enthesitis count and HAQ), dactylitis (dactylitis count and HAQ), skin disease (Psoriasis Area Severity Index (PASI) and Dermatology-Life-Quality-Index (DLQI)), spinal disease (BASDAI and Ankylosing Spondylitis Quality of Life (ASQOL)). Within each domain, a score of 0–3 is assigned. A total score representing disease activity is calculated and ranges from 0-15 (Schoels, 2014). Proposed cut-offs for near-remission and LDA are <2 and <3-4, respectively (Ogdie et al., 2020). Other versions of the score are also available (modified CPDAI and CPDAI-JED) (Schoels, 2014)

Disease Activity Score using 28 joints

The Disease Activity Score using 28 joints (DAS28) was originally developed to assess disease activity in patients with RA. The score is based on the four following items: tender joint count, swollen joint count, patient global VAS and erythrocyte sedimentation rate or CRP (**Supplementary Table 9**) (Schoels, 2014). Of note, joint count in DAS28 is low (i.e., 28 joints), thus it does not fully capture all aspects of peripheral arthritis involved in PsA.

4.1.1.2.2 Alternative digital approaches

The digital solutions which aim at assessing the joints, enthesitis, dactylitis mainly refer to imaging applications, i.e., processing radiographic, ultrasound and MRI images to aid diagnosis and monitoring of arthritis, focusing on osteoarthritis and rheumatoid arthritis (Bird et al., 2022; Imtiaz et al., 2022). However, since iPROLEPSIS project develops mobile health applications, the scope of the literature review is to find digital solutions based on photographs acquired from mobile smartphones. The search produced two relevant research works.

The only work which targets PsA is Webster et al. (Webster et al., 2022) in which the Psorcast suite of mobile applications is presented and validated. One of the presented applications is the “Hand image processing” in which hand landmarks in the palm and joints of the fingers are generated from hand images and processed to estimate the thickness of joints. For the hand and joint landmarks generation, the Mediapipe framework was used. The locations of the generated landmarks are shown in **Figure 17**.

To automatically assess joint thickness, they propose a metric called the effective joint thickness measurement. For every finger, the effective width of distal (DIP) and proximal interphalangeal (PIP) are calculated. The calculation involves the width of the joint, PIP or DIP, and the average of PIP to DIP length across all fingers. A segmented finger overlaid with the aforementioned joint measurements is illustrated in **Figure 18**. The effective joint thickness is calculated as:

$$\text{Effective Width of Joint} = \frac{\text{Width of Joint}}{\text{Mean PIP to DIP length across all fingers}}$$

Moreover, Huggle et al. (Huggle et al., 2022) proposes an AI-based approach to detect and monitor joint swelling in patients with rheumatoid arthritis. The approach incorporates the extraction of dorsal finger fold lines of a joint and their processing with a CNN network to classify whether they are swollen or not. The dataset used for the training and validation of the proposed approach was collected within the study in Lausanne University Hospital and it consists of 190 PIP joint images (123 swollen/67 no swollen). The CNN architecture was the ResNet34 for the feature extraction followed by a fully connected layer with 1000 input nodes and 2 output nodes. A simplified pipeline of the approach is shown in **Figure 19**.

Figure 17. The locations of the 21 landmarks generated by the MediaPipe framework⁷.

Figure 18 The effective width of a joint is calculated as the ratio of joint width to average PIP to DIP length. The yellow lines on the image indicate how these joint related measures are calculated given the generated landmarks and the segmentation contour of a finger. Source: (Webster et al., 2022).

Figure 19 Swollen joint detection processing dorsal finger fold images with CNN. Source: (Hugle et al., 2022).

⁷ <https://developers.google.com/mediapipe/solutions>

Although the work focuses on patients with RA, the transfer of the AI approach to PsA cases is straightforward.

Using a sensorized glove, Patanè et al. assessed hand finger mobility in patients with RA, in which patients were instructed to perform finger movements (Patane et al., 2022). From the resulting data, features such as touch duration, inter-tapping interval and movement rate were extracted. Associations were found between finger movements and DAS28 (Patane et al., 2022).

The knee brace by Richardson et al. was used to measure features such as joint acoustic emissions, electrical bioimpedance and kinematics, by letting patients with RA perform flexion and extension exercises with the leg (Richardson et al., 2022). Richardson et al. applied extracted features to predict DAS28 with its machine learning approach (Richardson et al., 2022).

Kiefer et al. used ROM and range of kinematics electronic sensors placed alongside the spine to measure disease activity in patients with AxSpA (Kiefer et al., 2022). Patients performed a choreography, which included various extension, flexion and rotations mostly involving the upper body. From this data, ROM and range of kinematics features were extracted. All novel wearable tasks were performed in a lab setting and machine learning approach was implemented to predict disease status (Kiefer et al., 2022).

4.1.1.3 Datasets

No relevant publicly available datasets were identified.

4.1.2 Nail

4.1.2.1 State-of-art

Nail psoriasis is a common symptom of PsA as up to 80% of the patients with PsA have nail involvement (Sobolewski et al., 2017). Moreover, nail psoriasis is an early sign of PsA (Raposo & Torres, 2015). The strong relationship between nail psoriasis and PsA occurs because the nail is anatomically connected to distal interphalangeal extensor tendon (**Figure 20**), which is significantly affected in PsA.

Figure 20 Nail-enthesal-joint apparatus, the anatomical structure that manifests the nail and distal interphalangeal extensor tendon enthesis relationship. Source: (Raposo & Torres, 2015).

There are various nail conditions associated with psoriasis, the most common ones range from the pitting to subungual hyperkeratosis, which is more common in toenails, and onycholysis, i.e., the detachment of the nail plate from the nail bed (**Supplementary Figure 5**). These nail conditions are also present in other diseases, e.g., eczema and thyroid diseases, so the nail psoriasis diagnosis does not only rely on their occurrence. Nevertheless,

the existence of nail dystrophy is one of the criteria in CASPAR classification (Taylor et al., 2006) proving their importance in PsA early diagnosis.

4.1.2.2 Measurement

The most commonly used nail psoriasis assessment tools are the Nail Psoriasis Severity Index (NAPSI) and the Modified Nail Psoriasis Severity Index (MNAPSI).

4.1.2.2.1 Clinical measurement of nail

Nail Psoriasis Severity Index

In NAPSI, the nail is divided into quadrants, and each quadrant is evaluated by giving 1 point for nail matrix and nail bed psoriasis (Rich & Scher, 2003). The sum of these two numbers is the NAPSI score. In **Supplementary Figure 6**, an example of calculating NAPSI is shown.

Modified Nail Psoriasis Severity Index

mNAPSI is a shorter and more practical scoring tool that shows excellent interrater reliability (Cassell et al., 2007). Specifically, for each nail, 7 groups of features are evaluated: 1) pitting, 2) onycholysis and oil-drop dyschromia, 3) nail plate crumbling, 4) leukonychia, 5) splinter hemorrhages, 6) hyperkeratosis, and 7) red spots in the lunula. Pitting, onycholysis and oil-drop dyschromia, and crumbling (including fragmentation and horizontal ridging of the nail bed) are graded from 0–3 in severity. Leukonychia, splinter hemorrhages, hyperkeratosis, and red spots in the lunula are graded as either present or absent, i.e., 0-1.

The distribution of the classes of both datasets are shown in the **Supplementary Table 10**.

4.1.2.2.2 Digital measurement of nail

The state-of-the-art of technology-based solutions for the detection and quantification of nail psoriasis is limited, but active in recent years. Specifically, in Webster et al. (Webster et al., 2022) a suite of mobile applications for the assessment of psoriasis and PsA, i.e., the Psorcst suite, and its clinical validation are presented. One application of Psorcst suite is the detection and classification of nail psoriasis. This application incorporates a two stage AI approach. The first stage performs nail object detection using a pre-trained Faster R-CNN model which was fine-tuned with a compose dataset that consisted of images from the Hong Kong Polytechnic University Contactless Hand Dorsal Images Database (Kumar & Xu, 2016), nail psoriasis images searched from Pubmed Central database, and healthy nail images searched from Google Image search engine. The second stage performs nail psoriasis binary classification fine-tuning the VGG16 neural network architecture pre-trained with the ImageNet dataset. The dataset used for the fine-tuning consisted of 316 images of controls, 38 images for nail psoriasis collected in clinical sites from recruited participants, and 281 images of nail psoriasis from Pubmed Central database. The evaluation of each stage resulted in a mean average precision of 73.4% for the nail detection stage and an accuracy of 0.76 for the nail classification stage.

Moreover, in Folle et al. (Folle et al., 2023), an AI approach to automatically quantify the modified NAPSI (nail psoriasis severity index) was proposed. For the development and evaluation of the AI a dataset of 1154 nail images was collected from patients with psoriasis, PsA, and RA, and annotated with the respective mNAPSI scores. The AI approach called deepNAPSI was based on the BEiT model (Bao H., 2021) which is a self-supervised vision transformer neural network. The evaluation of the model resulted in an average area-under-receiver-operator-curve of 0.88 and correlation with human annotations of 0.9. The deepNAPSI model is available online in <https://git5.cs.fau.de/folle/hand-ki-model> (accessed in 3/8/2023).

Similarly, in Hsieh et al. (Hsieh et al., 2022), an AI powered imaging system for automatic assessment of NAPS score was presented. The AI approach was based on the Mask R-CNN neural network architecture with ResNet101 backbone network. The dataset used for the development of the neural network consists of 450 images, 300 for training and 150 for evaluation, which were collected both from in clinic using a prototype of the proposed imaging system and from research articles and medical textbooks. The evaluation of the model showed a mean accuracy of 91.5%. Although this result is exceptional, we should be skeptical due to the limited number of images used.

4.1.2.3 Datasets

The Nail Disease Detection Computer Vision Project dataset consists of 3020 nail images of 12 classes. (available in <https://universe.roboflow.com/knm/nail-disease-detection-mx0qy>, license CC BY 4.0)

The Nail Disease Computer Vision Project dataset consists of 3096 nail images of 31 classes. (available in <https://universe.roboflow.com/tugas-akhir-kx2jl/nail-disease-bs9o4>, CC BY 4.0)

4.1.3 Skin

4.1.3.1 State-of-art

PsO is an inflammatory skin disorder that can be triggered by various factors in genetically susceptible individuals, including trauma, infections (e.g., streptococcal infections), and medications (such as β -blockers, IFN α , and lithium) in the skin. It affects around 2% of the population worldwide, with some variabilities: the prevalence is the highest worldwide in Caucasian and Scandinavian people, while the lowest is in people from Southeast Asia (Damiani et al., 2021).

PsO frequently presents with comorbidities, with PsA being a prominent association. Approximately 20-30% of individuals diagnosed with PsO will go on to develop PsA. However, the mechanism for PsO transition to PsA is yet to be discovered. Several theories have been put forward to describe the association between PsO and PsA. Both PsO and PsA are characterized by chronic inflammation, featuring a complex interplay between cells of the innate immune system, such as innate lymphoid cells (ILC), DCs, and mast cells (MCs), and cells of the adaptive immune system, such as T cells (Schon & Erpenbeck, 2018).

In the pathogenesis of psoriatic skin disease, there is a first phase of pathological inflammation, followed by a chronic inflammatory phase perpetuated by feedback loops and amplification signals. In PsO, key mediators including antimicrobial peptides (AMPs) such as cathelicidin antimicrobial peptide (CAMP), are responsible for pathogen defense. CAMP production is typically absent in healthy keratinocytes but becomes upregulated during epithelial damage (Lande et al., 2007). In PsO lesions, the uncontrolled CAMP expression and production, in the setting of keratinocyte damage, triggers the release of self-nucleotides, pathological IFN signalling cascades, and the activation of DCs, which result in uncontrolled inflammation. The expression of AMPs leads to the clinical manifestations of PsO: acanthosis (an increase in the thickness of the stratum spinosum of the epidermis) and the Auspitz sign (punctate bleeding upon the removal of a scale) (Zheng et al., 2007). Also, keratinocytes in psoriatic skin exhibit elevated levels of stem cell factor (SCF) and of alarmins like TSLP and IL33 that can recruit immune cells (such as MCs, DCs and T cells) to the dermis and activate them to release pro-inflammatory cytokines and chemokines, including TNF, IL17, IL22, and CC-chemokine ligand 20 (CCL20), along with pro-angiogenic factors (Balato et al., 2012).

In both PsO and PsA, a significant role is played by the T cells (Greb et al., 2016). Multiple T cell lineages are involved, including Th1, Th2, Th9, Th17, Th22, and regulatory T cells (Treg). Each lineage produces unique cytokines and transcription factors. Th1 is linked to IFN γ and

IL12, TH17 to IL17 and IL23, and TH22 to IL22, while TNF is not specific to a single Th cell profile. The activation of CD8⁺ T cells in both PsO and PsA and their response to therapeutic immunomodulation suggest their significant role. Psoriasis inflammatory environment can also lead to PsA bone remodelling, with IL22 and IL23 promoting bone formation, TNF- α enhancing bone resorption, and IL17A stimulating both bone formation and resorption (Suzuki et al., 2014). By comparing PsA patients' synovial fluid to rheumatoid arthritis synovial fluid, Leijten et al. found in PsA patients increased numbers of IL-17-producing ILCs as well as CD4⁺ and CD8⁺ TH cells (Leijten et al., 2015). Therefore IL23-IL17 axis and TNF are viewed as major contributors to etiopathogenesis of PsO and PsA, as evidenced by the effectiveness of treatments targeting TNF- α , IL23, and IL17 (Boutet et al., 2018). Importantly trauma or biomechanical stress at tendon insertion sites can also trigger the release of IL23 that activates Th17 cells to release cytokines like IL22 and TNF- α , leading to bone remodelling as mentioned above. For example, IL22 and other factors stimulate mesenchymal cells to differentiate into osteoblasts, forming enthesophytes in peripheral entheses and joints (Ocampo, 2019). From nearby entheses or the bloodstream, Th17 cells, osteoclast precursors, and DCs migrate to the joints. In the joints, the osteoclast precursors differentiate into osteoclasts due to the increased expression of NF- κ B (RANK) ligand (RANKL) by synoviocytes in the lining. The high expression of RANKL and differentiation of osteoclasts, combined with the higher levels of TNF- α , and IL17 in the joints, leads to synovitis and bone resorption resulting in PsA (Ocampo, 2019).

As stated above, IL-17 is an important cytokine in the pathogenesis of both PsO and PsA. While Th17 cells have long been known to be the main source of IL17 in PsO and PsA, recent investigations have shed new light on the MCs and neutrophils as major cellular sources of IL17 expression, particularly in PsO lesions. Using *in vivo* models for PsO-like human skin inflammation, Keijsers et al., found substantial evidence that not T cells, but neutrophils and MCs as the main cells contributing to the high levels of IL17 in cutaneous inflammation (Keijsers et al., 2014). MCs indeed express IL-17 mRNA, produce small amounts of IL17A, and express the IL17 receptor A. Additionally, MCs can capture, store, and release exogenous IL17A and trigger the release of IL17 and IFN- γ from Th1 and Th17 cells by modulating DCs maturation and function (Noordenbos et al., 2016).

MCs are tissue-resident immune cells that are primarily located in barrier tissues, such as the skin, respiratory tract, and intestinal mucosa. The skin is highly enriched in MCs, which account for 8% of all resident cells in the dermis. As local tissue sentinels, MCs are often activated by external environmental stimuli or by pathogens and release a variety of mediators, including *de novo* synthesized lipid mediators (such as prostaglandin D2 (PGD2) and the leukotrienes B4 and C4 (LTB4 and LTC4)), cytokines and chemokines (such as TNF- α , IL17, and CXCL2) and granule associated pre-stored mediators (such as histamine, neutral proteases), thus exerting immunomodulatory and vasodilation functions in driving allergic responses (Mukai et al., 2018; Zhou et al., 2022).

MC density and activation are high in T cell-mediated inflammatory diseases like PsA and PsO. MCs express MHC I and II to interact with T cells directly by activating T lymphocytes via the TCR, promoting antigen-specific T cell expansion (**Figure 21**) (Zhou et al., 2022). Activated MCs act synergistically with available IL-1 β to enhance Th17 cell responses and their numbers. This enhancement of Th17 cells was specifically observed for the memory CD4⁺ T cell population and not for the naive CD4⁺ T cell population (Suurmond et al., 2016). Another study found that tissue-resident memory CD8⁺ T cells derived from the skin, are enhanced in the circulation of patients with PsA compared to patients with PsO alone (Leijten et al., 2021). This may indicate a potential contribution of cutaneous tissue imbalances to PsA development. Interestingly Noordenbos et al., found that IL17-expressing MCs may contribute

to the progression of synovial inflammation in PsA since immunostaining of synovium biopsies, demonstrated an increase of c-Kit-positive MCs that are the major IL17 expressing cells (Noordenbos et al., 2016).

Figure 21 Interactions between MCs and other immune cells. Source: (Zhou et al., 2022)

MCs-neuronal interaction in the skin also contributes to the pathogenesis of PsO including the development of pain, neuroinflammation, and pruritus (itching). Itching manifests in about 60-90 % of patients with PsO. The pathogenesis of itch is still unclear. For example, it can be due to the high expression and release of several neuropeptides, such as substance P, from the nerves upon stimuli, as it has been found in plaque PsO (Szepietowski & Reich, 2016).

Although there is a clear association between the severity of PsO and the presence of PsA, it is worth noting that they may not always occur in a temporal sequence, as PsO flares do not consistently precede PsA flares. However, the localization of psoriasis lesions may help to identify risk factors. For instance, a longitudinal study involving 1593 cohorts of PsO patients estimated a 3.89-fold increased risk of PsA in patients with scalp lesions and a 2.35-fold increased risk in those with intergluteal or perianal lesions. The study's authors obtained data on the patient's demographics, clinical symptoms, psoriasis type, location of lesions, nail involvement, findings of skin biopsies, and dermatologist confirmation using a standard, computerized data abstraction form. Additionally, PsO patients with radiographic signs typical of PsA in the hand and wrist, foot, and spine were noted for possible diagnosis of PsA. These criteria included joint pattern, the presence of dactylitis, laboratory data such as the presence of rheumatoid factor, and radiographic abnormalities in the hand and wrist, foot, and spine. This observation led to the hypothesis that an abundance of microbial flora at these sites could trigger an immune reaction contributing to the development of psoriatic arthritis (F. C. Wilson et al., 2009; Floranne C. Wilson et al., 2009). Notably, the association between PsA and scalp PsO was also significant in a retrospective cohort study of 162 PsA patients, with a majority experiencing a severe form of arthritis (Pavlica et al., 2005).

The classical clinical manifestations of PsO are demarcated, erythematous, pruritic plaques covered in silvery scales. They can coalesce and cover large areas of skin. Common locations include the trunk, the extensor surfaces of the limbs, and the scalp, depending on the subtypes of PsO. Indeed, several skin manifestations of PsO have been identified. Almost 90% of PsO cases correspond to psoriasis vulgaris or plaque-type psoriasis (**Supplementary Figure 7**).

Inverse Psoriasis (also called flexural psoriasis) affects intertriginous locations such as groin folds, axillae, and gluteal cleft and is characterized clinically by slightly erosive erythematous plaques and patches (Rendon & Schakel, 2019). Guttate psoriasis has an acute onset of small erythematous plaques. It usually affects children or adolescents after a group-A streptococcal infection of tonsils. About one-third of patients with guttate psoriasis will develop plaque psoriasis in their adult life (Ko et al., 2010). Pustular psoriasis is characterized by multiple and coalescing sterile pustules and can be localized or generalized. Two phenotypes have been described: psoriasis pustulosa palmo-plantaris and acrodermatitis continua of Hallopeau. Both affect the hands and feet; the former is restricted to the palms and soles, and the latter is located at the tips of fingers and toes, and the nail apparatus. Generalized pustular psoriasis presents with an acute and rapidly progressive course characterized by diffuse redness and subcorneal pustules, often accompanied by systemic symptoms like shivers, intense itching, muscle weakness, and joint pain.

Erythrodermic psoriasis is an acute condition in which over 90% of the total body surface is erythematous and inflamed. It can develop in any kind of psoriasis type and requires emergency treatment (Navarini et al., 2017).

4.1.3.2 Measurement

The PASI score is the golden tool used to measure the severity and extent of PsO. The score considers the intensity and area of PsO lesion on the skin. A representative area of PsO is selected for each body region (**Supplementary Figure 8**). The intensity of redness, thickness, and scaling of the PsO is assessed as none (0), mild (1), moderate (2), severe (3), or very severe (4) (**Supplementary Figure 8**). The percentage area affected by PsO is evaluated in the four regions of the body (head, arms, trunk, and legs) as nil (0), 1-9% (score 1), 10-29% (score 2), 30-49% (score 3), 50-69% (score 4), 70-89% (score 5) or 90-100% (score 6).

In recent years, state-of-the-art AI technology has developed several machine learning algorithms for the detection and quantification of PsO. As described by Fink et al., automated computer guided PASI measurements (ACPMs) are an image processing tool that allows for the automatic assessment of PASI of PsO patients (Fink et al., 2019). The ACPMs involve automated total-body imaging and a digital image analysis to distinguish PsO and then give a PASI score. The dataset for the training of this system is available in an unpublished pilot study by the authors of the study above.

Furthermore, Pal et al. built a Deep Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) to assess the severity of PsO plaques using erythema, scaling, and induration (Pal et al., 2016). An image of PsO is sent to the computer, which then predicts how severe the three parameters used in assessing PsO severity will be. The DNN is trained by the perception that this challenge is a novel multi-task learning (MTL) problem made up of three interdependent subtasks in addition to three distinct single-task learning (STL) difficulties. The deep CNN-based MTL technique works well when evaluating the disease parameters alone, but significantly worse when all three parameters are accurately rated at the same time. However, by combining MTL and STL, a slight improvement was made incorrectly scoring all three parameters together. An average accuracy of 27.58% is achieved by following such a combination and when the ± 1 tolerance is allowed this accuracy is increased to 86.28%.

Huang et al. have built an AI-based PsO severity assessment application into a smartphone (Huang et al., 2023). The application called SkinTeller promises an alternative for dermatologists' accurate assessment in the real world and chronic disease self-management in PsO patients. A CNN model was developed and deployed into the app. The model takes N lesion images per body part as input and predicts attributes like erythema redness, induration thickness, desquamation scaling, and area ratio. The model comprises three main blocks: an image-processing block, a Multiview feature enhancement block, and a cross-reverse output block. A deep learning system was trained to estimate the PASI score by using 14,096 images from 2367 patients with PsO. The SkinTeller app is used for PASI scoring over 18 hospitals, and its excellent performance was confirmed by a feedback survey of dermatologist users.

Another study by Thamizhvani et al. has trained a machine learning algorithm called the support vector machine that uses histological images of PsO skin biopsies to identify PsO and detect its rate of growth (TR Thamizhvani, 2022). The system uses SVM segmentation and scaling of histological (2D) processed skin pore images of PsO (**Figure 22**). The Feature Scaling Technique uses color, contrast, and image texture along with a combination of SVM classification features, to diagnose and come up with a treatment solution. This computer-assisted image processing system removes erythematous areas from the PsO image for analysis and determination of growth rate.

Figure 22 Filtering of histological skin images for use in the SVM classification. Source: (TR Thamizhvani, 2022)

4.1.3.3 Datasets

No data set available.

4.2 Markers based on optoacoustic imaging

4.2.1 State-of-art

PsO is an immune-mediated skin disease associated with adverse effects on the quality of life as it manifests with several extracutaneous conditions. In particular, the arthritic manifestation of psoriasis, termed PsA, occurs in up to 30% of psoriasis patients (Ogdie & Weiss, 2015; Villani et al., 2015). Nevertheless, the pathophysiology of psoriasis and its progression into PsA is still not fully elucidated. There is increasing evidence that early diagnosis of PsA reduces the significant disease consequences. The diagnosis of PsA depends on history, physical examination, absence of rheumatoid arthritis (seronegative test for the rheumatoid factor and cyclic citrullinated peptide (CCP) antibodies), and presence of radiographically notable joint destruction (Mease & Goffe, 2005; Merola et al., 2018).

Several imaging modalities have been used in the diagnosis of PsA including conventional radiography, ultrasonography and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI). Radiography remains the most reliable and widely used imaging modality to diagnose arthritic conditions as it has been used to measure the degree of erosion and new bone formation that is unique to PsA and does not occur in other forms of inflammatory arthritis (Siannis et al., 2006). Despite its advantages in detecting progression of PsA, conventional radiography cannot detect the early

inflammatory changes affecting the soft tissues in PsA, which limits its usefulness in predicting early arthritic changes in psoriasis patients (Sudol-Szopinska et al., 2016). On the other hand, MRI and US are adopted as safe and sensitive imaging modalities to assess the inflammatory lesions during disease progression (Marina et al., 2015; McQueen et al., 2006). While ultrasonography provides valuable information on the structural and functional constituents of the tissues of interest, it does not directly measure the molecular consistency or the blood flow changes within the joint tissues. In addition, MRI is associated with high cost and limited access, which compromises its usefulness for the daily clinical measurements and follow-up required for psoriasis or PsA patients.

Optoacoustic is emerging as a promising imaging modality for monitoring the disease progression of psoriasis and PsA (Karlas et al., 2021). As the name implies, optoacoustics has the advantage of uniquely combining high optical resolution (light in) with high depth capabilities of acoustic waves (sound out). In an optoacoustic measurement, the tissue is illuminated with a transient laser of variable wavelengths in the nanosecond range. Different molecules within the tissue absorb the illuminated light at characteristic wavelengths, resulting in rapid thermoelastic expansions and the subsequent propagation of ultrasound waves that get detected by ultrasound detectors (Karlas et al., 2021). Without using labels, optoacoustic techniques can detect key molecules in tissues, including oxygenated hemoglobin, deoxygenated hemoglobin, lipids, water, collagen, and melanin. Literature findings indicate the use of optoacoustic examination in various endocrinologic disorders, whereas few human clinical studies have investigated optoacoustic imaging in arthritic disorders (Jo et al., 2018; Karlas et al., 2021; Rajian et al., 2012; Regensburger et al., 2021). Indeed, the field of optoacoustics has only recently matured to the point where it is possible to efficiently study various human diseases without relying on specialized laboratory facilities (Karlas et al., 2021). Our literature search revealed few studies that have derived biomarkers to monitor disease progression and validate the efficacy of various treatment strategies in psoriasis or PsA patients as we detail next.

4.2.2 Measurement

4.2.2.1 Raster-Scan Optoacoustic Mesoscopy (RSOM)

RSOM is a hand-held optoacoustic technique that provides high-resolution imaging ($< 10 \mu\text{m}$), enabling mesoscopic visualization of human skin microvasculature at a superficial depth of 1 - 2 mm. RSOM has the potential to produce highly detailed images of the skin microvasculature, suggesting its usefulness in developing unique biomarkers for monitoring inflammation in various skin diseases such as psoriasis, atopic dermatitis, and other relevant skin conditions (Aguirre et al., 2017; Li et al., 2022; Nau et al., 2023).

The clinical study by Aguirre et al. was the first to use RSOM at a fixed wavelength of 532 nm in the ultrabroad band range (10 - 180 MHz). RSOM was used to visualize the dermal layer, epidermal layer and the vasculature morphology of 13 psoriasis patients (Aguirre et al., 2017). 3D reconstruction of RSOM signals at low and high spatial-frequency components enabled detailed visualization of healthy and psoriatic skin layers. Key inflammatory biomarkers were extracted to derive an RSOM-based objective severity index that correlates with the gold standard PASI. RSOM features of psoriatic skin include elongated and dilated capillary loops in the epidermal layer, dilated and dense vascular structures in the dermal layer, and increased thickness of the epidermis (Aguirre et al., 2017; Hindelang et al., 2019).

In a recent study by Hindelang et al, ultra-broadband RSOM was used to monitor treatment outcomes in 20 psoriasis patients undergoing conventional treatment or treatment with biologics in combination with concomitant topical corticosteroid (Hindelang et al., 2022). RSOM features describing inflammatory and morphological skin markers include: the mean

capillary loop length (MCLL) and mean plexus width (MPW). Upon treatment, RSOM reconstruction of the epidermis revealed the decrease in the diameters and lengths of the capillary loops, reduction in width of the subepidermal plexus containing the microvessels and reduction in the vasodilation and tortuosity (Hindelang et al., 2022). Indeed, studies with a larger number of subjects are needed to validate the current results and explore additional label-free optoacoustic biomarkers that could better assess psoriasis and its treatment strategies.

4.2.2.2 Multispectral Optoacoustic Tomography (MSOT)

MSOT is a hand-held optoacoustic technique that provides real-time macroscopic imaging of tissues at a depth range of 2 - 4 cm and with a resolution of 200 - 300 μm (Karlak et al., 2021). An early study by Sun et al. was the first to use photoacoustic to assess the finger joints in osteoarthritis patients. The study imaged the distal interphalangeal joints and used the optical absorption coefficients to examine the joint cavity differences between osteoarthritic and healthy joints (Sun et al., 2011). As for inflammatory arthritis, the study by Jo et al. examined the use of optoacoustic techniques at a single wavelength corresponding to the distribution of blood content to assess the presence of hyperemia and hypoxia in the synovium of the metacarpophalangeal joints (Jo et al., 2017). Later, optoacoustic imaging of psoriasis was first reported in the study by Ishida et al. that assessed peripheral vasculature and oxygenation status in a patient who had psoriasis for 20 years and was treated with ixekizumab (Ishida et al., 2018). Optoacoustic measurement performed prior to treatment with ixekizumab revealed a thickened and severely tortured vasculature in the psoriasis patient, who presented with swollen digits and painful interphalangeal joints. The patient's post-treatment optoacoustic imaging showed improvement in venous oxygen levels, suggesting recovery of oxygen consumption at the peripheral level (Ishida et al., 2018). In another study, optoacoustic imaging was used in combination with confocal laser scanning microscopy to perform a follow-up of 11 psoriasis patients compared with 6 healthy subjects. The study showed no change in mean vessel diameter and vasculature per unit volume between the healthy subjects and the lesioned and non-lesioned skin areas of the psoriasis patients (Ossadnik et al., 2018).

Optoacoustics has been used in a few studies to derive biomarkers describing inflammation in the joints of PsA patients. Using MSOT, the study by Hallasch et al. measured the optoacoustic signal intensity of the distal (DIP) or proximal interphalangeal (PIP) hand joint of PsA patients. Using finite wavelengths (700, 730, 760, 780 800 and 875 nm) which correspond to blood content levels, the study demonstrated the significant increase in oxygenated and deoxygenated hemoglobin (i.e., higher blood content) in 22 PsA patients compared with 19 healthy individuals at their finger joints (Hallasch et al., 2021).

Recently, the study by Tascilar et al. used MSOT to noninvasively assess metabolic differences, including blood, oxygen, lipid, and collagen levels, in 34 PsA patients, 17 rheumatoid arthritis patients, and 36 healthy individuals (Tascilar et al., 2023). MSOT and US scans were performed for healthy and inflamed joints or enthesal sites clinically characterized by tenderness or swelling. MSOT analysis showed increases in total hemoglobin, oxygen saturation, and collagen content in inflamed entheses which were linked with high enthesal calcifications and enthesal thickening. In contrast, in inflamed synovial joints, i.e., synovitis, MSOT analysis showed an increase in total hemoglobin content but decreases in oxygen saturation and collagen content, which may indicate an increase in local blood flow and synovial vascularization and an increase in cellular oxygen demand in the inflamed synovial joints (Tascilar et al., 2023). The main findings of the study above indicate the promise of optoacoustic in differentiating the molecular contents of arthritis and enthesitis. Another study examined the use of a combined optoacoustic-ultrasonography system in SpA patients to assess the presence of enthesitis at the Achilles tendon insertion position. Optoacoustic

images were acquired at 850 nm, which corresponds to blood content, and the presence of inflammation and hyperemia of the entheses in 10 SpA patients was confirmed compared with 10 healthy subjects (Jo et al., 2020). As for the measurement of synovitis, the study by van den Berg et al. evaluated the potential of a portable optoacoustic system to monitor synovitis in the proximal interphalangeal joints of 10 patients. The joint space of inflamed joints showed a quantitatively higher amount of optoacoustic signals compared to noninflamed joints or joints of healthy subjects (van den Berg et al., 2017).

The above findings motivate further research to identify clinical multiscale optoacoustic features that allow efficient monitoring of psoriasis and its development into psoriatic arthritis. Optoacoustics holds a promising role in high-resolution and high-contrast assessment of structural and functional features of the skin and joints, which can be used for early diagnosis and monitoring of various treatment strategies in psoriasis and psoriatic arthritis.

4.2.3 Datasets

No relevant datasets on optoacoustic were identified.

4.3 Laboratory markers

4.3.1 DNA

4.3.1.1 State-of-art

A remarkable feature of PsA is that patients with family history of PsA are more susceptible to develop disease (Ogdie & Gelfand, 2010). Epidemiological studies provide convincing evidence on the genetic predisposition for the development of PsA (Mulder et al., 2021; O’Rielly & Rahman, 2021). Given that, a number of susceptibility genes have been identified of which the major histocompatibility complex (MHC) region has shown strong contribution (Eastmond, 1994; Liu et al., 2008). These genes were mostly immune- and inflammation-related genes (e.g., HLA-B*27, IL12B gene), as these are central mechanisms in disease pathology (Mulder et al., 2021). Besides disease risk, genetic factors can also contribute to inter-patient differences in disease manifestations (e.g., disease activity and pain perception) as well as in treatment effectiveness (Iwaszko et al., 2021; Queiro et al., 2002). Therefore, identifying these genetic contributions would aid in selecting more personalized treatments and perhaps leading to better quality of life of these patients.

Genetic predisposition for the development of PsA

The majority of genetic studies in the field of PsA focused on genetic predisposition for susceptibility to or protection from PsA. Here, we provide examples on genetic associations with PsA obtained from systematic reviews and meta-analyses. A recent systematic review by Mulder et al, examined the genetic markers associated with PsA risk in PsO patients and classified markers according to the level of evidence (Mulder et al., 2021). A moderate level of evidence for positive association was shown for HLA-B*27, haplotypes B*27-C*01, B*27-C*02, B*38-C*12 and B*39:01-C*1, and IL13 (rs1800925), whereas B*57-C*06, HLA-C*06, IL12B rs2082412 showed moderate evidence for negative association (Mulder et al., 2021). Contrarily, HLA-C*06 phenotype was associated with PsA risk in the meta-analysis of Shao et al (Shao et al., 2020). In addition, HLA-C*02, HLA-C*12, TNF (rs361525) and TNF (rs1799724) were significantly associated with PsA susceptibility (Loures et al., 2019; Shao et al., 2020; J. Zhu et al., 2013; K. J. Zhu et al., 2013). On the other hand, HLA-C*04, IL12B (rs3212227), TNF (rs1800629), IL23A (rs2066808), IL23R (rs11209026) and IL17F (rs763780) were shown to have a significant protective effect (Loures et al., 2019; Shao et al., 2020; Villalpando-Vargas et al., 2021; Zhu et al., 2012; K. J. Zhu et al., 2013). (Loures et al., 2019; Shao et al., 2020; J. Zhu et al., 2013; K. J. Zhu et al., 2013) Outcomes on IL12B (rs6887695) polymorphism were contradictory; one meta-analysis showed significant positive

association, whereas the other showed significant negative association to PsA (Loures et al., 2019; K. J. Zhu et al., 2013). Other meta-analyses also analysed associations between KIR 2DL2, KIR 2DS1, KIR 2DS2, KIR 2DS3, REL (rs13017599), MICA-TM A9 with PsA susceptibility and showed significant associations (Ellinghaus et al., 2012; Enciso-Vargas et al., 2021; Song et al., 2014). Besides, Chen et al listed 50 non-HLA susceptible genes for PsA (e.g., IL23A, IL12B, TNIP1) with the majority of these genes being involved in regulating the IL23/Th17, NF- κ B or JAK/STAT pathways (Chen et al., 2020).

In addition to the genetic markers identified in the systematic review of Mulder et al, latest research investigated other genetic markers in relation to PsA. Additionally investigated genetic markers include TRAF3IP2 (rs33980500), TNFAIP3 (rs6920220), STAT 4 (rs7574865), HLA-Cw*0602 (rs10484554) which have shown positive association with PsA (De Benedittis, Latini, Conigliaro, et al., 2022). Other genetic markers that have shown protective effects include IL10 (rs1800872), ERAP1 (rs10050860, rs17482078, rs27525) (De Benedittis, Latini, Conigliaro, et al., 2022; Kepiro et al., 2021).

Genetic studies also investigated genetic predisposition for number of PsA phenotypes. For example, HLA-B*27 is suggested to be a risk factor for psoriatic spondyloarthritis (Queiro et al., 2002) and was increased in patients with psoriatic arthritis mutilans (PAM) compared to PsA patients without PAM (Nikamo et al., 2021). The C-alleles of NLRP1 (rs878329) and NLRP3-Q705K (rs35829419) were significantly associated with axial involvement and destructive form of the disease, respectively (Juneblad et al., 2021). Furthermore, the IL6 (rs1800795, G allele) polymorphism was associated with peripheral form of disease (Cubino et al., 2016).

Genetic markers for disease activity

Little is known on the association between genetic contribution to disease activity in PsA. A study by Benedittis et al showed that the variant allele of TRAF3IP2 polymorphism (rs33980500) was associated with higher number of tender and swollen joints and higher DAPSA (De Benedittis, Latini, Conigliaro, et al., 2022). Another study showed a significant association between C-allele of NLRP3-Q705K (rs35829419) and destructive form of PsA (Juneblad et al., 2021). Also, patients with PsA carrying both alleles HLA-Cw6 and HLA-DRB1*07 had fewer involved or damaged joints (Ho et al., 2007). The IL1 β (rs16944, G allele) polymorphism was associated with DAS>23.2, representing high disease activity (Cubino et al., 2016). Moreover, TNFa (rs80267959) polymorphism was associated with severity of disease (PASI and DAS scores) (Murdaca et al., 2014). Although not directly comparable, TNFa induced genes showed significant associations with disease activity in patients with RA (De Groof et al., 2016). Given the limited literature in this field, future research is warranted.

Genetics of pain perception

Genes can confer to amplification or decrease in pain perception, as well as to the type of pain experienced (Foulkes & Wood, 2008). Of the investigated genes, polymorphisms in the COMT and OPRM1 genes have been extensively analysed with confirmed association with pain perception (James, 2013; Vetterlein et al., 2023). In the field of PsA, no previous research (to the best of author knowledge) investigated genetic associations with pain perception in patients with PsA. Here, we present some general basics on genetic contribution to pain perception with focus on inflammatory pathways.

A number of genes involved in regulating inflammatory response are also suggested to function as pain modulators. For example, cancer patients with the inflammatory gene polymorphism PTGS2 (rs5275) were at lower risk for severe pain, whereas TNF-a (rs1800629) and NF- κ BIA (rs8904) were predictive of severe pain (Reyes-Gibby et al., 2009). In an

exercise-induced shoulder injury model, polymorphisms in the IL1B and TNF/LTA genes were associated with the intensity of pain (George et al., 2014). In addition, various studies showed significant associations between inflammatory markers/pathways and pain perception among patients with arthritis, which suggests that the variants of encoding genes could be involved in this process (Bruno D'Aurea Furquim, 2016; Schaible, 2014). However, this has to be further investigated in future studies. Examples of such markers/pathways include IL23, TNF- α , IL1B, IL6 and the JAK/STAT and NF κ B pathways (Crispino & Ciccina, 2021; Hartung et al., 2015; Lee et al., 2022; Schaible, 2014). Besides, the GCRP peptide has been also suggested to play a role in joint pain perception and inflammation (Takano et al., 2017; Walsh et al., 2015). Moreover, the genes SDIM1, CPE, OTOF, ANKRD20A4 and PTX3 were differentially expressed in synovium of patients with osteoarthritis experiencing low and high pain (Bratus-Neuenschwander et al., 2018).

Pharmacogenomics

Pharmacogenomics refer to the role of genes in individual response to drug therapy (**Figure 23**). In essence, patients with PsA show different response to medication which can be in part explained by their genetic background (Magee et al., 2021). Previous studies identified associations between polymorphisms in genes, TNFAIP3 (rs610604 and rs6920220), TNF- α (rs80267959, -238G>A and -308G>A), TRAF3IP2 (rs33980500), IL10 (rs1800872) and treatment response to TNF- α inhibitors (De Benedittis, Latini, Ciccacci, et al., 2022; De Simone et al., 2015; Magee et al., 2021). Further studies showed that the IL6 (rs1800795) and DHFR (rs1232027) polymorphisms were associated with responsiveness to methotrexate (Chandran et al., 2010; Sokolik et al., 2021). Other genes involved in drug metabolism include CYP2C19, (Ahmed et al., 2016)

Efficacy of certain treatment is determined by the process of metabolism and transport of drug within the body, which can be affected by the genetic variants of the encoding gene (Ahmed et al., 2016). Considering metabolism, Cytochromes P450 (CYP) is an important family of enzyme involved in drug metabolism (Ahmed et al., 2016) (**Figure 23**). For example, the CYP2C9 and CYP2D6 genes encode respectively the hepatic enzymes CYP2C9 and CYP2D6, which are involved in the metabolism of various drugs including pain relief medications (e.g., NSAIDs and opioids) (Ahmed et al., 2016; Theken et al., 2020). Phenotypes of patients can be classified as poor-, intermediate-, normal-, or extensive-metabolisers based on the CYP member genetic variant (Ahmed et al., 2016; Theken et al., 2020). Moreover, polymorphisms in CYP2D6 and CYP3A5 genes were associated with TNF inhibitor etanercept treatment efficacy in patients with ankylosing spondylitis (Chen, 2017).

Polymorphisms in genes responsible for drug transport can also influence treatment efficacy as they control movement of drug (active or inactive form), in and out of cells (Ahmed et al., 2016). Of the drug transporters, the ABC and SLC are important superfamilies involved in drug transport (Nigam, 2015). Several genetic variants encoding for these families have been identified and have shown association with drug efficacy (Ahmed et al., 2016). Examples of such variants in the scope of medications used to treat PsA include ABCB1 C3435T, ABCC1 (rs rs35592, rs2238476, rs28364006), ABCC2 (rs3740066, rs4148396, rs717620), ABCG2 (rs13120400, rs17731538), SLC19A1 (rs12659 and rs3788200) (Cen et al., 2022; Takatori et al., 2006; Warren et al., 2008).

Figure 23 Genetic polymorphisms in CYPs and drug metabolism. Source: (Ahmed et al., 2016)

4.3.1.2 Measurement

DNA can be extracted from various body tissues with the whole blood and saliva representing most feasible sources in humans (Abraham et al., 2012; Gupta, 2019). DNA extraction procedures involve organic, nonorganic and adsorption methods (Chacon-Cortes D, 2014; Gupta, 2019). Following extraction, the PCR technique is used to amplify specific DNA segments (Gupta, 2019). The quality and quantity of DNA can be influenced by the source and method of extraction. Currently, there are two approaches when measuring genes to determine genetic association with disease or non-disease trait: the genome-wide association study (GWAS) and the candidate gene study.

Genome-wide association studies

GWAS has been used in genetic studies of PsA (Liu et al., 2008). This approach involves scanning of the entire genome to identify genomic variants associated with disease or specific trait (Tam et al., 2019). Of interest, GWAS can identify genes of unknown function or relevancy, which with further analysis/experiments aids in revealing novel pathways. This is done mostly by capturing variations in the form of single nucleotide polymorphism (SNP) across the genome. In essence, GWAS often require much larger sample size to achieve sufficient statistical power.

Candidate gene studies

This is a common approach where genetic variants of priori selected candidate gene(s) are tested (Kwon & Goate, 2000). Selection of candidate gene(s) is mostly based on the suggested role of the gene in disease pathogenesis or other pathways of interest (e.g., pain, pharmacogenomics). For example, genes encoding for cytokines are plausible candidate genes for PsA. Following selection of candidate gene(s), identification of existing gene variants (most common are the SNP), as well as selecting the relevant ones should be also performed to test for associations. Candidate gene study has been also used in the field of PsA.

In the IPROLEPSIS PDPID study (T5.2), we will use saliva or blood to extract DNA and we propose to focus on specific genes. Analysis of DNA will be performed according to procedures of the genetic laboratory of the Erasmus MC. Information on analysis methods will be provided in the Task T5.2.

4.3.1.3 Datasets

The approach with iPROLEPSIS DNA data analysis will be focused on pathway analysis of the genetic variations rather than GWAS analysis. For the use of datasets this will mean that we mostly will rely on the literature and SNP databases rather than using raw data from biobanks.

This information is centrally available in: NGDC⁸; (Soomro et al., 2022; Loft et al., 2018; Manuel Sanchez-Maldonado et al., 2020) UCSC Genome⁹; Ensemble Genome Browser¹⁰; NCBI Map Viewer¹¹.

4.3.2 Gut microbiome

4.3.2.1 State-of-art

Autoimmune diseases (ADs) are characterized by an immune system response that targets and attacks the body's own tissues and organs, leading to chronic inflammation and tissue damage. PsA is believed to belong to the ADs (Miyachi et al., 2023). In PsA, the immune system becomes dysregulated and attacks healthy tissues, leading to joint inflammation, pain, and stiffness. The presence of psoriasis is one of key features distinguishing PsA from other forms of arthritis, together with characteristic distribution of inflamed joint in some particular cases and enthesal involvement. While genetic factors contribute to the development of PsA, environmental factors also play a significant role. Among these factors, changes in the composition of the gut microbiota have gained attention in the past decade (Miyachi et al., 2023).

Host-associated microbial communities, collectively known as the microbiota, have a significant impact on human health. The microbiota refers to the diverse array of microorganisms, including bacteria, viruses, fungi, and archaea, that inhabit various body sites such as the gut, skin, mouth, and reproductive organs.

The gut microbiota refers to the diverse community of microorganisms residing in the intestinal tract. It has a symbiotic relationship with the host, contributing to various aspects of human health, including immune system development and regulation (Cani, 2017). Research suggests that alterations in the gut microbiota composition, termed dysbiosis, may influence the development and progression of autoimmune diseases (Clemente et al., 2018; Kamada et al., 2013).

⁸ <https://ngdc.cncb.ac.cn/databasecommons/browse>

⁹ <http://genome.ucsc.edu/>

¹⁰ <http://www.ensembl.org>

¹¹ <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/mapview/>

The understanding of the potential associations between gut microbiota and rheumatic diseases is still evolving and the exact mechanisms and causality are not yet fully understood. It is important to note that the field of gut microbiota research is complex and there are many factors that can influence the composition and function of the gut microbiota, including diet, lifestyle, medications, and genetics. It is challenging to establish clear cause-and-effect relationships between specific microbial populations and rheumatic diseases due to the variability in individual responses and the potential bidirectional relationship between gut microbiota and immune system function. To gain a more comprehensive understanding of the associations between gut microbiota and rheumatic diseases, further research is needed, including large-scale longitudinal studies, clinical trials, and mechanistic investigations (Wang et al., 2022).

4.3.2.2 Measurement

When analyzing microbiome data, researchers often quantify differences between groups at two levels: alpha diversity and beta diversity (Kers & Saccenti, 2022). These metrics provide valuable insights into the structure and composition of microbial communities.

Alpha Diversity

Alpha diversity metrics assess the diversity of microorganisms within a single sample or group. They provide information about the richness (number of different taxonomic groups or species) and evenness (distribution of abundances) of the microbial community within a sample. Commonly used alpha diversity indices include observed number of amplicon sequence variants (ASVs) (Callahan et al., 2017; Chao, 1984; Faith, 2007). Higher alpha diversity indicates a more diverse and balanced microbial community, while lower diversity suggests reduced richness or an uneven distribution of species (Willis, 2019).

Beta Diversity

Beta diversity metrics quantify the differences in microbial community composition between samples or groups. They examine how microbial communities vary in terms of their taxonomic or functional composition across different samples. Beta diversity measures take into account the presence or absence of taxa, as well as their abundances. Various methods can be used to calculate beta diversity, such as Bray-Curtis dissimilarity (J. Roger Bray, 1957), Jaccard index (Jaccard P., 1912), weighted and unweighted UniFrac distances (Lozupone et al., 2007). These metrics allow for the comparison and clustering of samples based on their microbial community composition.

By utilizing both alpha and beta diversity analyses, researchers can gain a comprehensive understanding of microbial communities in different samples or groups. Alpha diversity reveals the richness and evenness within a single sample, while beta diversity provides insights into the similarities or differences between samples. These diversity metrics are valuable tools for studying microbial ecology, assessing the impact of interventions or diseases on the microbiome, and identifying potential associations between microbial composition and health outcomes.

A research of colleague Scher et al in 2015 (Scher et al., 2015) showed that there is a decrease in gut microbiota diversity in patients with PsA as compared to healthy controls. Also, several bacterial species were found in a lower relative abundance in PsA patients when compared to healthy controls, especially taxa *Akkermansia*, *Ruminococcus* and *Pseudobutyrvibrio* were considered the most relevant genera that discriminated PsA microbiota from healthy controls, albeit the number of patients participating in this study were quite low (PsA=16; healthy controls=17).

For the purposes of this study, we will invite around 600 patients with established PsA to participate and to donate at least one sample at baseline and one sample in case of the flare up of the disease. In The Netherlands, the participants will also be invited to donate stool samples at month 6 into the study period and at the end of the study period, at month 12.

The samples will be collected using OM-200 kits (DNAGenotek.com) accompanied by taking diet history according to the SOP's of Erasmus MC Rotterdam The Netherlands, shipped to the Erasmus MC for storage and analyses. The analysis will be performed in batches, using standard protocol for NGS 16s rRNA sequencing Illumina system (Illumina.com) for bacterial identification.

Sequencing data will be processed and analyzed according to the internal standard operating protocols (SOP's) of the Erasmus MC and used for the calculations of alpha and beta diversity. The baseline data will be analyzed according to the geographical distribution, taking into considerations clinical and demographical data and genetic factors. Additional analysis will be performed on the data from paired samples (baseline/ sample at the time of PsA exacerbation).

4.3.2.3 Datasets

There are no datasets available to date with great number of PsA patients being analyzed or longitudinal studies (Mi-PART study with 60 PsA patients followed in a longitudinal manner is currently on the way (Miguens Blanco et al., 2020).

Section highlight

Summary of findings, measurement tools and identified datasets for each marker are depicted in Table 3 and **Table 4**. Genetic factors may contribute to susceptibility to or protection against development of PsA and can play a role in pain perception and response to treatment. Gut microbiome is an environmental factor involved in immuno-inflammatory pathways, thus suggested to play a role in PsA, but requires further investigation. Monitoring of PsA can be through clinical examination for inflamed joints, enthesitis dactylitis, nail and skin, and the calculation of relative indices and composite scores. In skin, MCs are also suggested to play a role in skin inflammation. Imaging-based approaches represent a complementary or alternative approach to clinical assessment. Such approaches include processing of images obtained from smartphones through imaging applications and the optoacoustic imaging modality. Apart from one dataset identified for gut microbiome, no datasets on markers have been identified in patients with PsA. Other datasets were identified for nail.

5 AI-based models for the detection/prediction of disease activity and flare

To advance current disease management, personalized medicine aims to tailor diagnosis and treatment to individual patient characteristics and has the potential to improve outcomes for patients (Tada et al., 2020). To implement personalized medicine solutions, model-driven approaches are employed. Data-driven models (statistical models and Machine learning-based) are constrained by the available data (the amount and heterogeneity) and the fact that usually remain a black-box for the clinicians and healthcare professionals with limited explainability provided (Rai, 2019). Data-driven approaches can serve to find predictive relations even when the underlying mechanisms are poorly understood or are too complex.

The application of digital technologies in healthcare, commonly known as eHealth, has the potential to bridge the gap in psoriasis care (Fagni et al., 2021). Telemedicine allows remote rheumatological consultations, while mobile technologies enhance monitoring by enabling

patients to continuously self-report symptoms and disease-related parameters. Symptom checkers can guide patients to seek medical attention earlier in their disease progression, reducing diagnostic delays. These interventions have the potential to lead to swifter arthritis diagnoses, enhanced monitoring, and improved disease management. Simultaneously, they bolster the capabilities of referral centers.

The most advanced approach, that is directly related to the aim of iProleptis, is the multi-modality data driven analysis of (Xu et al., 2023). The results demonstrate that machine learning and statistical approaches enable accurate early prediction of PsA and its progression. With a large-scale cohort dataset with 104 clinical features of 3961 patients, machine learning models for PsA diagnosis and analysis of PsA progression risk were developed. The clinical features were clustered into four categories, including physical examination results, indices for severity and extent of psoriasis, laboratory tests, and patients' consultation time and corresponding drugs. The independent experiment on the PsA prediction model demonstrated outstanding prediction performance with an Area Under the Curve score of 0.87.

Additionally, we have identified state-of-the-art data-driven models which predict PsO/PsA disease activity, through a diverse set of disease activity indicators (**Table 5**). We focus on models of disease activity, a narrow topic, specifically important for WP3 effort: to develop the unimodal analysis components and to fuse them in a model that predicts PsO/PsA disease activity. The identified models use various data types (health records, laboratory tests, skin images) to quantify PsO/PsA activity based on various indices of disease manifestation. Thus, such approaches are limited compared to iPROLEPSIS planned implementation, in the following ways: i) types of data used to monitor disease activity are limited and ii) amount of data (e.g., samples in the data) are limited. Still, these models can be utilized in the initial stages of WP3 development to accelerate our analysis and model development. Furthermore, we could utilize prediction models for disease activity for medical conditions other than PsO/PsA, using transfer learning approaches (Yu et al., 2023). In the case of Rheumatoid arthritis, machine learning models have been developed on large, high-quality digital datasets to detect disease flares (Orange et al., 2018) and to classify patients' phenotypes (Eng et al., 2020).

Table 3 Summary of state-of-art literature on symptoms, triggers, consequences, and markers for development and monitoring of PsA.

Topic	Measurement	Summary of findings	Dataset(s) identified
Symptoms			
Fatigue	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> □ The Functional Assessment of Chronic Illness Therapy Fatigue (FACIT-F) □ VAS fatigue and NRS fatigue □ Fatigue Severity scale (FSS) □ Multidimensional Assessment of Fatigue (MAF) □ SF-36 vitality scale □ Wearable (e.g., physical activity and HR) □ Smartphone (e.g., keystroke dynamics and gaze) 	<p><i>General</i> Fatigue is a psychophysiological condition of physical and/or mental tiredness that is not relieved by resting. Fatigue is one of the mostly reported PRO. A patient-physician discordance has been reported when assessing fatigue.</p> <p><i>Pathophysiology</i> Inflammatory cytokines are suggested to be involved in pathophysiology of fatigue as they are implicated in tetrahydrobiopterin deficiency, biosynthesis of dopamine,</p>	Yes

Topic	Measurement	Summary of findings	Dataset(s) identified
		<p>norepinephrine and serotonin, and formation of neurotoxic kynurenine metabolites.</p> <p><i>Relation with other PsA manifestations</i></p> <p>Fatigue was associated with PASI, higher swollen and tender joints, disease activity, enthesitis, pain, quality of life, and sleep.</p>	
Pain	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> VAS/Likert scale for pain <input type="checkbox"/> Clinical examination <input type="checkbox"/> Wearable (e.g., physical activity/movement) <input type="checkbox"/> Other signs (heart rate and heart rate variability, EEG, PPG, blood pressure) 	<p><i>General</i></p> <p>Pain is “an unpleasant sensory and emotional experience associated with, or resembling that associated with, actual or potential tissue damage”. Pain is one of the primary symptoms of PsA.</p> <p><i>Pathophysiology</i></p> <p>In case of inflammation or injury, nociceptors become more active and transmit pain signals to brain through spinal cord. Brain structures such as stem, thalamus, hippocampus and hypothalamus play a role in processing pin signals.</p>	Yes
Stiffness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Single question for presence or duration of stiffness (Yes/No; in minutes) <input type="checkbox"/> Multiple questions covering presence, duration and severity (Yes/No; in minutes; VAS, NRS) <input type="checkbox"/> Rheumatoid Arthritis Stiffness questionnaire (RAST) <input type="checkbox"/> Morning stiffness assessment scale (MSAS) <input type="checkbox"/> Wearable (Five Times Sit to Stand) 	<p><i>General</i></p> <p>Stiffness is generally referred to morning stiffness as it mostly occurs after a period of resting position, especially when waking up in the morning. Stiffness has been associated with the risk of developing PsA in PsO patients. Peripheral stiffness is common in patients with PsA.</p> <p><i>Pathophysiology</i></p> <p>Stiffness has been linked to abnormalities in circadian rhythm of HPA axis and cortisol, and to presence of synovial neutrophils and fibrin in synovium.</p> <p><i>Relation with other PsA manifestations</i></p> <p>Stiffness was associated with tenosynovitis and enthesitis index.</p>	Yes
Triggers and consequences			
Mood	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale (HADS) <input type="checkbox"/> Patient Health Questionnaire (PHQ-9) 	<p><i>General</i></p> <p>PsA is associated with increased prevalence for anxiety and depression which impact mood.</p>	No

Topic	Measurement	Summary of findings	Dataset(s) identified
	<input type="checkbox"/> Hamilton Depression Rating Scale (HDRS) <input type="checkbox"/> Zung Self-rating Depression Scale (ZDS) <input type="checkbox"/> Hamilton Anxiety Rating Scale (HAM-A)	<p><i>Relation with other PsA manifestations</i></p> <p>Anxiety and depression as a proxy of mood were associated with pain, disease activity and tender joint count.</p>	
Stress	<input type="checkbox"/> Perceived stress scale <input type="checkbox"/> Cortisol levels <input type="checkbox"/> Wearables (heart rate and heart rate variability) <input type="checkbox"/> Other signs (respiration frequency, skin, pupils, saliva, muscle tone and posture, GI track functions, brain alertness, memory, sleep and emotional aspects)	<p><i>General</i></p> <p>Stress is a state of physical or mental tension in times of crisis, which could be elicited by a disease, that strain human adaptive capacity. Little is known on stress in PsA.</p> <p><i>Pathophysiology</i></p> <p>Stress mechanisms are suggested to involve a crosstalk between autonomous nervous system (norepinephrine), the HPA axis (glucocorticoids) and the immune system (cytokines).</p> <p><i>Relation with other PsA manifestations</i></p> <p>Stress has not been previously assessed in PsA.</p>	No
Sleep	<input type="checkbox"/> Polysomnography <input type="checkbox"/> Wrist actigraphy <input type="checkbox"/> Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (PSQI) <input type="checkbox"/> Jenkins Sleep Scale (JSS) <input type="checkbox"/> Sleep diaries	<p><i>General</i></p> <p>Poor sleep quality is prevalent in patients with PsA.</p> <p><i>Pathophysiology</i></p> <p>A cross talk exists between sleep deprivation and inflammation. Mechanisms involve alterations in leukocytes, pro-inflammatory markers and immune cell markers.</p> <p><i>Relation with other PsA manifestations</i></p> <p>Anxiety, pain, ESR, emotional recovery, depression, fatigue, physical function, and tender or swollen joint count can be predictors of sleep problems.</p>	Yes
Physical activity and fine motor skills	<input type="checkbox"/> Accelerometer (physical activity) <input type="checkbox"/> Keystroke dynamics (motor skills and cognition)	<p><i>General</i></p> <p>PsA can impact functional mobility and fine motor skills.</p> <p><i>Relation with PsA</i></p> <p>Accelerometer can capture spatiotemporal parameters. Keystroke dynamics can assess fine motor skills and cognition.</p>	Yes

Topic	Measurement	Summary of findings	Dataset(s) identified
Bowel movements	<input type="checkbox"/> EEG/ EEGG <input type="checkbox"/> Bowel sounds	<p><i>General</i> Bowel movements can be monitored non-invasively via recording gastrointestinal muscle electrical activity and bowel sounds.</p> <p><i>Relation with PsO and PsA</i> A causal relationship exists between inflammatory bowel disease with PsO and PsA.</p>	No
Environmental factors	No current measures in place	<p><i>General</i> Weather has been reported as a factor influencing arthritis, mainly pain. Higher prevalence of PsO and PsA in colder northern regions as compared to tropical areas. Air pollution has not been studied previously in PsA.</p> <p><i>Pathophysiology</i> Air pollutants can stimulate immunological process, induce production of inflammatory mediators and autoantibodies.</p>	Yes
Markers for disease development and monitoring			
Inflamed joints Enthesitis Dactylitis	<p><i>Joints</i></p> <input type="checkbox"/> 28-joint count <input type="checkbox"/> 76/78-swollen and tender joint counts <input type="checkbox"/> 66/68-swollen and tender joint counts <p><i>Dactylitis</i></p> <input type="checkbox"/> Dactylitis Severity Score (DSS) <input type="checkbox"/> Leeds Dactylitis Index (LDI) <p><i>Enthesitis</i></p> <input type="checkbox"/> Leeds Enthesitis Index (LEI) <input type="checkbox"/> Spondyloarthritis Research Consortium of Canada index <p><i>Disease activity</i></p> <input type="checkbox"/> The minimal disease activity (MDA) score <input type="checkbox"/> Disease Activity Psoriatic Arthritis (DAPSA) <input type="checkbox"/> Psoriatic Arthritis Disease Activity Score (PASDAS) <input type="checkbox"/> Composite Psoriatic Disease Activity Index (CPDAI)	<p><i>General</i> Musculoskeletal manifestations of PsA include peripheral and axial joint inflammation, enthesitis and dactylitis. Peripheral joint inflammation involves distal interphalangeal joints of hands and feet. Axial PsA involves spine and/or sacroiliac joints. Enthesitis is the inflammation of entheses. Dactylitis is inflammation of a digit (finger or toe).</p>	No

Topic	Measurement	Summary of findings	Dataset(s) identified
	<input type="checkbox"/> Disease Activity Score using 28 joints (DAS28) <i>Digital</i> <input type="checkbox"/> Images of body marks (e.g., hand, feet) from smartphone		
Nail	<input type="checkbox"/> Nail Psoriasis Severity Index (NAPSI) <input type="checkbox"/> Modified Nail Psoriasis Severity Index (mNAPSI)	<i>General</i> Nail PsO (mostly pitting, subungual hyperkeratosis and onycholysis) is a common symptom and early sign of PsA. <i>Pathophysiology</i> PsA can affect interphalangeal extensor tendon which is anatomically connected to nail.	Yes
Skin	<input type="checkbox"/> Psoriasis Area Severity Index (PASI) <input type="checkbox"/> AI-based (Images of body parts and histology)	<i>General</i> PsO is an inflammatory skin disorder prominently presented with PsA. Common manifestations are PsO vulvaris and plaque-type PsO. <i>Pathophysiology</i> The inflammatory process of psoriatic skin involves AMPs, mast cells, dendritic cells, interleukins, TNF and T cells.	No
Optoacoustic	<input type="checkbox"/> Raster-Scan Optoacoustic Mesoscopy (RSOM) <input type="checkbox"/> Multispectral Optoacoustic Tomography (MSOT)	<i>General</i> Optoacoustic is an imaging modality which illuminates the tissue using a transient laser of variable wavelengths in the nanosecond range. This technique can detect key molecules in tissues (oxygenated hemoglobin, deoxygenated hemoglobin, lipids, water, collagen, and melanin). <i>Relation with PsO and PsA</i> The use of optoacoustic allowed for extraction of key inflammatory and skin markers of psoriatic skin using RSOM, as well as markers for joint inflammation using MSOT (hemoglobin, oxygen saturation, collagen content and optoacoustic signals).	No
DNA	<input type="checkbox"/> Genome wide association studies <input type="checkbox"/> Candidate gene studies	<i>General</i> Genetic markers were associated with the susceptibility to (e.g., HLA-B*27) or protection against (e.g., HLA-C*06) developing PsA, as well	No

Topic	Measurement	Summary of findings	Dataset(s) identified
		<p>as with number of disease phenotypes.</p> <p><i>Pathophysiology</i> Genetic variants involved in regulation of IL23, TNFa, IL1B, IL6, IL12B, as well as IL23/Th17, NF-κB and JAK-STAT pathways are relevant markers in PsA pathophysiology.</p> <p><i>Relation to other PsA manifestations</i> Genetic variants may also contribute to variations in disease activity, pain perception and response to drug therapy.</p>	
Gut microbiome	<input type="checkbox"/> Alpha diversity metrics <input type="checkbox"/> Beta diversity metrics	<p><i>General</i> Gut dysbiosis, as manifested by imbalance in microorganisms' communities relative to the communities in healthy individuals, can influence the host immune system. PsA was associated with decrease in gut microbiota diversity.</p> <p><i>Pathophysiology</i> The bacterial species <i>axa</i> Akkermansia, Ruminococcus and Pseudobutyrvibrio were found in lower abundance in PsA.</p> <p><i>Relation with other PsA manifestations</i> Association between gut microbiome with other PsA manifestations has not been assessed before.</p>	Yes

Notes. Definition of pain is as according to the International Association for the Study of Pain (Raja et al., 2020). AMP, antimicrobial peptides; EEG, Electrogastrography; EGEG, Electrogastroenterography; ESR, erythrocyte sedimentation rate; HPA, hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal; HR, heart rate; PPG, Photoplethysmogram; PsO, psoriasis; PsA, psoriatic arthritis; TNF, tumour necrosis factor; VAS, visual analogue scale.

Table 4 Summary of retrospective datasets and datasets identified from scientific literature.

Title	Topic	Type	Country	Population	N population	Frequency of data collection	Relation to prospective data	Availability	Status
Existing cohorts of clinical partners									
DEPAR	PROs, clinical examination and treatment response	Clinical	NL	PsA	~1000	Year 1/ Year 2: every 3 months Following year 2: every 12 months	PRO and clinical examination will be investigated in T5.2	Available from clinical partners	1
MONITOR PsA	PROs, clinical examination and treatment response	Clinical	UK	Newly diagnosed PsA	~400	Year 1: every 3 months Following year 1: every 6-12 months	PRO and clinical examination will be investigated in T5.2	Available from clinical partners	1
Reuma.pt	PROs, clinical examination and treatment response	Clinical	Portugal	Rheumatic diseases	<input type="checkbox"/> PsA: 3521 <input type="checkbox"/> Total: >30K	Monthly / yearly	PRO and clinical examination will be investigated in T5.2	Available from clinical partners	1
Literature									
Greece's Air Pollution	Air pollution	Env	Greece	Not indicated	Not indicated	Hourly	Weather and air pollution will be investigated in T5.2	Publicly available ¹²	2

¹² <https://ypen.gov.gr/perivallon/poiotita-tis-atmosfairas/dedomena-metriseon-atmosfairikis-rypansis>

Title	Topic	Type	Country	Population	N population	Frequency of data collection	Relation to prospective data	Availability	Status
Netherlands' Air Pollution	Air pollution	Env	NL	Not indicated	Not indicated	Hourly	Weather and air pollution will be investigated in T5.2	Publicly available ¹³	2
Portugal's Air Pollution	Air pollution	Env	Portugal	Not indicated	Not indicated	Yearly	Weather and air pollution will be investigated in T5.2	Publicly available ¹⁴	2
Observational study: Association of digital measures and self-reported fatigue: a remote observational study in healthy participants and participants with chronic inflammatory rheumatic disease	Fatigue	Digital	US	SLE and SJS, and healthy	<input type="checkbox"/> Patients: 191 <input type="checkbox"/> Healthy: 105	<input type="checkbox"/> Accelerometer: Continuous for one month <input type="checkbox"/> Questions: daily and weekly for one month	Fatigue will be investigated using digital biomarkers in T5.2	Not available publicly ¹⁵	2

¹³ <https://data.rivm.nl/data/luchtmeetnet/>

¹⁴ <https://www.pordata.pt/en/portugal/gas+emissions-1081>

¹⁵ <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fdgth.2023.1099456/full>

Title	Topic	Type	Country	Population	N population	Frequency of data collection	Relation to prospective data	Availability	Status
Observational Study: a Wearable Sensor and Smartphone Application Supporting Unsupervised Exercises to Assess Pain and Stiffness	Stiffness	Digital	Ireland	RA, PsA and OA, and healthy	<input type="checkbox"/> Patients: 30 <input type="checkbox"/> Healthy: 15	<input type="checkbox"/> Accelerometer: Continuous for one month <input type="checkbox"/> Questions: three times per week for one month	Stiffness will be investigated using digital biomarkers in T5.2	Not available publicly ¹⁶	2
WISDM	Human activity recognition	Digital	US	Healthy	51	Performance of 18 activities (3 minutes each)	Human activity recognition will be investigated using digital biomarkers in T5.2	Publicly available ¹⁷	2
UCI-HAR	Human activity recognition	Digital	US	Healthy	30	Performance of six activities of daily living	Human activity recognition will be investigated using digital biomarkers in T5.2	Publicly available ¹⁸	2

¹⁶ <https://karger.com/dib/article/2/3/106/99462/Observational-Study-of-a-Wearable-Sensor-and>

¹⁷ <http://archive.ics.uci.edu/dataset/507/wisdm+smartphone+and+smartwatch+activity+and+biometrics+dataset>

¹⁸ <https://archive.ics.uci.edu/dataset/240/human+activity+recognition+using+smartphones>

Title	Topic	Type	Country	Population	N population	Frequency of data collection	Relation to prospective data	Availability	Status
UniMiB SHAR	Human activity recognition	Digital	Italy	Healthy	30	Performance of nine activities of daily living and eight types of falls.	Human activity recognition will be investigated using digital biomarkers in T5.2	Publicly available ¹⁹	2
KU-HAR	Human activity recognition	Digital	Bangladesh	Healthy	90	Performance of 18 activities of daily living	Human activity recognition will be investigated using digital biomarkers in T5.2	Publicly available ²⁰	2
Extrasensory	Human activity recognition	Digital	US	Healthy	60	>300k minutes of sensor data	Human activity recognition will be investigated using digital biomarkers in T5.2	Publicly available ²¹	2
Capture-24	Human activity recognition	Digital	UK	Healthy	151	24 hours	Human activity recognition will be investigated using digital biomarkers in T5.2	Publicly available ²²	2
Motion and heart rate from a wrist-worn wearable and labeled	Sleep	Digital	US	Healthy	31	One night in a sleep lab	Sleep will be investigated using digital biomarkers in T5.2	Publicly available ²³	2

¹⁹ <https://www.sal.disco.unimib.it/technologies/unimib-shar/>

²⁰ <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/niloy333/kuhar>

²¹ <http://extrasensory.ucsd.edu/>

²² <https://ora.ox.ac.uk/objects/uuid:99d7c092-d865-4a19-b096-cc16440cd001>

²³ <https://physionet.org/content/sleep-accel/1.0.0/>

Title	Topic	Type	Country	Population	N population	Frequency of data collection	Relation to prospective data	Availability	Status
sleep from polysomnography									
Nail Disease Detection Computer Vision Project	Nail images	Digital	-	Nail pathologies (including nail psoriasis symptoms)	Images: 3022	-	Nail images will be investigated using digital biomarkers in T5.2	Publicly available ²⁴	2
Nail Disease Computer Vision Project	Nail images	Digital	-	Nail pathologies (including nail psoriasis symptoms)	Images: 1179	-	Nail images will be investigated using digital biomarkers in T5.2	Publicly available ²⁵	2
Nail Pitting Computer Vision Project	Nail images	Digital	-	Nail pitting	Images: 312	-	Nail images will be investigated using digital biomarkers in T5.2	Publicly available ²⁶	2
DANBIO register	PROs, genetics, clinical examination and treatment response	Clinical	Denmark	Rheumatic diseases	Not indicated	Monthly/ Yearly	PROs, genetics and clinical examination will be investigated in T5.2	Upon request ²⁷	3
The British Society for	PROs, clinical	Clinical	UK	PsA	Not indicated	Monthly/ Yearly	PROs and clinical examination will	Upon request ²⁸	3

²⁴ <https://universe.roboflow.com/knm/nail-disease-detection-mxoqy>

²⁵ <https://universe.roboflow.com/tugas-akhir-kx2jl/nail-disease-jmapt>

²⁶ <https://universe.roboflow.com/mist-r9pt1/nail-pitting-pv4l1>

²⁷ <https://danbio-online.dk/>

²⁸ <https://www.rheumatology.org.uk/improving-care/registers/psoriatic-arthritis>

Title	Topic	Type	Country	Population	N population	Frequency of data collection	Relation to prospective data	Availability	Status
Rheumatology psoriatic arthritis	examination and treatment response						be investigated in T5.2		
US-Based Corrona Registry	PROs, clinical examination and treatment response	Clinical	US	PsA	<4546	Monthly/ Yearly	PROs and clinical examination will be investigated in T5.2	Upon request ²⁹	3
UK biobank	PROs, genetics and clinical examination	Clinical	UK	Rheumatic diseases	PsA: 1836	Varied depending on parameter	PROs, genetics and clinical examination will be investigated in T5.2	Upon request ³⁰	3
Observational study: Longitudinal Analysis of Fatigue in Psoriatic Arthritis	Fatigue and disease activity	Clinical	Canada	PsA	390	6 month/ 12 month	Fatigue and disease activity will be investigated in T5.2	Upon request ³¹	3

Notes. These datasets will be further assessed for relevancy and usability. Status: 1 - relevant to be used; 2 - to be assessed for relevancy and usage; 3 - to be assessed for relevancy and usage in case of missing variables from datasets of clinical partners. Env, environmental; NL, Netherlands; US, United States; OA, osteoarthritis; PsA, psoriatic arthritis; RA, rheumatoid arthritis; SJS, Sjögren's Syndrome; SLE, and Systemic Lupus Erythematosus.

²⁹ <https://www.corevitas.com/>

³⁰ <https://www.ukbiobank.ac.uk/>

³¹ <https://www.jrheum.org/content/37/9/1878>

Table 5 Data-driven decision models for PsO/PsA activity.

Disease activity index	Aim	Methods	Data	Code availability
Predict moderate-to-high activity of PsA (DAPSA>14) ³² (Queiro et al., 2023) Predict Severe PsA (Queiro et al., 2022)	To identify patient- and disease-related characteristics predicting moderate-to-high disease activity in recent-onset PsA.	Logistic regression model, random forest algorithms, XGBoost algorithms.	Observational prospective study (2-year follow-up, regular annual visits) in patients aged ≥18 years. The sample comprised 158 patients.	On request
PsA progression risk (Xu et al., 2023)	To predict PsA and its progression	Machine learning methods (logistic regression, support vector machines, XGBoost, gradient boosting decision trees etc) Cox regression model	3961 patient clinical records	Available ¹
Predict the risk of PsA for a given patient within the next 6 months (Lee et al., 2023)	To develop and validate a prediction model for PsA based on chronological large-scale and multidimensional electronic medical records.	A convolutional neural network was used to develop a prediction model.	Taiwan's National Health Insurance Research Database from January 1, 1999, to December 31, 2013. The authors used 2.5-year diagnostic and medical records (inpatient and outpatient). The analysis included a total of 443 patients with PsA with earlier diagnosis of PsO and 1772 patients with PsO without PsA.	Not available
Classification of different types of psoriasis (Aijaz et al., 2022)	To classify five types of psoriasis namely, plaque, guttate, inverse, pustular, and erythrodermic as well as the prediction of normal skin.	Deep learning algorithms: 1) convolutional neural network (CNN), 2) long short-term memory (LSTM) network	172 images of normal skin from the BFL NTU dataset and 301 images of psoriasis from the Dermnet dataset.	On request

³² <https://github.com/joy50706/PSA-analysis>

Disease activity index	Aim	Methods	Data	Code availability
Diagnose PsO (Zhou et al., 2021)	To derive a predictive model for psoriasis disease based on only routine hospital tests.	Boruta feature selection method, Random Forest Model.	Sample of 466 psoriasis patients and 520 healthy control, with 81 variables from only laboratory routine tests.	Not available

6 Implications for clinical practice

6.1 Recommendation systems

6.1.1 State-of-art

Recommendation systems are information filtering systems that provide suggestions for items that are pertinent to a user. In health applications, recommendation systems have been widely employed to suggest nutritious and balanced diets, as well as useful physical activity advice to users. In this section, we will initially describe literature works on technologies for recommendation systems that provide personalized meal and physical activity plans to users, prior to presenting recommendation guidelines, designed specifically for PsO and psoriatic PsA patients.

Nutrition in general is a fundamental factor of overall health, immune function and quality of life. Humans consume food that provide them with vital nutrients, such as carbohydrates, proteins, fats, vitamins and minerals, necessary by human bodies to function properly (Karacabey, 2012). To improve physical performance, enhance mental health, and prevent the onset or alleviate the effect of chronic diseases, such as obesity, cardiovascular disease and diabetes, it is of paramount importance to adapt and maintain a nutritious and balanced diet. However, finding the optimal diet is challenging as it varies among people due to personal characteristics, such as age, weight, height, physical activity and medical conditions. In a similar fashion, physical activity recommendations pose their own challenges as they highly depend on the overall strength, stamina and fitness level of a user, while such recommendations should also consider the users' medical condition (e.g., PsA patients may suffer from swollen joints that can inhibit the execution of high intensity physical exercises).

In literature, several diet and physical activity recommendation systems have been proposed that fall into three main categories: content-based (CB), collaborative filtering-based (CF) and hybrid techniques (De Croon et al., 2021; Theodoridis, 2019; Tran et al., 2021). Content-based methods employ the preferences, actions, and profile of each user to customize suggestions. Bianchini et al. proposed in the PREFer food recommender system, which was designed to offer healthy personalized diets to users based on their preferences and medical prescriptions using content-based filtering (Bianchini et al., 2017). Agapito et al. proposed the DIETOS system, a specialist food advisor that offers tailored nutritional guidance to both healthy people and people with chronic disease (Agapito et al., 2018). It generates individual health profiles using replies to real-time medical questionnaires and makes meal recommendations. Shandilya et al. proposed a content-based recommender system that gives precedence to users' recent preferences over previous ones (Shandilya, 2022). Their work focused on suggesting meals based on user preferences and dietary advice, ensuring that the daily nutrient needs are satisfied. In contrast to previous systems, this system provides justification for its suggestions and adapts to shifting user needs.

On the other hand, collaborative filtering is a technique that aims to find similarities between user profiles and thus recommend to a user diets and physical activities similar to those of other users with common profile characteristics. Freyne & Berkovsky developed a recommendation system that provides food suggestions tailored to the users by employing the nearest neighbours algorithm and the Pearson correlation of the user-rating matrix (Freyne & Berkovsky, 2010). Harvey et al. used Singular Value Decomposition on the feature matrices of recipe ratings to uncover relationships between recipes and ratings and recommend nutritious meal plans to users (Harvey et al., 2013).

Recently, hybrid recommendation systems have been proposed to combine CB and CF systems, leveraging their advantages and mitigating their drawbacks. Such hybrid systems rely on the notion that developing food recommendation systems that balance user preferences and nutritional needs is the optimal strategy to follow. Although healthy food and 'tasty food' are not mutually exclusive, there is often an optimization trade-off between nutrient intake and user preferences (Trattner & Elswiler, 2018). Toledo et al. in (Yera Toledo et al., 2019) proposed a filtering stage to avoid suggesting inappropriate meals based on the user profile. A complex optimization stage was additionally used to ensure that recommended daily plans were in line to user preferences, while satisfying their nutritional requirements. Similarly, Nagaraj et al. in (Nagaraj & Deepalakshmi, 2022) proposed a model that used electronic health records and diabetes risk modelling to recommend diets and physical activities to patients with diabetes. Then, a decision tree was used to validate the recommendations according to rules from medical specialists. Finally, a holistic approach to hybrid diet and physical activity recommendation systems was proposed in (Stefanidis, 2022). The authors proposed a knowledge-based personalized recommendation system that relied on expert-defined nutritional rules, a large database of expert-validated meals and physical activities and an elaborate ontology (Tsatsou et al., 2021), capable of suggesting suitable meals for a wide variety of users, ranging from athletes to adults with cardiovascular diseases (CVD).

For patients with PsO and PsA, diet and physical activity recommendations belong to the non-pharmaceutical management of the disease. A recent cross-sectional study (S. S. Zhao et al., 2023) investigated the association between psoriatic disease, i.e. PsA and PsO, and lifestyle factors (BMI, smoking, alcohol intake, etc.) and comorbidities (hypertension, diabetes, etc.). Cross-sectional data from the UK Biobank (1836 PsA, 8995 psoriasis, 36 000 healthy controls) were analysed. The analysis suggested that BMI and diabetes are associated with increased risk of PsA and PsO and a connection between psoriatic disease and coronary artery disease was also revealed. Moreover, it has been shown in the literature that diet has a significant impact on such patients as it can reduce symptoms and provide a better quality of life. Ford et al. in (Ford et al., 2018) made a comprehensive literature review about the connection of diet and psoriasis. The authors found out that dietary weight reduction with a hypocaloric diet is a beneficial and an established medical therapy for individuals with psoriasis, who are overweight or obese with BMI more than 25. Moreover, the effectiveness of a gluten-free diet and vitamin D supplements varies among individuals with psoriasis, while increasing the intake of n-3 polyunsaturated fatty acids, monounsaturated fatty acids, fiber, or complex carbohydrates and reducing the intake of total energy, saturated fatty acids, total polyunsaturated fatty acids or simple carbs could provide some reduction on the on inflammation.

As a general rule, patients with psoriasis or psoriatic arthritis could be recommended to follow a Mediterranean diet that includes eating extra virgin olive oil as the primary culinary lipid, at least two servings of vegetables daily, three servings of fruits daily, legumes every third day, fish or seafood every third day, tree nuts every third day, and sofrito sauce (tomatoes, onions, garlic, and olive oil) every second day. According to Barrea et al. in (Barrea et al., 2020), the

very-low-calorie ketogenic diet can benefit individuals with psoriasis by encouraging weight loss, decreasing inflammation, and perhaps even preventing disease flare through the production of ketone bodies. Due to its antioxidant and anti-inflammatory benefits, this diet may be a suitable first-line treatment choice for obese patients with psoriasis. In (Mohamed Haris et al., 2023), the authors conducted a comprehensive analysis and found that patients with psoriasis have a significant frequency of metabolic syndrome and low nutritional status. Simple anthropometric measurements, such as weight and height to compute BMI, waist circumference to forecast abdominal adiposity, metabolic markers, such as fasting blood glucose, triglyceride, low density lipoprotein (LDL) and high density lipoprotein (HDL) cholesterol and blood pressure, were used to conduct the nutritional evaluations. Even though obese people may be at risk for malnutrition, most of the research did not evaluate the patients' nutritional intake. Duchnik et al. in (Duchnik et al., 2023) suggested that a nutritious diet full of anti-inflammatory elements may help lessen the symptoms of psoriasis and enhance quality of life. In a similar fashion, the authors in (Garbicz et al., 2021) emphasized the crucial part that customized dietary treatments play in treating the chronic inflammatory skin condition psoriasis. The adoption of low-energy diets for overweight people, lowering the saturated fat intake, increasing consumption of omega-3 polyunsaturated fatty acids and including antioxidants are highly recommended. Moreover, various eating plans like gluten-free, vegetarian, or Mediterranean diets may be helpful for some psoriasis patients. Importantly, these dietary changes should support medical interventions. Therefore, to improve skin conditions and lower related health risks, the use of individualized dietary methods in the treatment of psoriasis is recommended. From the previous findings, it is deduced that recommending appropriate diets to patients with PsO and PsA is very beneficial for their health, preventing the progression of their disease and alleviating several of its effects.

In a similar fashion with diet, physical activity and targeted exercises are important components of the nonpharmacological therapy in PsA. It has been demonstrated that physical activity has definite positive effects on functional capacity, general well-being, fatigue, and quality of life in patients with PsA and these benefits appear to outweigh the danger of enthesitis brought on by mechanical stress (Kessler et al., 2021). Low impact exercise has been found to enhance cardiovascular function and lessen disease activity in people with axSpA and RA (Vivekanantham et al., 2021). The potential mechanisms underlying the beneficial impacts of exercise are multifactorial but likely incorporate some positive impact on circulating inflammatory levels and reduced joint loads from weight loss (Beavers et al., 2010; Messier et al., 2005). Two clinical studies have examined the impact of exercise regimens on functioning and disease activity in PsA (Roger-Silva et al., 2017; Thomsen et al., 2019). These studies looked at different exercise modalities; from a resistance training program to a high-intensity interval training (HIIT) approach. PsA patients that received a 12-week resistance training program against controls receiving standard care demonstrated a significantly improved functional capacity, as measured by HAQ-S, and reduced disease activity, measured using the Bath Ankylosing Spondylitis Disease Activity Index (BASDAI) (Roger-Silva et al., 2017). On the other hand, no significant difference in disease activity was found between the intervention and control group for the HIIT program, however, patients in the intervention group reported less fatigue at 12 weeks (Thomsen et al., 2019). Limitations of these studies include their relatively small sample sizes and the use of non-specific disease activity measures for quantifying post-intervention effects. The ACR/NPF guidelines have been developed against this backdrop of relatively low-quality evidence for exercise in PsA by conditionally recommending low impact over high impact exercise (Singh et al., 2018).

Despite the benefits of physical activity in PsA, patients tend to avoid regular physical exercises due to pain or fear of pain (Wervers et al., 2019). As a result, it is imperative to develop personalized physical activity recommendation systems that can keep patients

engaged to a physical training program, thus contributing to the patients' well-being and the alleviation of the symptoms of their disease.

6.1.2 Datasets

To the best of our knowledge there are no available datasets that incorporate diet and physical activity recommendations for PsO and PsA patients. However, there is a large dataset, called Protein NAP database, that consists of meal and physical activity plans for healthy users, as well as users with NCDs, such as obesity, cardiovascular diseases (CVD) and Type-2 diabetes (T2D), that can be used for the training of the AI recommendation engine to be developed in the framework of the iPROLEPSIS project.

Protein NAP database is a dataset of expert-validated Nutrition and Physical Activity Plans (NAPs) (Stefanidis, 2022). In the dataset, there are 381 daily meal and physical activity plans that were created by 1250 unique meals and 121 unique exercises. Each plan consists of three distinct meals (breakfast, lunch, and dinner) and three snacks (mid-morning, mid-afternoon, and evening), as well as two exercises (morning, afternoon). The plans have been created and reviewed by nutritionists, physicians and medical experts according to European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) (Authority, 2010) and WHO (WHO, 2019) guidelines. For the creation of the NAPs, 10 different user groups were considered that correspond to health individuals in different age groups (i.e., adolescents, adults, older adults), athletes, as well as adults with deficiencies or medical conditions (i.e., adults with excess weight, obesity, CVD, T2D, iron deficiency and a diet low in fruit and vegetables). The meal plans were designed with crucial dietary elements, including whole grains, in mind for particular user groups, like individuals with CVD and T2D, as well as with an emphasis on diverse iron sources and optimizing vitamin C, which increases the absorption of iron, for individuals with an iron deficiency. In addition to meals and physical activities, the database also contains foods and recipes.

6.2 Serious Games

6.2.1 State-of-art

In the field of healthcare, SGs have emerged as a versatile and powerful tool with various applications, encompassing screening, diagnosis, education, prevention, and rehabilitation (Manera et al., 2017; Wiemeyer & Kliem, 2011). Overall, these innovative SGs have demonstrated remarkable potential in addressing a wide range of health-related challenges. One of the most significant contributions of SGs lies in health education (Sharifzadeh et al., 2020). In addition, by engaging users in interactive and immersive experiences, SGs have proven effective in disseminating crucial health information, promoting healthy behaviours, and enhancing health literacy among individuals across all ages. From understanding medical conditions to adopting preventive measures, SGs can also offer an engaging and effective means of communicating knowledge.

Another area where SGs have made notable advancements is in acute pain management (Smith et al., 2020). For instance, by integrating gamified techniques and virtual reality, SGs have been successful in helping patients cope with pain and discomfort, reducing the need for traditional pain management methods. Such immersive experiences not only distract patients from their pain but also contribute to their overall well-being and recovery.

Moreover, the impact of SGs on cognitive functions should be considered. Recent research has demonstrated their positive effects on various cognitive aspects, including global cognition, memory, executive functions, and processing speed (Abd-Alrazaq, Ahmed, et al., 2022). In this line, SGs have become valuable tools in cognitive rehabilitation, helping

individuals recover from brain injuries or degenerative disorders and enhance their cognitive abilities.

SGs have also proven to be instrumental in addressing mental health disorders, such as depression and anxiety (Kowal et al., 2021). Through targeted interventions, these games can provide therapeutic benefits, helping users cope with stressors, manage symptoms, and improve their mental well-being. In addition, the gamified approach has shown great promise in complementing traditional mental health treatments and reaching individuals who may be hesitant to seek help through conventional means.

Moreover, the potential of SGs extends beyond cognitive and mental health domains, encompassing improvements in functional, motor, and sensory functions (Vieira et al., 2021). For instance, SGs have been adopted in rehabilitation settings to assist patients recovering from injuries, surgeries, or other physical impairments. By offering interactive exercises and personalized challenges, SGs motivate individuals to engage in their recovery journey actively.

Perhaps one of the most exciting aspects of SGs in healthcare is their potential for disease screening and diagnosis. Studies have indicated that SGs can help in identifying conditions such as mild cognitive impairment (Pazzi et al., 2014), developmental dyslexia (Gaggi et al., 2017), and attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder (Serrano-Barroso et al., 2021). By gathering data during gameplay, SGs can provide valuable insights into users' cognitive and behavioral patterns, contributing to early detection and prompt intervention for these conditions. It is important to underline that SGs offer a versatile and tailored approach in their design and development, depending on the therapeutic approach. These formats include a range of interventions (**Table 6**).

Table 6. Game formats and interventions

Format	Intervention
Exercise games	Engaging players in physical activity during gameplay (e.g., (Martin-Niedecken & Mekler, 2018; Petsani et al., 2022; Xu et al., 2020))
Cognitive games	Targeting cognitive abilities such as executive functions, memory, and learning enhancement (e.g., (Bojan et al., 2021; Bonnechère et al., 2020))
Dietary games	Supporting players in gaining nutritional knowledge (e.g., (Blackburne et al., 2016; Chatziavgeri et al., 2023; Kalvourtzis et al., 2022))
Breathing games	Incorporating breathing exercises by using for instance inhale-hold-exhale breathing patterns during gameplay (e.g., (Lukic et al., 2022))
Bio/neurofeedback games	Using sensors to monitor players' physiological state, influencing body functions such as heart rate (e.g., (Dias et al., 2023; Dias et al., 2020; Zafar et al., 2020))

By adopting these diverse intervention approaches, SGs can support various health-related needs and offer innovative solutions to enhance well-being and address specific medical conditions.

Moreover, AI is at the forefront of a transformative revolution in healthcare and medicine by intelligently handling and analysing complex data sets (Rajpurkar et al., 2022). AI models have become increasingly vital in medical research and clinical practice, enabling personalized screening, diagnosis, prognosis, risk modeling, drug discovery, and predicting response to therapy (Abd-Alrazaq, Abuelezz, et al., 2022; Wood & Reiners, 2014). AI-driven SGs, combining video games with AI offer a customizable and immersive experience by adjusting

speed and difficulty based on the player's performance (Frutos-Pascual & Zapirain, 2017). Through AI algorithms, SGs can monitor players in real-time fashion, evaluating behaviours, mood, and personality (Kamal, 2021; Keshtkar et al., 2013). Additionally, AI-driven SGs, utilizing data mining techniques, enhance players' knowledge, skills, and training progress by analyzing the data collected during gameplay (Alonso-Fernández et al., 2019; Skinner & Walmsley, 2019).

A recent scoping review (Abd-Alrazaq, Abuelezz, et al., 2022) has analysed 64 AI-driven SGs. It concluded that these games targeted a range of health conditions, with motor impairment being the most common, and were primarily used for rehabilitation purposes. The results also shown that multiple AI algorithms were employed, with support vector machines being the most used. While the study revealed promising applications of AI-driven SGs, it emphasized the need for larger, more rigorous, and diverse studies to assess their efficacy and effectiveness in different populations with various health conditions. Currently, there is available on the Apple Store, a mobile application, specifically designed for individuals with chronic joint pain and arthritis. More specifically, the *Reactiv*³³ mobile app offers engaging and interactive experiences, customized gaming exercises, and progress tracking to promote healthy movement at home, utilizing the phone's camera to track movements and integrate exercise motions with popular mobile games. Moreover, there are some proposed SG-based rehabilitation approaches targeting specific manifestations of arthritis, as described below.

6.2.1.1 SGs in rheumatoid arthritis

In a work from (Metsis et al., 2013), game-based activities were embedded within a cyberphysical system, namely RPLAY, intended to preserve the functional ROM and cardiovascular health in persons with rheumatoid arthritis, by promoting their physical activity levels and enhancing their physical therapy routines. It was combined with vision-based motion tracking to ensure patient compliance with the prescribed physical therapy routines and activity levels. The gamification factor was adopted to increase user motivation making the physical therapy routines more interesting and engaging for the patients and providing them with real-time feedback of their progress. In this way, how well each activity was performed, especially the estimated ROM exhibited in the activity, was estimated. Such measurements were then summarized, visualized and reported to the therapist who uses this information on correct performance of exercise to prevent possible deleterious effects (e.g., bursitis, joint pain). The ROM improvements overtime were then stored into the database. Moreover, information to the therapists was also provided regarding the patient's overall adherence to the rehabilitation program. This was an initial effort of employing SGs within the rehabilitation programs of rheumatoid arthritis, without extending its applicability in any RCT.

The effect of social support features and gamification on a Web-based intervention for rheumatoid arthritis patients was explored in the work of Allam et al. (Allam et al., 2015). A 5-arm parallel RCT including 157 rheumatoid arthritis patients was conducted and the patients were randomly allocated to 1 of 4 experimental conditions with different types of access to online social support and gamification features and a control group that had no access to the website. It was found that physical activity increased over time for patients having access to social support sections plus gaming and patients who had access to either social support sections or the gaming experience of the website gained more empowerment and patients who were offered a gamified experience used the website more often than the ones without gaming. This study has shown that gamification alone or with social support increased physical activity and empowerment and decreased health care utilization, highlighting the role of SG as a potential positive driver on health and behavioral outcomes.

³³ <https://apps.apple.com/us/app/reactiv-games-for-arthritis/id1535944723>

Zernicke et al. focused on the positive effects of the Wii game console on physical and psychosocial conditions of patients with rheumatoid arthritis (Zernicke et al., 2016). Investigating the feasibility and patients' assessment when using an animated home-based exercise program. 30 Patients with rheumatoid arthritis reaching low disease activity under therapy with a biological disease modifying anti-rheumatic drug (bDMARD), were split to group A: 15 patients started with a conventional home-based physical exercise program, and Group B: 15 patients began with a predefined animated exercise program by using the Wii game console for 12 weeks. Afterwards, patients were crossed over to the other treatment arm for another period of 12 weeks. Multi-methodical assessments were performed by qualitative analysis of the interview-data as well as statistical analysis of functional tests and PROs. The study reported, via the evaluation of patients' interviews, feasibility and usefulness of the chosen animated home-based exercise program. Compared to standard physical home exercises, similar effects were observed indicating that such an animated program might be an alternative supportive option for rheumatoid arthritis patients.

In a similar vein, Ambrosino et al., explored the effectiveness of home videogame-based serious exergame as an additional rehabilitative tool in 40 young patients (18-35 years of age) with rheumatoid arthritis (Ambrosino et al., 2020). Initially, the patients underwent both a 4-week-lasting traditional rehabilitation program and a training by Nintendo® Wii-Fit™ videogame system. At a second stage, subjects were randomly assigned (1:1) to two groups: Group A (experimental group), including subjects who continued Wii-Fit training at home for additional 8 weeks, and Group B (control group), including subjects maintaining their habitual activity during the 8-week follow-up (T2). Measures of disease activity, quality of life, and fatigue were evaluated at each time point. The study reported a significant improvement in most evaluated outcomes in both study groups, showing that home exergaming may be an effective additional rehabilitative tool in rheumatoid arthritis, since it allows to maintain the benefits of traditional multidisciplinary rehabilitation.

In the work of Pouls et al. (B. P. Pouls et al., 2022), the SG-entertainment was combined with medication-related triggers in order to improve medication adherence in patients with rheumatoid arthritis. A SG was developed using the intervention mapping framework guided by a multidisciplinary expert group, which proceeded along 6 steps, namely: (1) exploring the problem by assessing the relationship between medication adherence and implicit attitudes, (2) defining change objectives, (3) selecting evidence-based behavior change techniques that focused on adjusting implicit attitudes, (4) designing the intervention, (5) guaranteeing implementation by focusing on intrinsic motivation, and (6) planning a scientific evaluation. Implicit negative and illness-related attitudes of patients with rheumatoid arthritis were defined as the main target for the intervention, in an effort to capture if, after the intervention, participants had a more positive attitude toward antirheumatic drugs. Attention bias modification, evaluative conditioning, and goal priming were the techniques chosen to implicitly target medication needs. These techniques were redesigned into medication-related triggers and built in the serious puzzle game. 37 Patients with rheumatoid arthritis use the SG at several stages and the intrinsic motivation was led by the self-determination theory and addressed competence, autonomy, and relatedness. This SG was tested in a subsequent (B. P. H. Pouls et al., 2022) via a multicenter RCT. In this, involving individuals with rheumatoid arthritis, the impact of the SG targeting implicit attitudes towards medication on adherence to disease-modifying anti-rheumatic drugs (DMARDs) was evaluated. The study involved adults with rheumatoid arthritis using DMARDs and owning a smartphone/tablet, divided into intervention and control groups. Although the SG was played frequently (median playtime of 9.7 hours), it did not significantly improve adherence to DMARDs or clinical outcomes in patients with RA, suggesting the need for further research to explore alternative strategies to enhance its effectiveness in RA management.

6.2.1.2 SGs in osteoarthritis

In the work of Mete and Sari (Mete & Sari, 2022), the efficacy of exergaming as a rehabilitation tool in patients with knee osteoarthritis was assessed via a related RCT. The study investigated the effects of exergaming to patients given by visual and auditory stimulated assisted joint training device in addition to the conventional physiotherapy program on pain intensity, ROM, functional status, kinesiophobia, proprioceptive acuity, muscle strength, and postural stability in patients with knee osteoarthritis. 60 Patients with knee osteoarthritis aged 40–65 years, who were at stage of two to three according to the Kellegren Lawrence radiological evaluation were included in the study. The patients were randomly divided into two groups as study group (conventional physiotherapy + exergaming) and control group (conventional physiotherapy). Electrotherapy and exercise program were applied to both of the groups along 5 days a week for 6 weeks, but exergaming only applied to study group. ROM, pain intensity, proprioceptive acuity, kinesiophobia, muscle strength, and postural stability of the patients were evaluated at the beginning and end of the treatment. It was found that in the intra-group analyses of all the assessments of the patients, there was a significant difference in the positive direction in both groups, except for the postural stability values. In the intra-group analyses of postural stability, there was a significant increase only in the study group. In comparison between the groups, proprioceptive acuity, ROM, functional status, and postural stability scores were significantly increased in the study group according to the control group; pain and kinesiophobia decreased significantly. The findings suggest that exergaming accompanied with conventional physiotherapy programs could result in more positive improvements on physical and functional status of patients with knee osteoarthritis compared to the conventional physiotherapy program alone.

In a recent study performed by Özlü et al. (Özlü et al., 2023), the effect of a virtual reality-mediated gamified rehabilitation program on pain, disability, function, and balance in knee osteoarthritis was explored via a prospective randomized controlled study. In fact, this study combines disease-specific gamification through virtual reality (VR) glasses on pain, disability, functionality, and balance in knee osteoarthritis. A total of 73 patients were divided into two groups (35 in experimental group and 38 in control group). All patients were evaluated with pain, functionality, disability, and balance before treatment, after treatment (3rd weeks), and 4 weeks after treatment (7th weeks). In the experimental group, plus the conservative treatment, a total of 15 sessions of disease-specific gamification through VR glasses were applied. The findings suggest that in knee osteoarthritis, the disease-specific gamification through VR glasses added to the conservative treatment has a positive effect on pain, functionality, and balance, paving the way for more studies that could reveal the long-term effect of the added gamification factor on structural healing.

6.2.1.3 SGs and psoriatic arthritis

Despite the exhaustive search in various databases (i.e., Scopus, IEEE Xplore, ACM digital library, Google Scholar, PubMed), no SG that targets Psoriatic Arthritis was identified, indicating a visible gap in this field. The most relevant, yet distant from the concept of SG per se, was the work of Klemm et al. (Klemm et al., 2021), where a feasibility study related with the use of a virtual reality-based app to educate health care professionals and medical students about inflammatory arthritis, including psoriatic arthritis, was conducted. In their work, Klem et al. (Klemm et al., 2021) tested new didactic approaches using virtual reality app to demonstrate disease manifestations as well as joint pathologies in a more comprehensive manner compared to the conventional education approaches. The proposed approach, namely Rheumality, uses data from inflammatory arthritis patients, as well as 2D/3D-visualized pathological joints from X-ray and computed tomography-generated images, allowing the user to interact with representative arthritic joint and bone pathologies of patients with inflammatory arthritis. This approach shows the potential of virtual reality to create more

immersive experiences that could be boosted by the gamified factor of a SG, providing increased user engagement towards the achievement of the characterizing goal of the related SG.

In summary, SGs represent a dynamic and multi-faceted approach in the healthcare landscape. Their applications span from (re)education and rehabilitation to address physical and mental health concerns and even assisting in disease screening and diagnosis (Dias et al., 2022). As technology continues to advance, the integration of SGs in healthcare seems to hold the promise of further revolutionizing the way we approach health and wellness. Apparently, the development of the iPROLEPSIS Serious Gaming Suite will fill the current gap and would further expand the rehabilitation possibilities, providing more accessible, engaging, personalized and effective solutions for individuals with PsA.

6.2.2 Datasets

At present, there are no available SGs-related datasets specifically tailored for people with PsA. Despite this limitation, we can consider more general available game-related datasets for game adaptation models, which can open possibilities for the AI-based personalization of the iPROLEPSIS Serious Gaming Suite (AI-PGS).

Under a multitargeting goal, the AI-PSG intends to provide interventional activities to improve mobility/balance, integrating body gestures and coordination of sequences, fitness, diet, mood, and breathing, involving biofeedback and sensorimotor art-based approaches for stress, fatigue and pain management (consisting of ExerGames, DietaryGames, EmoGames, BreathingGames, NoPainGames, and SensorimotorArtGames).

It is worth noting that most of the available datasets are primarily focused on one specific therapeutic approach, such as Exercise games, Dietary games, Breathing games, Emotional games, Cognitive games, among others. Hence, the description of the characteristic SG-related datasets follows the therapeutic approach (characteristic goals) of each game category (where applicable). Although they may not directly address PsA, these datasets can still offer valuable insights and serve as a foundation for the development of tailored interventions in the iPROLEPSIS project via the AI-PGS.

6.2.2.1 Exergames-related databases

Exergames are often used as SGs tools in rehabilitation scenarios. Here is a list of exergames-related datasets:

GAME2AWE Platform (Danousis & Goumopoulos, 2023)

GAME2AWE platform includes datasets for assessing the motor and cognitive condition of seniors based on their in-game performance data. 15 elderly participants provided data and a random forest classifier achieved a classification accuracy ranging from 93.6% for cognitive screening to 95.6% for motor assessment. These results highlight the potential of using exergames within a technology-rich environment as an effective means of capturing the health status of seniors. [AVAILABILITY: from authors upon request]

PGS/iMAT Assessment tests (Mahboobeh et al., 2022)

In the PGS/iMAT dataset, 51 Parkinson's Disease (PD) patients at Stage 1 and 3 interacted with exergames from the Personalized Serious Game Suite (PGS) and intelligent Motor Assessment Tests (iMAT) gamified environments developed in the i-PROGNOSIS H2020 project. Machine learning classifiers, namely K-Nearest Neighbor (KNN), Support Vector Machines (SVM), and random forest, were employed to analyze five feature vector (FV) scenarios and determine the stage of each PD patient. The study adopted a Leave-One-Out

Cross-Validation (LOOCV) method, revealing that both data sources (PGS/iMAT) achieved a high classification accuracy of over 90%. These findings show the effectiveness of PGS/iMAT in accurately reflecting the motor skill status of PD patients. The successful outcomes of the experiment highlight the potential for further enhancing PGS/iMAT with machine learning techniques to infer the stage of PD patients more efficiently. [AVAILABILITY: from FMH/AUTH/CERTH partners as AUTH was the coordinator of i-PROGNOSIS H2020 project and FMH/CERTH were also partners]

Medical Interactive Recovery Assistant (MIRA) Platform (Ismail et al., 2021)

MIRA platform is a new virtual reality application that presents a wide variety of games and movements for various rehabilitation needs. It consists of three parts, namely: adapted movement-based interactive video games, the Kinect, and the leap motion. The Kinect sensor tracks motion and provides different interactions between the patient and the different types of exergames. Leap motion tracks the hand's movement that composed with the flexion gauges placed into the glove. In other words, the exergames in MIRA are created specifically to aid physical rehabilitation therapies and assessments including more than 450 exergames and cognitive games. [AVAILABILITY³⁴]

Effects of exergames in sedentary young adult males dataset (Xu, 2023)

This dataset includes demographic information from 52 participants (age, height, weight, and average sedentary time), physiological (energy expenditure and heart rate) and psychosocial (reaction time, positive affect, and sociability) health variables in single-player and multi-player mode, targeting the effects of exergames on physiological and psychosocial health in sedentary young adult males: single-player vs. multi-player mode. [AVAILABILITY³⁵]

Effectiveness and sustainability of a motor-cognitive stepping exergame dataset (Hauer et al., 2020)

This dataset includes data from 56 older adults (78.3 ± 6.5 years) participated in the randomized controlled trial with a 10-week intervention and 10-week follow-up period. The intervention group (IG: $n = 29$) took part in a once-weekly exercise program including strength and balance exercises supplemented with an additional stepping exergame training. The control group (CG: $n = 29$) only performed the strength and balance exercises. Outcome measures included stepping reaction times (SRTs) and games scores for individual stepping exergame levels and for the overall exergame performance, as measured by an assessment strategy previously validated in older adults. The analysis of the data demonstrates that the additional stepping exergame training effectively and sustainably improves the performance in complex motor-cognitive stepping exergame tasks in older adults, which can be relevant for preventing falls. [AVAILABILITY: from authors upon request]

Exergame Enjoyment Questionnaire (EEQ-G) dataset (Manser et al., 2023)

This dataset includes data for the development and initial validation of the German version of the exergame enjoyment questionnaire (EEQ-G)', consisting of: (1) the original and complete dataset (Data_EEQ-G_Validation_Study_for-publication.xlsx), and (2) a corresponding README file including: (a) general information, (b) data and file overview, (c) sharing and access information, (d) methodological information, and (e) data-specific information. This

³⁴ <https://peerj.com/articles/cs-599/#supplemental-information>

³⁵ <https://data.mendeley.com/datasets/vjz4dbnvp/1>

dataset is useful for the construction of the EEQ for the exergames of iPROLEPSIS AI-PGS. [AVAILABILITY³⁶].

6.2.2.2 Dietary games-related databases

Dietary games are less dominant in the SG domain, use as means to re-educate the users towards healthier nutrition. Some examples are given below:

PROTEIN H2020 project (2019-2023) dietary games³⁷

In PROTEIN project, some dietary games were developed for educational purposes, targeting different age groups, e.g., children at obesity risk, diabetic patients, obese adults. These games could contribute to the design of the dietary games of iPROLEPSIS AI-PGS. [AVAILABILITY: from CERTH as the coordinator of PROTEIN H2020 project]

i-PROGNOSIS H2020 project (2016-2020) dietary games³⁸

In i-PROGNOSIS project, two dietary games were developed for re-educational purposes, targeting Parkinson's Disease patients. These games could also contribute to the design of the dietary games of iPROLEPSIS AI-PGS. [AVAILABILITY: from FMH/AUTH/CERTH partners as AUTH was the coordinator of i-PROGNOSIS H2020 project and FMH/CERTH were also partners]

Cooking activity SG dataset (Vallejo et al., 2017)

The dataset of this study includes data from 18 healthy elderly controls that were asked to execute a cooking activity in a SG and in real life and were assessed using a neuropsychological test battery. Results showed that performance on the virtual cooking task was associated with multiple cognitive measures and that performances in the virtual task were highly representative of what participants did in real life. [AVAILABILITY: from authors upon request]

6.2.2.3 Physiological activity during serious gaming-related databases

There are several datasets that include physiological data acquired during serious gaming with specific characterizing goal. Some examples are given below:

6.2.2.4 Characterizing SG goal: affective state

BIRAFEE2 (Kutt et al., 2022)

The BIRAFEE2 (2nd Study in Bio-Reactions and Faces for Emotion-based Personalization for AI Systems) dataset includes data from a stimulus-appraisal paradigm and an affective gaming session, gathering contextual information from the game environment. The dataset encompasses accelerometer, ECG, and EDA signals, facial expression data of participants, as well as personality and game engagement questionnaires. Collected from 102 participants, the dataset's potential usefulness is highlighted through validation of the contextual data's accuracy and the examination of relationships between personality traits, participants' emotions, and physiological signals. [AVAILABILITY³⁹]

GAMEEMO (Alakus et al., 2020)

The GAMEEMO dataset collects EEG signals from 28 participants using a wearable and portable EEG device called the 14-channel EMOTIV EPOC+. Overall, the main objectives of this work were to provide an emotion dataset based on computer games, a novel method for

³⁶ <https://zenodo.org/record/7373180>

³⁷ <https://protein-h2020.eu/>

³⁸ <https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=com.TeoS.iPGS&hl=el&gl=US>

³⁹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3865859>

collecting brain signals, and to assess the success of the portable EEG device compared to classical EEG devices. More specifically, the participants played four different computer games (boring, calm, horror, and funny) for 5 minutes each, resulting in a total of 20 minutes of EEG data per subject. The participants rated each computer game based on arousal and valence using the Self-Assessment Manikin (SAM) form. The dataset includes both raw and pre-processed EEG data (in .csv and .mat formats), along with each subject's rating score and SAM form. The researchers also employed pattern recognition and signal-processing methods to observe the dataset's performance and classify EEG signals based on arousal-valence emotion dimensions and positive/negative emotions. [AVAILABILITY⁴⁰]

AKTIVES (Coşkun et al., 2023)

The AKTIVES dataset evaluates stress detection and game reaction methods by using physiological signals. The dataset includes data from 25 children with obstetric brachial plexus injury, dyslexia, intellectual disabilities, and typically developed children during game therapy. Physiological signals (i.e., blood volume pulse, electrodermal activity, and skin temperature) were recorded using a wristband, and facial expressions of the children were also captured. The AKTIVES dataset can be valuable for investigating research questions related to multimodal stress detection game reaction using physiological signals. [AVAILABILITY⁴¹]

Affect recognition in high intensity VR exergaming (Barathi et al., 2020)

This study relates with datasets of two experiments that investigate the use of different sensors for affect recognition in a VR exergame. The first experiment compares the impact of physical exertion and gamification on psychophysiological measurements during rest, conventional exercise, VR exergaming, and sedentary VR gaming. The second experiment compares underwhelming, overwhelming and optimal VR exergaming scenarios. They identify gaze fixations, eye blinks, pupil diameter and skin conductivity as psychophysiological measures suitable for affect recognition in VR exergaming and analyze their utility in determining affective valence and arousal. Their findings provide guidelines for researchers of affective VR exergames. [AVAILABILITY⁴²]

Physiological activity during a virtual reality serious game dataset (Dużmańska-Misiarczyk, 2021)

This dataset includes data that were collected during an experimental study aimed at testing the ability of a virtual reality SG to evoke certain affective states. The data were collected using the BITalino device and the EDA and ECG sensors. This dataset could inform the design of the emotional games of iPROLEPSIS AI-PGS to maximize their affective effectiveness. [AVAILABILITY⁴³]

6.2.2.5 Characterizing SG goal: cognitive state

EEG in SGs (Babusiak et al., 2021)

This dataset includes EEG data during a SG for assessing the cognitive improvement via the SG. This assessment was based on the analysis of the spectrogram of particular brain activity. Changes in brain activity power at a characteristic frequency band during the gameplay were calculated from the spectrogram. This dataset could provide some initial perspective on the

⁴⁰ <https://data.mendeley.com/datasets/b3pn4kwpmn/3>

⁴¹ <https://www.synapse.org/#!Synapse:syn43685982.2/datasets/>

⁴² <https://researchdata.bath.ac.uk/758/>

⁴³ <https://zenodo.org/record/4750613>

cognitive functionality during SGs that could be taken into consideration in the design of the iPROLEPSIS AI-PGS. [AVAILABILITY: from authors upon request]

Brain-IT (Manser, 2022)

This dataset includes data to evaluate the feasibility, system usability, and acceptance of a newly developed training concept ('Brain-IT') that combines exergame-based motor cognitive training with HRV-guided resonance breathing for older adults with mild neurocognitive disorder (mNCD). Via a pilot RCT with an allocation ratio of 2: 1 (i.e., intervention : control) it was found that feasibility and usability of the 'Brain-IT' training implemented with the 'Senso Flex' were acceptable. This dataset could contribute to the design of breathing games within the iPROLEPSIS AI-PGS. [AVAILABILITY⁴⁴]

6.2.2.6 Characterizing SG goal: autonomic nervous system response

HRV in SGs (Hou et al., 2021)

This dataset includes the physiological response in normal elderly people as they play two types of SGs using HRV features from ECG. A wearable device designed in-house was used to measure ECG, and 10 HRV features were extracted, including time-domain, nonlinear, and frequency-domain features. The dataset includes data from 30 older adults (age: 65.9 ± 7.34 ; male: 15, female: 15). The statistical results show that there was a significant difference in the HRV between the two types of games. From this, it can be concluded that the type of game has a significant effect on the autonomic nervous system response. This can contribute to the design of the iPROLEPSIS AI-PGS. [AVAILABILITY: from authors upon request]

Within the iPROLEPSIS project's duration, we intend to gather specific datasets that consider the unique characteristics of PsA patients and their interaction with SGs to ensure more accurate and tailored applications in this domain. In addition, expanding the availability of such datasets will undoubtedly facilitate the exploration of novel approaches for leveraging SGs to benefit individuals with PsA.

Section highlight

Diet and physical activity have been linked to PsO and PsA which can be modified and improved by providing patient with recommendations. Recommendations can be provided based on content, collaborative filtering and hybrid approaches. SG are another approach to improve patient behaviour. Applications of SG include (re)education, rehabilitation, addressing physical and mental health concerns and assisting in disease screening and diagnosis. Diet, physical activity, medication adherence, social support, cognition, breathing, biological and neural function are all targets for SG. No previous SG targeted PsA. Datasets have been identified for healthy participants and patients of different age and disease groups, however none was focused to patients with PsO and PsA.

7 Methods for datasets harmonisation and curation

In selecting the Common Data Model (CDM) for iPROLEPSIS project, focused discussions were conducted with technical and clinical partners. First, options were narrowed down to Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership (OMOP) and Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources (FHIR) CDMs. After thorough examination, OMOP CDM was opted to be used for transforming datasets in task T2.4. The decision was guided by key factors: (i) Standardization: Clear and unique standards to enhance interoperability, which is our primary

⁴⁴ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7428378>

goal; (ii) Support: Robust support networks, including comprehensive documentation, open training resources, and active communities. This support accelerates the adoption of the chosen CDM; (iii) Conversion Tools: Availability of software tools to streamline data transformation to the CDM is essential.

OMOP has a unique vocabulary of standard terms, which brings consistency amongst all OMOP datasets. Furthermore, OHDSI consortium released a statement, shortly after the initiation of our project, requesting community contributions for the updates of the dictionaries. We consider this as a great opportunity for iPROLEPSIS. AINIGMA Technologies is involved in the vocabulary update process in order to include variables (e.g., wearables measurements) which are essential for the research conducted within iPROLEPSIS but are not currently standardized in OMOP. By the vocabulary update process, task T2.4 is achieving interoperability of iPROLEPSIS data with any future application which is using OMOP standardized data, as well as disseminating some of the initial results to other contributors that might work in similar focus areas. Key enablers for this transformation include: (i) Active OMOP Community: We benefit from an engaged community offering documentation, forums, conferences, working groups, and training courses; (ii) Free Data Transformation Tools: Community-developed software tools like White Rabbit, Rabbit in the Hat, and Usagi simplify the process of converting data to OMOP.

Overall, OMOP and FHIR complement each other. This led to an official collaboration initiated in 2021, with regular meetings and forthcoming official tools for seamless data transformation between the two standards. It is expected that upon completion of the project automated transformation from OMOP to FHIR will be also possible.

The term Extract Transform Load (ETL) is used to describe the standardization (OMOPing) of source data to OMOP CDM. The process follows a series of standard steps, assisted by software tools. We present the methodology we followed briefly here.

In **Figure 24**, we provide an overview of OMOP CDM Schema. All variables of interest will be mapped to standard concepts of the various tables presented in the figure (**Figure 24**).

Figure 24 OMOP CDM schema. The figure shows the standard tables of OMOP CDM. All iPROLEPSIS data will be converted to this format.

An example of using USAGI software on ReumaPT data is shown in **Supplementary Figure 9**. USAGI is a software that greatly simplifies OMOPing data, by mapping non-standardized variables to tentative matches in standard terms in OMOP vocabularies. Usagi returns for each variable the most similar terms in OMOP vocabularies. For some cases that USAGI results are out-of-context, we proceed with manual mapping to OMOP standard concept ids.

Using Rabbit-In-A-Hat for ReumaPT we mapped each source table with corresponding table on OMOP CDMV5.4 and for each field of any table (e.g., person table) we matched it with the corresponding OMOP fields (Figure 25).

After the Identification of the concept ids for the ReumaPT cohort, using USAGI, Rabbit-In-A-Hat was used to match the source data tables to OMOP tables. Rabbit-In-A-Hat generates the ETL report which is then used to convert the data to OMOP by SQL queries. For each of the variables that the Usagi could not help us in the identification of the concept ids, we manually search them in OMOP’s “Athena” vocabulary.

Figure 25 Use of Rabbit-In-A-Hat for Reuma.pt data.

In **Table 7**, we provide an example of mapping variables of interest to OMOP CDM standard concepts. Type of Data, ‘Observation’ and ‘Measurement’ in this example, are Tables in OMOP Schema (see **Figure 24**). Each variable of interest has been mapped to a standard concept with a unique concept id. Standard concepts in OMOP are inherited from standard vocabularies.

Table 7 Variables of interest and their associated OMOP concepts ids for data collected through wearables in iPROLEPSIS.

Variable of interest	Concept IDs	Type of Data	Standard Vocabulary
Body Energy	4234875	Observation	SNOMED
Sleep behavior/sleep	4123007	Observation	SMOMED
Stress	1001951	Measurement	LOINC
Calories	3028782	Measurement	LOINC
Heart rate	4301868	Measurement	SNOMED
Distance	3031111	Measurement	LOINC

Variable of interest	Concept IDs	Type of Data	Standard Vocabulary
Intensity	44786666	Observation	LOINC
Step count	40758552	Observation	LOINC
Stair count	4121036	Observation	SNOMED
Bowel sounds	4337265	Observation	SNOMED
Electrogastrography	4091889	Procedure	SNOMED
Arm movement	35622747	Condition	SNOMED
Diet	3007882	Measurement	LOINC
Raw Accelerometer statistics	4110139	Observation	SNOMED
Daily Time spent and interruptions of sedentary behaviors	36305596	Observation	LOINC
Time spent in light physical activity	3965722	Measurement	LOINC
Time spent in moderate physical activity	3964780	Measurement	LOINC
Time spent in vigorous physical activity	3965425	Measurement	LOINC
Daily physical activity habits	1988333	Observation	LOINC
Postural transitions	4152180	Observation	SNOMED
Movement quality	4113276	Observation	SNOMED

In conclusion, we have made the following achievements with their associated outcomes:

Environmental Data Curation (finished): Data quality analysis (missing values, variables identification, sampling (time and space) frequency). Availability (open or subscription?). Description of data retrieval process for each dataset.

Environmental Data retrieval (ongoing): We focused on air pollution data from three (Greece, Portugal, Netherlands) countries. The extraction of the data involves careful selection of relevant variables for each dataset, guided by the project's needs. Considering PsO/PsA disease mechanisms, it was decided that pollution data on a time-horizon of two years is relevant to disease activity. We selected to monitor the particles involved in air pollution, such as NO, NO₂, NO_x, O₃, PM₁₀, PM₂₅, SO₂, and the Air Quality Index (AQI) which indicates the level of air pollution. We retrieve new pollution data monthly, to ensure that we have up-to-date datasets when the iPROLEPSIS clinical study starts.

Decision on CDM (finished): OMOP CDM will be used throughout the project.

Variables of interest identification (finished): In collaboration with the consortium, the full list of variables that will be monitored and processed in this project was compiled. Each variable was mapped to related OMOP concepts. The identified variables of interest for iPROLEPSIS PDPID study are given in Table 8.

OMOP Community Contributions (ongoing): We participate in OHDSI Community Calls and OHDSI Symposium. The discussions will enable the optimal, i.e. achieving maximum interoperability, transformation of iPROLEPSIS data (especially mobile health data) to OMOP standard and future OMOP CDM releases. We have participated in Vocabulary Workgroup and Healthcare Systems Interest Group regular (weekly) meetings. We are contributing to OHDSI community effort to establish a process for custom term mappings to be shared and reused by researchers/developers.

Standardize in OMOP cohort data (ongoing): The three cohorts (ReumaPT, MONITOR, DEPAR) analyzed within the project, will be standardized in time for PDPID study launch. We

have aligned our effort with OpenClinica platform development (WP5), ensuring seamless integration with PDPID study data collection. Concerning the REUMAPT study, the OMOPed dictionary that was available is only an early draft version and far from finalized (there has been only a separation of the variables in the standard OMOP tables). We are currently working towards the mapping of the REUMAPT to provide the finalized OMOPed version of the whole study.

Table 8 Variables of interest and for data collected in iPROLEPSIS PDPID study.

Composite scores	Variable study of interest
secondary study parameters	MDA
secondary study parameters	PASDAS
secondary study parameters	DAPSA
secondary study parameters	PSAID
Other study parameters	CASPAR score
Questionnaires	Variable of interest
secondary study parameters	10-point likert scale morning stiffness
secondary study parameters	PSAID1 pain
secondary study parameters	PSAID2 fatigue
Other study parameters	Demographics
Other study parameters	VAS pain and patient global
Other study parameters	HAQ to measure physical function
Other study parameters	Psoriatic Arthritis Impact of Disease (PSAID)
Other study parameters	36-item Short Form Survey (SF36) for general health
Other study parameters	EQ5d for general health assessment
Other study parameters	Work Productivity and Activity Impairment (WPAI)
Other study parameters	Patient Health Questionnaire (PHQ9) for depression
Other study parameters	Life events
Other study parameters	Health care usage
Other study parameters	Global Rating of Change Questionnaire (GRCQ) to evaluate disease activity change
Other study parameters	Perceived Stress Scale (PSS)
Clinical assessment	Variable of interest
Other study parameters	Age
Other study parameters	Sex
Other study parameters	Years of disease
Other study parameters	Medication over the year of the study
Other study parameters	Comorbidity
Other study parameters	Care activities
Other study parameters	Job title
Other study parameters	shift work
Other study parameters	frequent fly
Other study parameters	66/68 joint count for swelling and tenderness
Other study parameters	6 tendon count for enthesitis using Leeds Enthesitis Index (LEI)
Other study parameters	Body Surface Area for skin
Other study parameters	BMI
Other study parameters	Abdominal circumference
Biological markers	Variable of interest

Other study parameters	DNA
Other study parameters	CRP
Other study parameters	HLA-B27
Other study parameters	Gut microbiome
Other study parameters	Hair cortisol
Environmental factors	Variable of interest
Other study parameters	Humidity
Other study parameters	Temperature
Other study parameters	Air Pollution: NO
Other study parameters	Air Pollution: NO2
Other study parameters	Air Pollution: Nox
Other study parameters	Air pollution: O3
Other study parameters	Air pollution: PM10
Other study parameters	Air pollution: PM25
Other study parameters	Air pollution: SO2

8 Conclusions

PsA is a chronic immune mediated inflammatory arthritis occurring in patients with PsO. The disease manifestation can be heterogeneous between subjects, and the resulting musculoskeletal impairment can interfere with physical function as well as quality of life of patients. A baseline model on predictors of inflammation in PsA with main focus on flare has been developed, of which the included variables were reviewed in this deliverable, as well as the clinical implications. The key takeaways from D2.2 are:

- Fatigue, pain and stiffness are commonly reported symptoms in PsA
- Flare may be triggered by alterations in mood, stress, sleep, bowel movements, and environmental factors
- Flare may affect mood, stress, sleep, bowel movements, physical activity and fine motor skills
- Certain symptoms of PsA may also trigger or be triggered by flare
- Clinical measurements of PsA symptoms and hypothesized flare associated factors, mainly include questionnaires
- The use of smartphone and wearables to monitor physical activity (mainly through accelerometer data), fine motor skills (through keystroke dynamics), heart rate, heart rate variability have also shown potential to measure PsA symptoms and hypothesized flare associated factors
- Electrography techniques can be also used in the assessment of certain symptoms and flare associated factors
- Genetic factors may contribute to development of PsA, pain perception and response to treatment. Gut microbiome may be involved in PsA. MCs in skin are suggested to play a role in skin inflammation
- Monitoring of PsA can be achieved through clinical examination for inflamed joints, enthesitis dactylitis, nail and skin and subsequent calculation of relative indices and composite scores
- Imaging-based approaches including images obtained from smartphones and optoacoustics represent a complementary or alternative approach to clinical assessment

- Data-driven models can serve to find predictive relations even when the underlying mechanisms are poorly understood or are too complex.
- Recommendations and SGs present a potential approach to modify and improve diet and physical activity
- Besides diet and physical activity, SGs can also address other aspects of disease including medication adherence, social support, cognition, breathing, biological and neural function
- OMOP CDM was opted to be used for standardizing the datasets

Future steps include update (deliverable D2.4) on state-of-art literature and measurement tools on the different topics covered in this report, and the identification of new datasets that could be relevant for data-driven models. Further details on existing prediction models for disease activity and their utilization in the project's implementation will be also provided in deliverable D2.4.

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Appendix I Supplementary material

Supplementary Table 1 Studies assessing stiffness in patients with Rheumatoid Arthritis.

Ref.	Type	Population	Axial/Peripheral	Instrument	PRO	Domains	Measurements	Rating	Accuracy
(Rhind et al., 1987)	OS	RA	NA	Set of rating scales	Yes	1. Severity 2. Severity 3. Severity 4. Duration	1. NA 2. NA 3. NA 4. How long did it take for your stiffness to begin to ease after you got out of bed this morning?	1. 10cm VAS 2. 11-point NRS 3. 5-point VS (no, mild, moderate, severe, very severe) 4. Minutes	NA
(Ward, 1993)	OS	RA	NA	Individual question	Yes	1. Duration	1. NA	1. Minutes	Moderate correlation with tender joint count (r=0.54, p<0.001). Low accuracy and sensitivity to change.
(Hazes et al., 1994)	OS	RA	NA	Set of questions	Yes	1. Duration 2. Duration 3. Duration 4. Duration 5. Duration 6. Duration	1. Waking to first improvement 2. Getting up to first improvement 3. Waking to maximum improvement 4. Getting up to maximum improvement 5. Waking to complete disappearance 6. Getting up to complete disappearance	1. Minutes 2. Minutes 3. Minutes 4. Minutes 5. Minutes 6. Minutes	Substantial within-patient variability and low accuracy. Estimation of time from waking to maximum improvement in those whose stiffness does not persist all day, seems to be the best indicator of the average duration of MS.

Ref.	Type	Population	Axial/Peripheral	Instrument	PRO	Domains	Measurements	Rating	Accuracy
(Wolfe, 1999)	OS	RA, OA, FM	NA	WOMAC (Two questions)	Yes	1. Severity 2. Severity after immobility in the morning	1. How severe has your stiffness been after you first woke up? 2. How severe has your stiffness been after sitting or lying down or while resting later in the day?	1. 100-mm VAS 2. 100-mm VAS	NA
(Fransen et al., 2000)	OS	RA	NA	RADAI (Question 4)	Yes	1. Presence 2. Duration	1. Were your joints stiff when you woke up today? 2. If yes, how long did this extra stiffness last?	1. Yes/No 2. <30 min, 30 min–1h, 1–2h, 2–4h, >4h, all day	Low accuracy and low internal consistency.
(Leeb et al., 2003)	OS	RA, OA	NA	SACRAH (Two questions)	Yes	1. Severity 2. Severity after a time of rest 3. Duration	1. NA 2. NA 3. NA	1. 100-mm VAS 2. 100-mm VAS 3. Minutes	NA
(Yazici et al., 2004)	OS	RA	NA	MHAQ (One question)	Yes	1. Duration	1. NA	1. Minutes	NA
(Westhoff et al., 2008)	OS	RA	NA	Set of questions	Yes	1. Severity 2. Duration	1. NA 2. NA	1. 10-NRS 2. Minutes	NA
(Khan et al., 2009)	OS	RA	NA	Set of questions	Yes	1. Duration	1. From time of waking to time of max improvement	1. Minutes	Moderate accuracy in distinguishing clinically active from inactive RA.
(Berthelot et al., 2012)	OS	RA	NA	FLARE (Question 1)	Yes	1. Presence	1. You noticed the appearance or worsening of morning stiffness in	1. 6-point LK ('absolutely true' to	NA

Ref.	Type	Population	Axial/Peripheral	Instrument	PRO	Domains	Measurements	Rating	Accuracy
							joints over several consecutive days	'completely untrue')	
(Jastrzabek et al., 2013)	RCT	RA	NA	Individual question	Yes	1. Duration	1. NA	1. Minutes	NA
(Wiesinger et al., 2013)	OS	RA	NA	Individual question	Yes	NA	NA	NA	NA
(Hamad et al., 2014)	OS	RA	NA	Individual question	Yes	1. Duration	1. How long does your MS last until maximum improvement occurs?	1. Minutes	NA
(Lie et al., 2014)	OS	RA	NA	<i>BASDAI</i> (Questions 5 and 6)	Yes	1. Severity 2. Duration	1. How would you describe the overall level of morning stiffness you have had from the time you wake up? 2. How long does your morning stiffness last from the time you wake up?	1. 10-cm VAS 2. 10-cm VAS	NA
(Bartlett et al., 2015)	OS	RA	NA	<i>RADAI</i> (Question 4)	Yes	1. Presence 2. Duration	1. Were your joints stiff when you woke up today? 2. If yes, how long did this extra stiffness last?	1. Yes/No 2. <30 min, 30 min–1h, 1–2h, 2–4h, >4h, all day	NA
(Ward et al., 2015a)	OS	RA	NA	Set of questions	Yes	1. Severity 2. Change 3. Importance of change	1. NA 2. Since the start of the study, my stiffness has... 3. NA	1. 100-mm VAS 2. 3-point VS (improved,	NA

Ref.	Type	Population	Axial/Peripheral	Instrument	PRO	Domains	Measurements	Rating	Accuracy
								stayed the same, worsened) 3. 7-point VS (Almost none, hardly at all, A little important, Somewhat important, Moderately important, A good deal important, Very important, Extremely important)	
(Ward et al., 2015a; Ward et al., 2015b)	OS	RA	NA	Set of questions	Yes	1. Severity 2. Duration	1. NA 2. How long does your MS last until maximum improvement occurs?	1. 100-mm VAS 2. Minutes	NA

BASDAI: Bath Ankylosing Spondylitis Functional Index; FLARE: Flare Assessment in Rheumatoid Arthritis; FM: Fibromyalgia; LS: Likert scale; MS: Morning stiffness; NA: Not available; NRS: Numerical scale; MHAQ: Modified Health Assessment Questionnaire; OA: Osteoarthritis; OS: Observational study; PRO: Patient-reported outcome; RA: Rheumatoid arthritis; RADAI: Rheumatoid Arthritis Disease Activity Index; RCT: Randomized control trial; SACRAH: Score for assessment and quantification of chronic rheumatic affections of the hands; VAS: Visual analogue scale; VS: Verbal scale; WOMAC: Western Ontario and McMaster University Osteoarthritis index

Supplementary Table 2 The RAST Stiffness PROM questions and response options (Halls, 2016).

RA Stiffness PROM	Response options
Severity components	
1. Over the past 7 days when have you experienced RA stiffness? Please tick all that apply to you	In the night In the morning In the afternoon In the evening None of these
2. Have you experienced RA stiffness in your joints over the past 7 days?	No, not in any of my joints Yes, in a few of my joints Yes, in many of my joints Yes, in all of my joints
3. Over the past 7 days have you experienced RA stiffness after a period of immobility (for example, after sitting for a while)?	No, not at all Yes, a little Yes, quite a lot Yes, very much
4. Please circle the number that best describes the severity of your RA stiffness over the past 7 days	10-point NSR (No to Extreme)
5. Please circle the number that best describes the impact that RA stiffness has had on your life over the past 7 days	10-point NSR (No to A great deal)
6. Please circle the number that best describes how important RA stiffness has been in your life over the past 7 days	10-point NSR (No to Very)
7. Were your joints stiff when you woke up today? If yes, how long did this extra stiffness last?	Less than 30min 30 min to an hour 1 - 2 hours 2 - 4 hours More than 4 hours but less than all day All day
8. How would you describe the overall level of morning stiffness you have had from the time you wake up?	10-point NSR (No to Very severe)
Physical components	
9. Has RA stiffness made it difficult to dress or undress yourself?	Not at all A little Quite a lot Very much
10. Has RA stiffness made it difficult to wash yourself (for example, have a shower)?	Not at all A little Quite a lot Very much
11. Has RA stiffness made it difficult to carry out your responsibilities or commitments?	Not at all A little Quite a lot Very much
12. Has RA stiffness made it difficult to do your daily tasks or activities?	Not at all A little Quite a lot Very much
13. Has RA stiffness made it difficult to get out of bed?	Not at all A little Quite a lot Very much
14. Has RA stiffness made it difficult to do fine movements (for example, write with a pen)?	Not at all A little

	Quite a lot Very much
15. Has RA stiffness made it difficult to grip or hold things?	Not at all A little Quite a lot Very much
16. Has RA stiffness made it difficult to balance without physically supporting yourself?	Not at all A little Quite a lot Very much
Psychosocial components	
17. Have you felt frustrated because of RA stiffness?	Not at all A little Quite a lot Very much
18. Have you felt worried or concerned because of RA stiffness?	Not at all A little Quite a lot Very much
19. Have you felt self-conscious because of RA stiffness?	Not at all A little Quite a lot Very much
20. Have you had to change your plans or behaviour because of RA stiffness?	Not at all A little Quite a lot Very much
21. Have you had to work around your RA stiffness (or do things in a different way)?	Not at all A little Quite a lot Very much

Supplementary Table 3 OMERACT summary of evidence for measurement properties of the RAST (Craig et al., 2019)

Psychometric property	Quality of evidence	Studies available
Truth domain match	Good evidence	4
Feasibility	No evidence	0
Construct validity	Low evidence	1
Test-retest reliability	No evidence	2
Longitudinal construct validity	No evidence	0
Clinical trial discrimination	No evidence	0
Thresholds of meaning	No evidence	0

Supplementary Table 4 The 3 stiffness questions PROM and response options.

3 item stiffness questions	Response options
1. In the past 7 days, how long did your stiffness last on average?	None < 30 min 30 min - 1 hour 1 - 2 hours 2 - 4 hours > 4 hours
2. In the past 7 days, how would you rate your stiffness on average?	None Mild Moderate Severe Very severe
3. In the past 7 days, how often did your stiffness interfere with your activities?	Never Rarely Sometimes Often Always
<u>Additional question:</u> How would you describe your stiffness in the past week?	100-mm VAS

VAS: Visual Analogue Scale

Supplementary Table 5 The Morning Stiffness Assessment Scale questionnaire and response options.
Retrieved from: (Oh et al., 2021).

Morning Stiffness Assessment Scale	Response options
1. How much stiffness do you experience after waking up in the morning?	Very stiff Somewhat stiff Almost no stiffness No stiffness
2. I have difficulties moving my body for a while after waking up due to morning stiffness.	Strongly agree Agree to some extent Disagree to some extent Not agree at all
3. How long does morning stiffness last after waking up?	Within 10 minutes of awaking Within 30 minutes of awaking More than 60 minutes of awaking Within 3 hours of awaking Almost all day
4. My morning stiffness affects only one or two joints.	Strongly agree Agree to some extent Disagree to some extent Not agree at all
5. Morning stiffness causes more pain.	Strongly agree Agree to some extent Disagree to some extent Not agree at all
6. I have difficulties performing daily activities, such as, tooth brushing or face washing, due to morning stiffness.	Strongly agree Agree to some extent Disagree to some extent Not agree at all
7. I have difficulties performing housework or going to work due to stiffness in the morning.	Strongly agree Agree to some extent Disagree to some extent Not agree at all
8. I am unable to work and stay in bed all morning due to morning stiffness.	Strongly agree Agree to some extent Disagree to some extent Not agree at all
9. I am depressed due to morning stiffness.	Strongly agree Agree to some extent Disagree to some extent Not agree at all
10. Morning stiffness lowers my quality of life.	Strongly agree Agree to some extent Disagree to some extent Not agree at all

Supplementary Table 6 Psychometric properties of the MSAS.

Psychometric property	Results
Construct validity	
Exploratory power	Acceptable (cumulated variance 62.5%).
Nomologic validity	Good nomologic validity Significant correlation with pain ($r=0.68$, $p<0.001$), functional disability ($r=0.61$, $p<0.001$), and quality of life ($r=0.54$, $p<0.001$).
Reliability	Good reliability (Cronbach $\alpha = 0.89$).

Supplementary Table 7 Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index questionnaire

ID	Question	Response			
1	During the past month, what time have you usually gone to bed at night?	<i>(Bedtime)</i>			
2	During the past month, how long (in minutes) has it usually taken you to fall asleep each night?	<i>(Number of minutes)</i>			
3	During the past month, what time have you usually gotten up in the morning?	<i>(Getting up time)</i>			
4	During the past month, how many hours of <u>actual sleep</u> did you get at night? (This may be different than the number of hours you spent in bed.)	<i>(Hours of sleep per night)</i>			
5	During the past month, how often have you had trouble sleeping because you ...	Not during the past month	Less than once a week	Once or twice a week	Three or more times a week
5a.	Cannot get to sleep within 30 minutes				
5b.	Wake up in the middle of the night or early morning				
5c.	Have to get up to use the bathroom				
5d.	Cannot breathe comfortably				
5e.	Cough or snore loudly				
5f.	Feel too cold				
5g.	Feel too hot				
5h.	Have bad dreams				
5i.	Have pain				
5j.	Other reason(s), please describe: _____				
6	During the past month, how often have you taken medicine to help you sleep (prescribed or “over the counter”)?				
7	During the past month, how often have you had trouble staying awake while driving, eating meals, or engaging in social activity?				
		No problem at all	Only a very slight problem	Somewhat of a problem	A very big problem

ID	Question	Response			
8	During the past month, how much of a problem has it been for you to keep up enough enthusiasm to get things done?				
		Very good	Fairly good	Fairly bad	Very bad
9	During the past month, how would you rate your sleep quality overall?				
		No bed partner or roommate	Partner / roommate in other room	Partner in same room but not same bed	Partner in same bed
10	Do you have a bed partner or roommate?				
	If you have a roommate or bed partner, ask him/her how often in the past month you have had:	Not during the past month	Less than once a week	Once or twice a week	Three times a week
10a.	Loud snoring				
10b.	Long pauses between breaths while asleep				
10c.	Legs twitching or jerking while you sleep				
10d.	Episodes of disorientation or confusion during sleep				
10e.	Other restlessness while you sleep, please describe: _____				

Supplementary Table 8 Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index scoring system.

Component 1: Subjective sleep quality	
Response to Q9	Component 1 score
Very good	0
Fairly good	1
Fairly bad	2
Very bad	3
Component 2: Sleep latency	
Response to Q2	Q2 sub score
< 15 minutes	0
16-30 minutes	1
31-60 minutes	2
> 60 minutes	3
Response to Q5a	Q5a sub score
Not during past month	0
Less than once a week	1
Once or twice a week	2
Three or more times a week	3
Sum of Q2 and Q5a sub scores	Component 2 score
0	0
1-2	1
3-4	2
5-6	3
Component 3: Sleep duration	
Response to Q4	Component 3 score
> 7 hours	0
6-7 hours	1
5-6 hours	2
< 5 hours	3
Component 4: Sleep efficiency	
$\frac{\text{hours slept (Q4 response)}}{\text{hours in bed (Q3 response - Q1 response)}} * 100\%$	Component 4 score
> 85%	0
75-84%	1
65-74%	2
< 65%	3
Component 5: Sleep disturbance	
Responses to Q5b - Q5j	Q5b-Q5j sub scores
Not during past month	0
Less than once a week	1
Once or twice a week	2
Three or more times a week	3
Sum of 5b to 5j scores	Component 5 score
0	0
1-9	1
10-18	2

19-27	3
Component 6: Use of sleep medication	
Response to Q6	Component 6 score
Not during past month	0
Less than once a week	1
Once or twice a week	2
Three or more times a week	3
Component 7: Daytime dysfunction	
Response to Q7	Q7 sub score
Not during past month	0
Less than once a week	1
Once or twice a week	2
Three or more times a week	3
<i>Response to Q8</i>	<i>Q8 sub score</i>
No problem at all	0
Only a very slight problem	1
Somewhat of a problem	2
A very big problem	3
Sum of Q7 and Q8 sub scores	Component 7 score
0	0
1-2	1
3-4	2
5-6	3

Supplementary Table 9 Formulas of disease activity composite scores in PsA (Adapted from Schoels (Schoels, 2014))

Score	Joint count	Formula
DAPSA	66/68	SJC + TJC + PtG + PP + CRP [mg/dl]
PASDAS	66/68	$((0.18 \cdot \sqrt{EGA}) + (0.159 \times \sqrt{PtG}) - (0.253 \cdot \sqrt{SF36/PCS}) + (0.101 \times \ln(SJC + 1)) + (0.048 \cdot \ln(TJC + 1)) + (0.23 \times \ln(LEI + 1)) + (0.377 \ln(TDC + 1)) + (0.102 \times \ln(CRP_{mg/dl} + 1))) \cdot 1.5$
CPDAI	66/68	Peripheral arthritis (joint count and HAQ) + skin disease (PASI and DLQI) + enthesitis (LEI and HAQ) + dactylitis (digit count and HAQ) + axial disease (BASDAI and ASQoL)
DAS28-ESR or -CRP	28	$0.56 \cdot \sqrt{TJC} + 0.28 \cdot \sqrt{SJC} + 0.70 \ln(ESR) + 0.014 \cdot PtG$ $0.56 \cdot \sqrt{TJC} + 0.28 \cdot \sqrt{SJC} + 0.36 \ln(CRP [mg/dl] + 1) + 0.014 \cdot PtG + 0.96$

DAS28, Disease Activity Score 28 Joints; DAPSA, Disease Activity in Psoriatic Arthritis; PASDAS, Psoriatic Arthritis Disease Activity Score; CPDAI, Composite Psoriatic Disease Activity Index; TJC, tender joint count, SJC, swollen joint count; PtG, patient global assessment; PP, patient pain; CRP, C-reactive protein; ESR, erythrocyte sedimentation rate; EGA, physician global assessment; SF36 PCS, Medical Outcomes Survey Short Form-36 Physical Component Score; LEI, Leeds Enthesitis Index; TDC, tender dactylitis count; HAQ, Health Assessment Questionnaire; PASI, Psoriasis Area Severity Index; DLQI, Dermatology Life Quality Index; BASDAI, Bath Ankylosing Spondylitis Disease Activity Index; ASQoL, Ankylosing Spondylitis Quality of Life.

Supplementary Table 10 Distribution of the classes of Nail Disease Detection Computer Vision Project and Nail Disease Computer Vision Project datasets

Class	Example image of the class	Nail Disease Detection Computer Vision Project dataset	Nail Disease Computer Vision Project dataset
Acral Lentiginous Melanoma		357	75
Beaus Line		218	97
Blue Nail		292	339
Clubbing		373	73
Koilonychia		259	92
Muehrck Lines		159	65
Lindsay's Nail		2	19
Terry's Nail		421	73

Pitting		312	
Onychogryphosis		329	343
Onycholysis			344
Onychomycosis			167
Onychocryptosis			48
Leukonychia			29
Paronychia			113
Pachyonychia Congenita			17
Darier Nail			8
Hang Nail			6

Median Nail			73
Pincer Nail			38
White Nail			29
Yellow Nail			80
Alopecia Areate			22
Eczema			76
Pseudomonas			76
Psoriasis			169
Red Lunula			6

Ridging Beading			66
Splinter Hemmorage			15
Subungual Hematoma			82
Trachyonychia			86
Healthy Nail		298	370

Supplementary Figure 1 Example of Consensus Sleep Diary.

Sample		ID/Name: _____						
Today's date	4/5/11							
1. What time did you get into bed?	10:15 PM							
2. What time did you try to go to sleep?	11:30 PM							
3. How long did it take you to fall asleep?	55 min							
4. How many times did you wake up, not counting your final awakening?	6 times							
5. In total, how long did these awakenings last?	2 hours 5 min							
6a. What time was your final awakening?	6:35 AM							
6b. After your final awakening, how long did you spend in bed trying to sleep?	45 min							
6c. Did you wake up earlier than you planned?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No
6d. If yes, how much earlier?	1 hour							
7. What time did you get out of bed for the day?	7:20 AM							
8. In total, how long did you sleep?	4 hours 10 min							
9. How would you rate the quality of your sleep?	<input type="checkbox"/> Very poor <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Poor <input type="checkbox"/> Fair <input type="checkbox"/> Good <input type="checkbox"/> Very good	<input type="checkbox"/> Very poor <input type="checkbox"/> Poor <input type="checkbox"/> Fair <input type="checkbox"/> Good <input type="checkbox"/> Very good	<input type="checkbox"/> Very poor <input type="checkbox"/> Poor <input type="checkbox"/> Fair <input type="checkbox"/> Good <input type="checkbox"/> Very good	<input type="checkbox"/> Very poor <input type="checkbox"/> Poor <input type="checkbox"/> Fair <input type="checkbox"/> Good <input type="checkbox"/> Very good	<input type="checkbox"/> Very poor <input type="checkbox"/> Poor <input type="checkbox"/> Fair <input type="checkbox"/> Good <input type="checkbox"/> Very good	<input type="checkbox"/> Very poor <input type="checkbox"/> Poor <input type="checkbox"/> Fair <input type="checkbox"/> Good <input type="checkbox"/> Very good	<input type="checkbox"/> Very poor <input type="checkbox"/> Poor <input type="checkbox"/> Fair <input type="checkbox"/> Good <input type="checkbox"/> Very good	<input type="checkbox"/> Very poor <input type="checkbox"/> Poor <input type="checkbox"/> Fair <input type="checkbox"/> Good <input type="checkbox"/> Very good
10. How rested or refreshed did you feel when you woke up for the day?	<input type="checkbox"/> Not at all rested <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Slightly rested <input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat rested <input type="checkbox"/> Well-rested <input type="checkbox"/> Very well-rested	<input type="checkbox"/> Not at all rested <input type="checkbox"/> Slightly rested <input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat rested <input type="checkbox"/> Well-rested <input type="checkbox"/> Very well-rested	<input type="checkbox"/> Not at all rested <input type="checkbox"/> Slightly rested <input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat rested <input type="checkbox"/> Well-rested <input type="checkbox"/> Very well-rested	<input type="checkbox"/> Not at all rested <input type="checkbox"/> Slightly rested <input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat rested <input type="checkbox"/> Well-rested <input type="checkbox"/> Very well-rested	<input type="checkbox"/> Not at all rested <input type="checkbox"/> Slightly rested <input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat rested <input type="checkbox"/> Well-rested <input type="checkbox"/> Very well-rested	<input type="checkbox"/> Not at all rested <input type="checkbox"/> Slightly rested <input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat rested <input type="checkbox"/> Well-rested <input type="checkbox"/> Very well-rested	<input type="checkbox"/> Not at all rested <input type="checkbox"/> Slightly rested <input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat rested <input type="checkbox"/> Well-rested <input type="checkbox"/> Very well-rested	<input type="checkbox"/> Not at all rested <input type="checkbox"/> Slightly rested <input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat rested <input type="checkbox"/> Well-rested <input type="checkbox"/> Very well-rested
11a. How many times did you nap or doze?	2 times							
11b. In total, how long did you nap or doze?	1 hour 10 min							
12a. How many drinks containing alcohol did you have?	3 drinks							
12b. What time was your last drink?	9:20 PM							
13a. How many caffeinated drinks (coffee, tea, soda, energy drinks) did you have?	2 drinks							
13b. What time was your last drink?	9:20 PM							
14. Did you take any over-the-counter or prescription medication(s) to help you sleep? If so, list medication(s) dose, and time taken	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No Medication(s): Relaxo-Herb Dose: 50 mg Time(s) taken: 11 PM	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No Medication(s): Dose: Time(s) taken:						
15. Comments (if applicable)	I have a cold							

Supplementary Figure 2 (a) A graphic illustration of the PSG setting and (b) a five second PSG recording from the SHHS Polysomnography Database during which an obstructive apnea event occurs.

(a)

(b)

Supplementary Figure 3 Classification of the main disorders evaluated with a polysomnography (Ibáñez et al., 2018).

Supplementary Figure 4 An example of wrist actigraphy data graphical presentation retrieved from (Noor et al., 2016). Each row represents a 24-hour period with activity counts plotted for each minute. The light blue shaded areas indicate times at which patient was in bed attempting to sleep. Sleep onset time, wake after sleep onset, and duration of sleep are calculated and presented on the right of the plot.

Supplementary Figure 5 Most common nail psoriasis manifestations. Left: Pitting, Centre: subungual hyperkeratosis, Right: Onycholysis. (Raposo & Torres, 2015; Sobolewski et al., 2017).

Supplementary Figure 6 Example of calculating NAPSI score (reproduced by (Rich & Scher, 2003)).

Nail Psoriasis Severity Index (NAPSI)
The target nail is graded for nail matrix psoriasis and nail bed psoriasis. The sum of these two scores is the total score for that nail.

Nail Matrix Psoriasis consists of any the following: pitting, leukonychia, red spots in the lunula, and nail plate crumbling.

score for **matrix psoriasis** 2
0=none
1=present in 1/4 nail
2=present in 2/4
3=present in 3/4
4=present in 4/4

Nail Bed Psoriasis is the presence or absence of any of the following: onycholysis, splinter hemorrhages, oil drop (salmon patch) discoloration, and nail bed hyperkeratosis.

Score for **nail bed psoriasis** 3
0=none
1=present in 1/4 nail
2=present in 2/4
3=present in 3/4
4=present in 4/4

Total for nail 5 (0-8)

Supplementary Figure 7 Some common PsO manifestation. Vulgaris (left side); Inverse (center); and generalized pustular psoriasis (right).

Supplementary Figure 8 Example of the PASI scoring sheet.

	Head	Arms
Area	<input type="radio"/> 0% <input type="radio"/> <10% <input type="radio"/> 10-29% <input type="radio"/> 30-49% <input type="radio"/> 50-69% <input type="radio"/> 70-89% <input type="radio"/> 90-100%	<input type="radio"/> 0% <input type="radio"/> <10% <input type="radio"/> 10-29% <input type="radio"/> 30-49% <input type="radio"/> 50-69% <input type="radio"/> 70-89% <input type="radio"/> 90-100%
Erythema (redness)	<input type="radio"/> 0 <input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3 <input type="radio"/> 4	<input type="radio"/> 0 <input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3 <input type="radio"/> 4
Induration (thickness)	<input type="radio"/> 0 <input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3 <input type="radio"/> 4	<input type="radio"/> 0 <input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3 <input type="radio"/> 4
Desquamation (scaling)	<input type="radio"/> 0 <input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3 <input type="radio"/> 4	<input type="radio"/> 0 <input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3 <input type="radio"/> 4
	Trunk	Legs
Area	<input type="radio"/> 0% <input type="radio"/> <10% <input type="radio"/> 10-29% <input type="radio"/> 30-49% <input type="radio"/> 50-69% <input type="radio"/> 70-89% <input type="radio"/> 90-100%	<input type="radio"/> 0% <input type="radio"/> <10% <input type="radio"/> 10-29% <input type="radio"/> 30-49% <input type="radio"/> 50-69% <input type="radio"/> 70-89% <input type="radio"/> 90-100%
Erythema (redness)	<input type="radio"/> 0 <input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3 <input type="radio"/> 4	<input type="radio"/> 0 <input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3 <input type="radio"/> 4
Induration (thickness)	<input type="radio"/> 0 <input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3 <input type="radio"/> 4	<input type="radio"/> 0 <input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3 <input type="radio"/> 4
Desquamation (scaling)	<input type="radio"/> 0 <input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3 <input type="radio"/> 4	<input type="radio"/> 0 <input type="radio"/> 1 <input type="radio"/> 2 <input type="radio"/> 3 <input type="radio"/> 4

Supplementary Figure 9 Example of using USAGI software on Reuma.pt data.

File Edit View Help

Status	Source code	Source term	Frequency	Match score	Concept ID	Concept name	Domain	Concept class	Vocabulary	Concept code	Standard concept	Parents	Children	Assigned To	Equivalence	Comment	Status Provenance
Checked	18	Naproxen	1.00	1.00	4186860	Naproxen	Observation	Substance	SNOMED	372588000	S	1	0				
Checked	25	Adalimumab	1.00	1.00	1119119	adalimumab	Drug	Ingredient	RNorm	327391	S	0	18				
Checked	23	Adalimumab	1.00	1.00	1119119	adalimumab	Drug	Ingredient	RNorm	327391	S	0	19				
Checked	2	Secinumab	1.00	1.00	4592983	secinumab	Drug	Ingredient	RNorm	1599788	S	0	17				
Checked	13	Methotrexate	1.00	1.00	4588304	Methotrexate	Meas Value	Answer	LOINC	LA1439-8	S	0	0				
Checked	21	Methotrexate	1.00	1.00	4588304	Methotrexate	Meas Value	Answer	LOINC	LA1439-8	S	0	0				
Checked	25	Methotrexate	1.00	1.00	4588304	Methotrexate	Meas Value	Answer	LOINC	LA1439-8	S	0	0				
Checked	8	Methotrexate	1.00	1.00	4588304	Methotrexate	Meas Value	Answer	LOINC	LA1439-8	S	0	0				
Checked	17	Methotrexate	1.00	1.00	4588304	Methotrexate	Meas Value	Answer	LOINC	LA1439-8	S	0	0				
Checked	9	Acemafacin	1.00	1.00	1902998	acemafacin	Drug	Ingredient	RNorm	16695	S	0	54				
Checked	19	Methotrexate	1.00	1.00	4588304	Methotrexate	Meas Value	Answer	LOINC	LA1439-8	S	0	0				
Checked	4	Methotrexate	1.00	1.00	4588304	Methotrexate	Meas Value	Answer	LOINC	LA1439-8	S	0	0				

Source code: 18 Naproxen Source term: Naproxen Frequency: -1

Target concepts:

Concept ID	Concept name	Domain	Concept class	Vocabulary	Concept code	Standard concept	Parents	Children	Mapping Type	Creation Provenance
4186860	Naproxen	Observation	Substance	SNOMED	372588000	S	1	0	MAPS_TO	<auto> (2023-10-10)

MAPS_TO [v] Remove concept

Search Query: [] Filters: []

Results:

Score	Term	Concept ID	Concept name	Domain	Concept class	Vocabulary	Concept code	Standard concept	Parents	Children
1.00	Naproxen	4186860	Naproxen	Observation	Substance	SNOMED	372588000	S	1	0
1.00	Naproxen	1115008	Naproxen	Drug	Ingredient	RNorm	7258	S	0	495
0.89	Naproxen Oral Tablet	40054724	Naproxen Oral Tablet	Drug	Clinical Drug Form	RNorm	373005	S	900	142
0.88	Naproxen 100 MG	1115096	Naproxen 100 MG	Drug	Clinical Drug Comp	RNorm	335264	S	1	4
0.87	Naproxen 50 MG	1115097	Naproxen 50 MG	Drug	Clinical Drug Comp	RNorm	335265	S	1	1
0.87	Naproxen 1000 MG	1115094	Naproxen 1000 MG	Drug	Clinical Drug Comp	RNorm	332448	S	1	7
0.86	Naproxen 100 MCGML	1115099	Naproxen 100 MCGML	Drug	Clinical Drug Comp	RNorm	335267	S	1	3
0.85	Naproxen 200 MG	4622322	Naproxen 200 MG	Drug	Clinical Drug Comp	RNorm	1608796	S	3	2
0.85	Naproxen 500 MG	1115092	Naproxen 500 MG	Drug	Clinical Drug Comp	RNorm	316326	S	1	321
0.84	Naproxen 50 MCGML	1911044	Naproxen 50 MCGML	Drug	Clinical Drug Comp	RNorm	446602	S	2	8
0.84	Naproxen 20 MCGML	1911050	Naproxen 20 MCGML	Drug	Clinical Drug Comp	RNorm	446614	S	1	3
0.83	Naproxen Dose	3023397	Naproxen [Mass] of Dose	Measurement	Lab Test	LOINC	4345-5	S	2	0
0.83	Naproxen 250 MG	1115070	Naproxen 250 MG	Drug	Clinical Drug Comp	RNorm	316325	S	104	49
0.83	Naproxen 25 MCGML	1115093	Naproxen 25 MCGML	Drug	Clinical Drug Comp	RNorm	317653	S	10	21
0.81	Naproxen 15 MCGML	21440189	Naproxen 15 MCGML	Drug	Clinical Drug Comp	RNormExtension	OMOP352644	S	1	2
0.81	Naproxen sodium	4175571	Naproxen sodium	Observation	Substance	SNOMED	4262007	S	1	0
0.80	Naproxen 0.5 MCGML	44179361	Naproxen 0.5 MCGML	Drug	Clinical Drug Comp	RNormExtension	OMOP3556084	S	1	4
0.80	Naproxen 150 MCGML	46241050	Naproxen 150 MCGML	Drug	Clinical Drug Comp	RNorm	1114867	S	1	7
0.80	Naproxen Oral Capsule	40054721	Naproxen Oral Capsule	Drug	Clinical Drug Form	RNorm	373002	S	130	8

Comment: [] Flag [] EQUAL [] Approve []

Approved / total: 0 / 31 0.0% of total frequency

Author: Vocabulary version: v5.0 10-JAN-1

Supplementary information 1 Summary on RA and weather.

Many people with rheumatoid arthritis (RA) believe that weather conditions can affect their symptoms, making them worse on certain days. However, scientific studies on this topic have shown mixed and inconclusive results (Abasolo et al., 2013; Aikman, 1997; Arber et al., 1994; Azzouzi & Ichchou, 2020; Drane et al., 1997; Gorin et al., 1999; Hollander, 1985; Hopkins, 2010; Patberg, 1987; Patberg, 2003; Patberg & Rasker, 2004; Rasker et al., 1986; Redelmeier & Tversky, 1996; Savage et al., 2014; Sibley, 1985; Smedslund & Hagen, 2011; Smedslund et al., 2009). Some studies suggest that weather, such as low temperature, high humidity, or changes in atmospheric pressure, might be associated with increased joint pain and stiffness in some RA patients. However, these effects are usually very small and not consistent among all individuals.

Other studies have not found any significant links between weather and RA symptoms. Overall, the scientific evidence does not strongly support the idea that weather directly causes or significantly worsens RA symptoms for most patients (Azzouzi & Ichchou, 2020; Patberg & Rasker, 2004).